
Final PhD Thesis Report

ECO-HEN

Dynamics of *Escherichia coli* in laying hens

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INTRODUCTION

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1. PhD Project team composition

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2. Abstract

The spread of bacterial antimicrobial resistant (AMR) determinants is a complex phenomenon whose features at different levels (population, bacterium, environment, etc.) must be considered for its accurate understanding and appropriate containment.

At the top level of this landscape are the human and animal population. Most human communities can be considered open populations where individuals are irregularly moving between diverse subpopulations (including semi-closed subpopulations like schools, hospitals, penitentiaries, etc.), adding a very difficult manageable component to the study of the flow of bacterial AMR determinants.

In contrast, intensive rearing animal systems, where animals live together in confined spaces and during variable time periods (from days to years), are closed populations where the above mentioned disadvantage is minimized. In special, laying hens, whose lifespan extend up to 90 weeks, are an excellent model, having the additional advantage that habitually the use of antimicrobials in almost negligible in eggs production

This thesis focus on the dynamics of AMR genes in *Escherichia coli* from a commercial layer farm where antibiotics were barely used. This farm was studied during 29 months encompassing five animal batches (B1 to B5). Batches B1 to B4 were checked eight times from day-old chicks to laying hens (about 82-85 weeks), whereas batch B5 was only checked four times from pullets (14 weeks) to laying hens (53 weeks)

Three different MacConkey agar plates (without antibiotics, with cefotaxime and with ciprofloxacin) were used for recovery of *E. coli* isolates from transport-boxes (first sampling of batches B1 to B4) and litter (all the remaining 32 samples)

In a whole, 687 *E. coli* isolates were detected, from which 272 were characterized by whole genome sequencing (WGS). Having in mind that up to 10 isolates were taken per culture media and sampling, a preliminary phylogenetic analysis served to detect 53 putative duplicated isolates that were discarded. Consequently, only 218 isolates were included into the final analysis.

Up to 32 AMR determinants were detected and 115 isolates harboured at least one. At isolate level, both integrons and multiresistance (MR) regions were identified, proving that AMR determinants were frequently linked.

Regarding plasmid replicons (PR), we detected at least one PR in 196 isolates. Although 11 different PRs were identified, only eight harboured AMR determinants in at least one isolate (IncF, IncI, IncX, IncK/B/O/Z, IncA/C2, IncQ, IncH e IncN). Finally, 30 clones (comprising between two and eight isolates) were detected.

Having in mind the different role of integrons, MR regions, plasmids and clones in AMR flow along the study, we focused the data analysis on the identification of different Russian dolls sets for AMR

determinants spread in this commercial farm detecting that the most common were the plasmid-clone set involving both single and linked (integron and MR regions) AMR determinants and single patterns, when only plasmids harboring AMR determinants or clones (with AMR determinants into the chromosome) were involved. In addition, events related to gain or losses of AMR determinants by plasmids or the gain or losses of AMR-containing plasmids itself by isolates were also recorded.

3. Introduction and Objectives

INTRODUCTION

1. Industrial egg production

1.1. Egg production and consumption

In 2021, 86.4 million tonnes of eggs were produced globally, with China being the leading country, accounting for 34% of global production (Poultry world, 2023). In 2018, the average egg consumption was 9.68 kg per person per year (International Egg Commission, 2019). Egg production is one of the most important food industry sectors in Europe.

Egg production in the European Union (EU) accounts for around 10% of global production (Windhorst, 2017). In the EU in 2020, 6 million tonnes of eggs were produced and an average of 13.8 kg per person per year was consumed (Hartmann, 2021). Of the eggs produced, a total of 467,359 tonnes were exported outside the EU in 2020, mainly to Japan (European Commission, 2021).

In 2021, Spain was the third largest producer of eggs in the EU, accounting for 12.3% of total production, behind France and Germany (Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, 2022). In Spain in 2021, annual per capita egg consumption was 13.7 kg/inhabitant and year and a total of 283,663 tonnes of eggs were exported that year, mainly to France (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2022). Eggs for consumption are exported for the most part (56.5% of exports), although hatching eggs and other egg products such as yolks or albumen are also exported. Furthermore, in 2020 the egg sector grew by 17.5% in turnover in Spain, generating 1,056 million euros in sales for retail consumption, 208 million more than in the previous year (Inprovo, 2021)

1.2. Laying hens

The EU has 380.5 million registered laying hens (2021 data). Of these hens, 78% are reared in conventional farms, i.e. in cages, while 22% of hens are reared in alternative farms, including free-range (13%), barn (8%) and organic (1%). Free-range farms are those where hens are kept in a house, free-range farms where hens are free-range and have access to fresh pasture and organic farms where hens consume feed from organic farming and are kept outdoors. Since 2016, when this study was initiated, and up to 2021, the number of hens on alternative farms in the EU has increased by 7.5% (Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, 2021).

47.07 million laying hens were registered in Spain in 2021, distributed among 21,683 farms. 73% of the hens registered in our country remain in these conventional farms. The hens registered on free-range farms account for 16% of the total, free-range hens for 9% and organic hens for 2%. Although the census of caged farms accounts for 73% of the total, the percentage of caged farms with respect to the total is only 36.7% in Spain (SITRAN?). In 2016, Spain had 43.6 million registered hens, 92.2% of them in conventional farms. Hens kept on alternative farms in 2016 accounted for 7.1% of the total, divided as follows: 4% free-range, 2.5% free-range and 0.6% organic.

1.3. Egg production structure

The structure of egg production is pyramidal. Production starts with lines of pure hens. These hens are genetically selected based on criteria such as disease resistance or quantity of eggs produced, among others, and will produce future generations of laying hens. These pure lines produce the so-called "grandparent" lines. At this point, a mating between pure lines takes place. From these lines, the "mother" or breeding lines are produced. At this step, a mating between the mixed lines takes place, resulting in the commercial animal lines (Ferryhough et al., 2020) (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1. Pyramid of commercial hen production (Own elaboration. Data from Ferryhough et al., 2019).

Day-old chicks are selected, vaccinated and transferred to the rearing farm. During the rearing period, the pullets are placed on the floor or in boxes until they are 16 to 18 weeks old, when they are transferred to the laying phase. After the laying phase, which lasts approximately 44 to 60 weeks, the hens are transported to the slaughterhouse for slaughter. During the laying period, eggs are collected daily (Figure 1.2) (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards), 2014). In order to extend the laying phase of the hens, a forced moult can be performed, which consists of subjecting the hens to a forced rest, which involves rejuvenation of the bird, resulting in involution of the ovary and oviduct. Laying stops for several weeks and is accompanied by a renewal of the plumage. Forced moulting is achieved by food deprivation

or specific diets (Cavero, 2012).

Figure 1.2. The basic egg production chain from breeding group to sale (Translated from EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards, 2014).

2. Antibiotics

Any substance that inhibits the growth and replication of bacteria or eliminates them completely can be called an antibiotic (Microbiology Society, 2021). Antibiotics can be classified according to their chemical structure and mechanism of action. The mechanisms of action of antibiotics are as follows: inhibition of cell wall synthesis, change of cell wall permeability, inhibition of protein synthesis, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis and inhibition of precursors of DNA synthesis (Reygaert, 2018) (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1. Outline of the main families of antibiotics classified by mechanism of action

<i>Mechanism of action</i>	<i>Antibiotic families</i>	<i>Interaction with bacteria</i>
Inhibition of cell wall synthesis	<i>b-lactams</i>	They covalently bind to and inhibit penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs). These PBPs are necessary to catalyze the cross-linking of the peptidoglycan layer of bacterial cell walls. When PBPs are inactivated by β -lactam antibiotics, the bacterial enzymes that

		hydrolyze the peptidoglycan cross-links during cell wall remodeling continue to function, further breaking down the cell wall. The result is bacterial rupture (Sykes et al., 2014).
Inhibition of protein synthesis	Aminoglycosides (30s) Macrolides (50s) Tetracyclines (30s) Phenicols (50s)	Bind to the small (30s) or large (50s) subunits of the ribosome preventing protein synthesis in bacteria (Molina et al. 2009).
Change in cell wall permeability (only in gram-negative bacteria)	Polymyxins	They increase the permeability of the outer membrane by binding the polypeptide to the lipopolysaccharide of the membrane of gram-negative bacteria (Molina et al. 2009).
Inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis	Fluoroquinolones	Interfere with DNA synthesis by inhibiting gyrase and topoisomerase enzymes (Higgins et al., 2003).
Inhibition of precursors of DNA synthesis	Sulphonamides Trimetoprim	Sulphonamides are analogues of para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) and compete with PABA for binding to dihydropteroate synthase (DHPS), thereby inhibiting dihydrofolic acid synthesis. Trimethoprim binds to dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR), thus blocking the conversion of dihydrofolic acid to tetrahydrofolic acid. (Wüthrich et al., 2019)

2.1. Mechanisms of antibiotic resistance

Antibiotic resistance is the loss of susceptibility of bacteria to the lethal or growth-inhibiting properties of an antibiotic agent (Morier, 2021), either through mutations or through the acquisition of antibiotic resistance genes. Many bacteria have the ability to acquire resistance to different antimicrobials by different mechanisms. Natural resistance can be intrinsic (naturally present in bacteria) or induced. Within intrinsic resistance, the mechanisms of resistance are the reduction of the impermeability of the outer membrane and the natural activity of efflux pumps (Reygaert, 2018).

Acquired resistance is the most problematic, as an antibiotic-sensitive bacterium can become resistant as a result of an evolutionary process whereby bacteria adapt to an antibiotic-containing environment through mutations in chromosomal DNA or by acquiring resistance genes through horizontal transfer (Clockaert et al., 2017).

In addition, natural selection plays a role in antimicrobial resistance. Bacteria that carry a favourable mutation or have acquired a resistance gene will be selected in an environment with selective pressure (presence of antibiotics), as opposed to sensitive bacteria that cannot survive in the environment. This results in a population of resistant bacteria, as they multiply and/or exchange genetic material (Figure 1.3) (Blázquez et al., 2002).

Figure 1.3. Natural selection process in antibiotic resistant bacteria (Own elaboration)

Both the acquisition of resistance genes and point mutations involve an energetic cost to the bacterium. Mutations are costly because they are aimed at modifying important biological functions in the cell (Melnyk et al., 2014), while the mobile genetic elements through which resistance genes are acquired provide bacteria with new adaptive tools, but also entail a metabolic burden that, in the absence of selection for the traits encoded by the genes, reduce the competitiveness of the bacteria carrying these mobile genetic elements (San Millán et al., 2017).

The mechanisms of antibiotic resistance are as follows (van Hoek et al., 2011) (Figure 1.4):

I. Permeability changes in the bacterial cell wall that restrict antimicrobial access to targets:

The change in permeability is achieved by modification of porins (both modification of expression and degradation), which are water channels through which antibiotics penetrate the bacteria. This method of resistance is effective against hydrophilic antibiotics such as tetracyclines and β -lactams, although the resistance achieved by this mechanism is low-level, so it is often associated with other resistance mechanisms, such as increased expression of efflux pumps (Munita et al., 2016).

II. Antibiotic expulsion from the cell by efflux pumps: efflux systems pump a wide variety of chemically and structurally unrelated compounds out of bacteria in an energydependent manner, without causing drug disruption or degradation (Blair et al., 2014). Pumps are

classified into families, depending on the substrate they use to catalyse transport, and the compounds they transport

III. Enzymatic modification and degradation of the antibiotic (Wright, 2004). Enzymatic modification and degradation can occur by transfer of functional groups, by hydrolysis of the antibiotic, or by other mechanisms such as reduction/oxidation.

- Hydrolysis: Many antibiotics have hydrolytically susceptible chemical bonds, the integrity of which is critical to their function. The β -lactamase enzymes, for example, hydrolyse the β -lactam ring of penicillins and cephalosporins. There are two main molecular strategies employed by lactamases to hydrolytically cleave the lactam ring and degrade the antibiotic: through the action of an active site nucleophile, or through the activation of water by a Zn centre²⁺.
- Functional group transfer: Transferase enzymes covalently modify antibiotics resulting in structural alterations that hinder binding to the target. Chemical strategies include acylation and phosphorylation, nucleotidylation, or ribosylation, among others. AAC and CAT acetyltransferases confer resistance to aminoglycosides and chloramphenicol, respectively.

IV. Alternative metabolic pathways to those inhibited by the antibiotic. Bacteria can acquire the property of obtaining substances with an alternative pathway to the one inhibited by the antibiotic. The *sul1* and *sul2* genes found in gram-negative bacteria, for example, encode resistant DHPS enzymes, i.e. they have the ability to discriminate between the inhibiting antibiotic and the substrate, binding to the substrate instead of the antibiotic in order to continue the metabolic pathway of folic acid (Sköld, 2000).

V. Modification and protection of antibiotic targets: Bacteria avoid antibiotic action by interfering with their target in two different ways:

- Protection of antibiotic targets: Proteins encoding resistance genes compete with the antibiotic to bind to the target. The *qnr* gene, for example, encodes a protein that competes with fluoroquinolones for binding to DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV (Munita et al., 2016).
- Modification of antibiotic targets: Bacteria modify, through chromosomal mutations, the targets on which the antibiotic acts so that the antibiotic cannot bind. In some cases, modification of the target structure requires other changes in the cell to compensate for the altered target characteristics. For example, mutations in the *gyrA*

and gyrB subunits of DNA gyrase or in the parE and parC subunits of topoisomerase prevent the binding of fluoroquinolones in both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria (Lambert et al., 2005).

VI. Overproduction of the target enzyme: This involves increasing the production of the antimicrobial target with the aim of saturating the antibiotic by increasing the number of available targets. This occurs, for example, in resistance to sulfonamides and trimethoprim. Bacteria increase the expression of target enzymes involved in folic acid synthesis (DHFR and DHPS), which are inhibited by TMP and SMX, respectively (Munita et al., 2016).

Figure 1.4. Diagram of the targets on which antibiotics act (left) and the different mechanisms of antibiotic resistance in bacteria (right) (Prepared by the authors).

3. *Escherichia coli* as an indicator of antibiotic resistance

E. coli is a facultative anaerobic gram-negative bacterium, belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae family. This bacterium is normally found in the large intestine of endothermic animals, including humans. Most strains of *E. coli* are harmless, although some serotypes, such as O157:H7 are pathogenic and can cause infections (Odonkor et al., 2013). These infections caused by *E. coli* are due to the acquisition of virulence genes by the bacterium and cause, in both humans and mammalian animals, three main clinical pictures: enteric disease, urinary tract infection and sepsis or meningitis. Combinations of these resistance genes have persisted in this bacterial species into specific pathotypes. Pathotypes causing intestinal disease include enteropathogenic (EPEC), enterohaemorrhagic (EHEC), enterotoxigenic (ETEC), enteroaggregative (EAEC) and enteroinvasive (EIEC) *E. coli*. Urinary tract infections are mainly caused by uropathogenic *E. coli* (UPEC), while the pathotype responsible for sepsis and meningitis is the so-called meningitis-associated *E. coli* (MNEC) (Kaper et al., 2004). In addition, the pathotype called avian pathogenic *E. coli* (APEC) causes

aerosacculitis, polyserositis, septicaemia and other mainly extra-intestinal diseases in chickens, turkeys and other avian species (Dho-Moulin, 1999).

However, most strains of *E. coli* are not pathogenic, and this bacterium is an important component of the gut microbiota of animals. *E. coli* present in healthy food-producing animals are considered good indicators of the selective pressure imposed by the use of antimicrobials in these animals, as they indicate levels of antimicrobial resistance in pathogenic bacteria of animal origin and provide information on reservoirs of resistant bacteria. Through horizontal gene exchange, commensal strains of *E. coli* may share acquired resistance genes with pathogens such as *Salmonella* spp. or pathogenic *E. coli*, especially in environments such as the gastrointestinal tract, where enormous species diversity and density allow for conjugation-mediated exchange of antimicrobial resistance genes between bacterial populations (Nyirabahizi et al., 2020). Some public surveillance reports on antimicrobial resistance in food-producing animal species, such as the EU reports generated by EFSA and ECDC, use commensal *E. coli* as an indicator of antimicrobial resistance (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

E. coli is the first colonising bacterium in the chick caecum during the first week of life. However, during the second week, *E. coli* is replaced by gram positive bacteria. Furthermore, *E. coli* easily survives in the environment, as it is a facultative anaerobe, and the likelihood of it coming into contact with animals on farms is high (Rychlik, 2020).

4. Horizontal transfer gene elements

4.1. Horizontal gene transfer

Horizontal gene transfer is the movement of genetic information between organisms. The transfer of genetic material between bacteria contributes greatly to the evolution and adaptation of bacteria, due to the acquisition of genes that endow bacteria with antibiotic or metal resistance, pathogenicity, or the ability to metabolise new substrates. Horizontal gene transfer is possible, in part, thanks to mobile genetic elements, such as plasmids, capable of mobilising genes in different environments, and transposable elements including integrons, transposons or insertion sequences (Bello-López et al., 2019).

The mechanisms of horizontal gene transfer are as follows (Figure 1.5):

- Transformation: a process involving a host cell and exogenous DNA present in the environment. The host bacterium internalises the exogenous DNA and integrates it into its genome by homologous recombination. The transformation is entirely directed by the host cell and all the proteins required for the process are encoded in its genome (Johnston et al., 2014).
- Transduction: in this case gene transfer is mediated by bacteriophages that can package segments of host DNA into their capsid and inject it into another host

bacterium when an environmental stimulus triggers cell lysis. When this occurs, the new genetic material injected into the virus-infected cell can recombine with chromosomal DNA generating a lytic or lysogenic cycle (Bello-López et al., 2019).

- Conjugation: Bacterial conjugation is considered one of the main culprits in the transfer of antibiotic-resistant genes. This method is the only one that involves contact between bacterial cells. Bacterial conjugation is a mode of gene transfer in which genetic material moves unidirectionally from the donor cell to the recipient cell either directly or via mobile genetic elements, followed by separation of the cells and further changes in the organisation or recombination of the combined genetic material within the recipient cell (Raleigh et al., 2013).

Figure 1.5. Diagram of the mechanisms of horizontal gene transfer: transformation, transduction and conjugation . The red lines represent the DNA of the donor bacteria and the blue lines the DNA of the recipient bacteria (own elaboration).

4.2. Plasmids

Plasmids are circular, double-stranded DNA molecules capable of replicating autonomously and independently of the bacterial chromosome. Plasmids have systems that ensure their autonomous replication, although they usually take advantage of the replication machinery encoded by the chromosome of the host bacterium. In addition, plasmids also have mechanisms that ensure stable inheritance during cell division (Carattoli, 2009). Plasmids also control their copy number: smaller plasmids are generally present at high copy number in the

bacterium, while larger plasmids are present at low copy number to reduce metabolic load and increase plasmid stability (Friehs, 2004).

Plasmid genomes often include a backbone that is conserved among plasmids of the same family with genes encoding plasmid-specific functions, such as replication and motility. In addition, plasmids carry accessory genes that confer relevant traits that favour bacterial adaptation, such as virulence or antibiotic resistance genes (Orlek et al., 2017).

Plasmid-mediated horizontal gene transfer is recognized as one of the main driving forces of bacterial adaptation and diversification. The spread of antibiotic resistance genes between bacteria of different taxa is one of the best examples of bacterial plasticity in response to various selective pressures (Smalla et al., 2015). Plasmids provide bacteria with new adaptive tools, but they also pose a metabolic burden by reducing the competitiveness of the plasmid-carrying bacterium when the plasmid does not confer an advantage to the bacterium. Although this reduction in competitiveness can be alleviated over time by compensatory evolution, the initial cost associated with the acquisition of plasmids by the bacterium is the main constraint to the replication of these genetic elements. In addition, any beneficial genes carried by the plasmid could eventually pass into the chromosome through homologous recombination (San Millan et al., 2017).

4.2.1. Incompatibility groups (Inc) and associated antibiotic resistance genes

Plasmids are classified according to their incompatibility group (Inc). Incompatibility groups represent the inability of two plasmids to coexist stably for several generations in the same bacterial cell line, as they have the same replication mechanism, so that plasmids that are incompatible with each other are assigned the same Inc group (Bozcal, 2019; Mutai et al., 2019). Furthermore, plasmids can be classified into conjugative and non-conjugative plasmids. Conjugative plasmids can be transmitted to other cells by themselves, whereas non-conjugative plasmids, usually small in size, need to use the transfer system of a co-resident conjugative plasmid to pass from the donor to the recipient cell (Yin et al., 1997).

Plasmids carrying known antibiotic resistance genes in enterobacteria include large plasmids (greater than 200 kb), usually conjugative, and small, often mobilisable plasmids. Typically, incompatibility groups are associated with different resistance genes (Table 1.2). Plasmids identified in enterobacteria include incompatibility clusters IncA/C, IncF, IncX, IncH, IncY, IncQ, IncN, IncI or ColE1, among others (Partridge et al., 2018).

Plasmid multilocus typing (pMLST) allows the classification of replicon types within a single incompatibility group, facilitating the tracking of plasmids between populations

(Robertson et al., 2019).

4.3. Integrons

4.3.1. Importance of integrons

Integrons are genetic elements that allow the capture and expression of exogenous genes. They play an important role in the spread of antibiotic resistance, especially among Gram negative bacteria (Gillings, 2014).

The structure of integrons includes a stable platform and a variable cassette site. The stable platform consists of the gene encoding integrase (IntI), which is a recombinase responsible for integrating and cleaving cassettes; a recombination site for cassette integration, called the attI site; and a Pc promoter, usually located between the integrase and the attI site, which promotes cassette expression. Cassettes are circular, non-replicative elements that usually contain a promoterless gene and a second recombination site called the attC site. These genes are made functional by integration into the integron and expression from the Pc promoter (Figure 1.6) (Escudero et al., 2015). This activity can result in the sequential insertion of multiple different cassettes to form a tandem structure, called a cassette, which can contain several different genes (Gillings et al., 2014).

Figure 1.6. Diagram of cassette insertion and excision in integrons . The stable platform, consisting of the IntI gene (green arrow), the Pc promoter (black arrow) and the attI insertion domain (red arrow). The circular cassette (blue arrow) is inserted by recombination of the attI site of the integron with the attC site of the cassette (own elaboration. Data from Escudero *et al.*, 2015).

In contrast to other mobile genetic elements carrying antibiotic resistance genes, integrons do not represent a high energetic cost for bacteria, with the cost of antibiotic resistance being 2-7 times less than plasmid resistance and 5-15 times less than chromosomal resistance. In *E. coli*, the SOS response has been shown to prevent the expression of integrases, the cost of which depends on the activity and antibiotic pressure in the

medium. This facilitates the adaptation of *E. coli* to the selective pressure caused by the presence of antibiotics, which explains its high frequency both in this bacterial species and in Enterobacteriaceae in general, as well as its maintenance and propagation even in antibiotic-free environments, which helps bacteria to maintain antibiotic resistance cassettes in the absence of selective pressure, keeping them available in case of antibiotic stress (Lacotte et al., 2017).

4.3.2. Classes of integrons

The amino acid sequences of integrases are used to classify integrons into class 1 (IntI1), class 2 (IntI2), class 3 (IntI3), class 4 (IntI4) and class 5 (IntI5) integrons (Deng et al., 2015; Kaushik et al., 2018):

- Class 1 integrons: These are the most ubiquitous and common in both pathogenic and non-pathogenic bacteria. They are considered to be directly related to the Tn402-type transposons and associated with the Tn3 family of transposons. Their structure has a conserved 5' region containing the integrase gene, the promoter and the attI site. The 3' region, also conserved, contains the truncated but functional qacEΔ1 gene encoding resistance to quaternary ammonium compounds, the sul1 gene encoding resistance to sulphonamides, an open reading frame (Orf5) of unknown function, and other sequences that differ from integron to integron. The variable regions of class 1 integrons contain resistance cassettes as well as attC recombination sites (Figure 1.7) (Messier et al., 2001). Although class 1 integrons are associated with a variety of resistance gene cassettes, most of these integrons contain an aadA resistance gene, which encodes resistance to streptomycin/spectinomycin, and trimethoprim resistance genes are also frequently detected. Class 1 integrons isolated from bacteria implicated in human infections also frequently harbour gene cassettes encoding resistance to β-lactams (Deng et al., 2015).

Figure 1.7. General structure of a class 1 integron (Own elaboration. Data from Messier *et al.*, 2021).

- Class 2 integrons: Class 2 integrons, commonly identified in gram-negative bacterial species, are usually found associated with the Tn7 family of

transposons. Typically, their conserved 3' region contains 5 tns genes (*tnsA*, *tnsB*, *tnsC*, *tnsD* and *tnsE*) that function in transposon movements, mediating the mobility of the class 2 integron through preferential insertion at a unique site within bacterial chromosomes. The classical structure of class 2 integrons features genetic cassettes, such as dihydrofolate reductase (*dfrA1*), streptotricin acetyltransferase (*sat1*) and aminoglycoside adenyltransferase (*aadA1*), which confer resistance to trimethoprim, streptotricin and streptomycin/spectinomycin, respectively (Figure 1.8), although new cassette rearrangements and resistance genes have been reported and identified in the last decade (Deng et al., 2015).

Figure 1.8. Schematic of the classical structure of a class 2 integron . (Own elaboration. Data from Deng et al., 2015).

- Class 3 integrons: Associated with Tn402, they have a prevalence of 0-10% in gram-negative bacteria. Class 3 integrons, first discovered in the bacterial species *Serratia marcescens*, evolve rapidly, colonising new species and acquiring new resistance cassettes. Most class 3 integrons carry in their cassettes genes for resistance to β -lactams, in particular *blaIMP* , *blaGES* and *blaOXA* , and to aminoglycosides (Kaushik et al., 2018).
- Class 4 and 5 integrons: Class 4 integrons have been identified in the bacterial species *Vibrio cholerae*, and may contain more than 200 cassettes that include genes that favour adaptation, such as antibiotic resistance or pathogenicity genes (Deng et al., 2015). As for class 5 integrons, only one has been identified in a *Vibrio salmonicida* transposon carrying the trimethoprim resistance gene *dfrA1* (Coque-Gonzalez, 2005).

Integrons can also be classified according to their genetic context as motile (MIs) or chromosomal (CIs). ICs can carry up to hundreds of cassettes and are not usually involved in antibiotic resistance. MIs, on the other hand, carry a limited number of genetic cassettes and are often implicated in the spread of antimicrobial resistance (Domingues et al., 2012).

4.4. Transposons and insertion sequences

Transposons play an important role in the responsiveness and adaptability of bacteria that carry them to environmental stresses.

Transposons are mobile genetic elements that can "jump" to different locations within a genome (Li et al., 2020). Transposons encode their own genetic information needed to move from one place in the genome to another. This transposition is carried out by transposase enzymes (Pajunen et al., 2010).

Insertion sequences (IS) are among the smallest mobile genetic elements. They can move within a genome or horizontally between genomes as part of other mobile genetic elements such as bacteriophage viruses or plasmids, playing an important role in the organisation of the genome of the bacteria that carry them (Siguier et al., 2014). More than 4,500 IS, belonging to 29 different families, have been identified. These elements, typically smaller than 3 kpb in size, are capable of independent transposition and are often flanked by short terminal inverted repeats (IRs) that carry one or two open reading frames encoding gene products essential for their mobility. DNA excision and strand transfer are catalysed by a transposon-specific enzyme, transposase. Another common feature of ISs is the duplication of a target site that results in short direct repeats (DRs) flanking the IS (Figure 1.9) (Siguier et al., 2014; Vandecraena et al., 2017).

Insertion sequences can act autonomously or be associated with transposons and, like transposons, encode their own tools for transposition. Insertion sequence common regions (ISCRs) are often associated with resistance and virulence genes. They are similar to IS, but lack terminal inverted repeats and are thought to be transposed by a rolling circle mechanism (Deng et al., 2009).

In a compound transposon, two insertion sequences span one or more genes. These composite transposons can mobilise between unrelated bacteria, having a major impact on the adaptive capacity of the host genome (Figure 1.9), whereas single transposons are not bordered by IS (Casacuberta et al., 2013).

Figure 1.9. A. Structure of an insertion sequence . ORF: Open reading frame. IR: Short terminal inverted repeats. DR: Direct short repeats. B. Structure of a compound transposon (Own elaboration, data from Casacuberta *et al.*, 2013 Siguier *et al.*, 2014 and Vandecraena *et al.*, 2017).

5. The problem of antibiotic resistance

Antibiotic resistance is currently one of the greatest threats to global public health. The misuse and overuse of antibiotics in both human and animal health has led to a growing problem of antibiotic resistance. In addition, the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, i.e. those that act against a wide range of pathogenic micro-organisms as a first line of therapy, has exacerbated the problem. For this reason, the number of infections whose treatment has become more complicated is increasing. Among the diseases that have become more difficult to treat are gonorrhoea, pneumonia and tuberculosis. This difficulty in treating infections results in prolonged hospital stays and increased mortality (WHO, 2020).

The O'Neill report, commissioned by the UK government and published in final form in 2016, analyses the growing problem of antibiotic resistance and the reasons why action is needed to combat it, and provides an overview of the solutions that should be implemented. In addition, it examines the role of public awareness campaigns, the need to improve hygiene, reduce contamination of agriculture and the environment, improve global surveillance, introduce rapid diagnostics, vaccines and so on. Finally, the paper examines how these solutions can be funded and explores ways to build political consensus around them (O'Neill, 2016).

The report estimates that, in Europe, deaths caused by multi-resistant bacteria are 33,000 each year, generating an additional cost of 1.5 billion euros per year and, globally, an estimated 700,000 deaths per year. It is also estimated that by 2050, antibiotic resistance will be one of the leading causes of death in the world, killing 10 million people each year, more than diseases such as cancer or diabetes (O'Neill, 2016).

In order to address the problem of antibiotic resistance, laws and plans to reduce the use of antibiotics in production animals have been adopted at European and national level. The Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) and WHO are cooperating to monitor the use of antimicrobials in animals. Surveillance systems, such as the National Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring System (NARMS) for enteric bacteria and the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network (EARS-Net), strive to collect information on antimicrobial consumption and antimicrobial resistance in both human and animal health (Ma et al., 2021).

In 2003 the European Commission established a regulation on additives in animal feed in which the use of antibiotics as growth promoters and feed additives was banned (EC No. 1831/2003). In 2019 the European parliament and the EU Council established a regulation (EU 2019/6) on veterinary medicinal products, which states that "antibiotic medicinal products should not be used for prophylactic purposes" and recommends antibiograms to ensure effective treatment. In addition, a regulation of the European Parliament and Council (EU 2021/1756) has been published and will enter into force in 2022 to extend the ban on the use of some antimicrobials in animals and

products imported into the EU from third countries.

At national level, a Royal Decree was issued in 2018 (RD 191/2018) establishing the electronic transmission of data on veterinary prescriptions of antibiotics for foodproducing animals for human consumption. In addition, the National Plan against Antibiotic Resistance (PRAN), adopted in 2014, aims to reduce the risk of selection and dissemination of antibiotic resistance in food-producing animal species.

6. Use of antibiotics in food-producing animals

The overuse of antimicrobials in animal feed has led to an increase in antibacterial resistance. Article 57 of the above-mentioned EU Regulation 2019/6 requires mandatory reporting of sales and use of antimicrobials used in animals to enable the evaluation of the use of antimicrobials in food-producing animals. The report with this data, called the European Surveillance Report on Antimicrobial Consumption in Veterinary Medicine (ESVAC), is published annually by the European Medicines Agency (EMA).

In 2020, among the 31 countries included in the above-mentioned report, 89 mg/PCU of antibiotics for production animals have been sold, making a total of 5,507.4 tonnes of antibiotics. Spain is the seventh country in the list with the highest sales (154.3 mg/PCU), behind Cyprus, Poland, Italy, Portugal, Hungary and Bulgaria. In both Spain and Europe, the antibiotic with the highest sales in 2020 was penicillin, accounting for 34.2% of total sales in Spain and 31.1% of total sales in Europe, followed by tetracyclines, accounting for 22.5% and 26.7% of total sales in Spain and Europe, respectively (Figure 1.10).

Furthermore, in Spain, 52.7% of antibiotics for production animals sold in 2020 were destined for pigs and only 11% for poultry (European Medicines Agency, European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption, 2020).

Figure 1.10. Antimicrobial sales for food-producing animals, in mg/PCU, of the different classes of veterinary antimicrobials in 31 European countries in 2020 (European Medicines Agency, European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption, 2021).

Between 2010 and 2014, sales of antibiotics for production animals in Spain increased from 295.5 mg/PCU to 418.8 mg/PCU. However, from that year until 2020, sales decreased by 63% due to adopted national plans aimed at reducing antibiotic resistance (Figure 1.11) (European Medicines Agency, European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption, 2020). As for sales of antibiotics classified as clinically important (Fluoroquinolones, polymyxins and 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins), these accounted for 2.9% of total sales of antibiotics for production animals in 2020. Polymyxin sales in Spain fell by almost 99% from 2010 to 2020, fluoroquinolone sales by 42%, and sales of 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins by 57.2%.

Figure 1.11. Sales of antibiotics for production animals expressed in mg/PCU in Spain, from 2010 to 2021. (Own elaboration. Data from European Medicines Agency, European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption, 2022).

7. Antibiotic resistance in food-producing animals

7.1. Antibiotic resistance in food-producing animals bacteria

Antibiotic-resistant bacteria are transmitted from animals to humans through food of animal

origin (meat, eggs...) or through vegetables contaminated by irrigation with water contaminated with these bacteria (CDC, 2019).

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) report on the levels of antimicrobial resistance in different bacterial species isolated from healthy production animals (calves, pigs, turkeys, broilers and laying hens) through reports synthesising data provided by EU Member States (MSs).

Resistance levels in these reports are classified according to the percentage of isolates showing resistance to the tested antimicrobials: Rare (1-10%), moderate (>10-20%), high (>20-50%), very high (>50-70%) and extremely high (>70%) (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

According to data from the latest report published by EFSA and ECDC in March 2022, in the indicator *E. coli* bacterial species, the most common antibiotic resistances in Europe were detected against ampicillin, tetracycline, sulfonamides and trimethoprim (Figure 1.13). In all four animal species where indicator *E. coli* resistance rates were analysed (calves, pigs, turkeys and broilers), these antibiotics showed high and very high levels of resistance, except for trimethoprim resistance in calves, which showed moderate levels. Resistance levels to clinically important antibiotics fluoroquinolones were high and very high in turkeys and broilers, respectively, and moderate in calves and pigs (Figure 1.13). For the other clinically important antibiotics (3rd generation cephalosporins, colistin and azithromycin), the levels of resistance to these antimicrobials were low or very low in all four animal species studied, except for azithromycin resistance in broiler turkeys, which was moderate (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

Isolates susceptible to the 14 antimicrobials tested (FS) were 50.3% in calves, 35.6% of the total in pigs, and 28.6% in broilers and 25.7% in turkeys, while multi-resistant isolates (resistant to three or more different antimicrobial groups) accounted for 46% of the total in broiler turkeys, 42.4% in broilers, 37.3% in pigs and 32.3% in calves (Figure 1.12) (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

In Spain, the antibiotics against which the highest levels of resistance were observed in indicator *E. coli* were, as in Europe, tetracycline, ampicillin, sulphonamides and trimethoprim (Figure 1.12). Resistance levels to these antibiotics were high and very high in all species except for trimethoprim in broilers and calves, where resistance was moderate (Figure 1.12).

For clinically important antibiotics, resistance to colistin, azithromycin and third generation cephalosporins was low and very low in all species studied, however, although resistance to fluoroquinolones was low in calves, it was high in pigs and very high in the two poultry species included in the report (Figure 1.12). The percentage of isolates that were sensitive to all antimicrobials tested ranged from 5.9 to 44.1%, depending on the species, with the lowest

percentage in pigs and the highest in calves, and multi-resistant isolates accounted for 76.7% of the total in pigs, 53.5% in turkeys and 31.2% in broilers and calves (Figure 1.12) (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

Figure 1.12. Resistance rates of indicator *E. coli* to antibiotics in production animals in 2019 and 2020 . The horizontal dashed lines show the cut-off points in the classification of resistance: below the yellow line the level of resistance is considered low or very low, above the yellow line the level of resistance is considered moderate, above the green line high, above the blue line very high and above the red line extremely high. Chart A: Data for Spain. Chart B: Data for Europe. FS: Isolates sensitive to all antimicrobials tested. MR: Multidrug-resistant isolates. TMP: Trimethoprim. TET: Tetracycline. SMX: Sulfamethoxazole. CIP: Ciprofloxacin. AMP: Ampicillin (own elaboration. Data from EFSA, ECDC, 2021).

In the year this study started (2016), resistance rates in both Spain and Europe in poultry (turkeys and broilers) were higher than in the last report issued (EFSA and ECDC, 2016; EFSA and ECDC, 2022): there was a decrease in resistance in all antibiotics from 2016 to 2020. Notably, colistin resistance levels in Spain in both species went from low levels of resistance (1.9%-3%) to rare levels (0%) and for some antibiotics, such as ampicillin, tetracycline and ciprofloxacin, resistance levels decreased significantly from extremely high levels of resistance in some of the avian species to very high levels (Figure 1.13).

Figure 1.13. Resistance rates of indicator *E. coli* to antibiotics in poultry in 2016 and 2020 . The horizontal dashed lines show the cut-off points in the resistance classification: below the yellow line the level of resistance is considered low or very low, above the yellow line the level of resistance is considered moderate, above the green line high, above the blue line very high and above the red line extremely high. Chart A: Data for Spain. Chart B: Data for Europe. FS: Isolates sensitive to all antimicrobials tested. MR: Multidrug-resistant isolates. TMP: Trimethoprim. TET: Tetracycline. SMX: Sulfamethoxazole. CIP: Ciprofloxacin. AMP: Ampicillin (Prepared by the authors, data from EFSA, ECDC, 2016; EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

7.2. Antibiotic use and resistance in laying hens

Only 11.1% of the antibiotics sold in Europe in 2020 were destined for poultry (European Medicines Agency, European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption, 2021).

Antibiotics authorised for laying hens in Spain are scarce. Table 1.3 shows the data collected from the Online Information Centre for Veterinary Medicines of the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products (AEMPS) (CIMAVet:

<https://cimavet.aemps.es/cimavet/publico/home.html>. Date of consultation: 2022): the

antibiotics authorised for laying hens, to which families they belong, and their indications for use

Table 1.3. Antibiotics permitted in Spain for laying hens and their indications for use (CIMA Vet data, 2021).

Familia	Antibiótico	Indicaciones
Tetracycline	Oxytetracycline	Sepsis, respiratory infections and gastrointestinal infections
	Clortetraciclina hidrocloreuro	Treatment and control of respiratory and systemic infections, Mycoplasmosis, Pasteurellosis
Pleuromutilins	Chlortetracycline hydrochloride	Treatment and metaphylaxis of chronic respiratory disease (CRD) and aerosacculitis caused by strains of <i>Mycoplasma gallisepticum</i>
Aminoglycosides	Neomycin	Nonspecific diarrhoea and salmonellosis, colibacillosis
Macrolide	Tylosin	Treatment and prevention of Chronic Respiratory Disease (CRD) caused by strains of <i>Mycoplasma</i> and treatment of necrotic enteritis caused by <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> strains.

Antibiotic resistance studies in laying hens are scarce and consequently, the data are under represented compared to other animal production species.

Antibiotic resistance data from EFSA and ECDC monitoring between 2019 and 2020 in *Salmonella* spp. isolates from laying hens in Europe show lower resistance values than in other production poultry species, such as turkeys or broilers. Multi-resistant *Salmonella* spp. isolates in laying hens constituted 6% of the total, compared to 41.8% of multiresistant isolates in broilers. In addition, fluoroquinolone resistance levels of *Salmonella* spp. isolates in Europe were moderate in laying hens, while in broilers the levels of resistance to these antibiotics were high (Nalidixic acid) and very high (Ciprofloxacin). Resistance to fluoroquinolones in *Salmonella* spp. isolates from laying hens from Spain was also low, while in broilers resistance was considered very high (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

In other studies in Europe with indicator *E. coli* isolates from laying hens (Harisberg et al., 2010; Van Hoorebeke et al., 2011), the percentages of multi-resistance were between 28 and 30% of the total, and the percentages of isolates susceptible to all tested antimicrobials were

between 55 and 60% of the total. In broiler chickens in Spain in 2011, these percentages were significantly different: FS isolates accounted for only 5.9% of the total, while multi-resistant isolates accounted for 79.3% (EFSA and ECDC, 2011). In both the *E. coli* indicator and *Salmonella* spp. resistance studies, resistance rates in bacteria isolated from laying hens were relatively low compared to other animal production species.

However, in a study carried out in *E. coli* from laying hens on Spanish farms in 2018 (Rivera-Gomis et al., 2021 (a); Rivera-Gomis et al., 2021 (b)), they were extremely high in sulphonamides, very high in tetracycline, trimethoprim and ciprofloxacin; and high in ampicillin, nalidixic acid, cephalosporins, azithromycin, meropenem and colistin. These levels of resistance in laying hens are significantly high and well above those observed in the other studies carried out in this animal species mentioned above.

OBJECTIVES

Some antibiotic-resistant bacteria can be transmitted from production animals to humans via food. Although levels of antibiotic resistance are relatively low in bacteria isolated from laying hens compared to other animal production species, antibiotic-resistant bacteria can be transferred to eggs, which are part of the human diet, posing a public health problem.

Studies of the transmission dynamics of antibiotic resistance genes carried out in commercial egg production farms are scarce compared to those carried out in other production animals, so the present thesis aims to fill the gap in the knowledge of the transmission and dynamics of antibiotic resistant bacteria in this scenario.

Therefore, the overall objective proposed for this thesis was to understand the transmission dynamics of antibiotic resistant *E. coli* in commercial egg production.

To achieve the general objective, the following specific objectives were addressed:

1. To search for resistance genes in complete gene sequences of *E. coli* isolates isolated from animals and eggshells in order to identify which resistance genes are present on farm.
2. To study the dynamics of antibiotic resistance genes between the different stages of egg production.
3. To identify mobile genetic elements involved in the dissemination of resistance genes.

- **Expected impact:**

- **Scientific impact:** The data collected in this thesis may be useful in other similar studies. This thesis is one of the few longitudinal studies of antibiotic resistance in laying hen farms, and the only one that studies the animals from their arrival on the farm until the end of the laying phase.
- **Societal and policy impact:** The EFSA and ECDC antimicrobial resistance reports do not include data on indicator *E. coli* from laying hens. This and similar studies demonstrate

the importance of monitoring for resistant *E. coli* in these types of farms. Therefore, it would be interesting to add this bacterium-animal species biomicroscope to the European surveillance of antibiotic resistance in food-producing animals.

4. *Materials and Methods*

PRE-WORK MATERIAL

1. *E. coli* isolates

A collection of 687 *E. coli* isolates from a commercial egg production farm was used (Tables 2.1 and 2.2).

The existing information on these isolates was: batch and sampling, date and location where they were sampled and culture medium on which they were isolated in the laboratory. In addition, for 643 of these isolates, the database contained information on the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of 14 antibiotics: ampicillin (AMP), chloramphenicol (CHL), ciprofloxacin (CIP), nalidixic acid (NAL), tetracycline (TET), trimethoprim (TMP), sulfamethoxazole (SMX), cefotaxime (CTX), ceftazidime (TAZ), meropenem (MERO), gentamicin (GEN), azithromycin (AZI), colistin (COL) and tigecycline (TGC). Isolates resistant to cefotaxime and/or ceftazidime also had MIC information for β -lactam antibiotics (cefepime, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, ceftazidime + clavulanic acid, ceftazidime, ceftazidime + clavulanic acid, ertapenem, imipenem, meropenem and temocycline).

To obtain these isolates, five batches of animals were sampled from a commercial egg farm located in southeastern Spain from March 2016 to October 2018. In flocks 1 to 4, monitoring was initiated on day-old chicks coming from different commercial houses. In flock 5, monitoring was started on 14-week-old pullets. Each flock, of different sizes: flock 1 (L1), size: 56,640; flock 2 (L2), size: 67,000; flock 3 (L3), size: 62,900 and flock 4 (L4), size: 57,600, entered the farm on a different date (figure 2.1). Each batch was first in a grower house, until 18-19 weeks of age. Batch 1 was located in hatchery 1 (A), while batches 2, 3 and 4 were located in hatchery 2 (B) (Table 2.1). During the laying phase, which runs from 18-19 weeks of age until approximately 85 weeks of age, animals from each of the batches were located in different laying houses: Batches 1 and 5 were located in house C, batch 2 in house D, batch 3 in house E, and batch 4 in house F (Figure 2.1).

Each flock was sampled 8 times, collecting 15 floors from transport boxes (between 15 and 50 grams each floor) of day-old chicks and 10 samples of 100g from the faeces collection belts of the houses in which the animals were placed. Therefore, no samples were collected from individual animals. Subscribe to DeepL Pro to edit this document. Visit www.DeepL.com/pro for more information.

Day-old chicks were first sampled on arrival at the farm (L1 to L4), constituting sampling 1 (M1).

During the growing phase, two samplings were carried out: sampling 2 (M2) at 2 weeks of chick life

(L1 to L4), and sampling 3 (M3) at 13-15 weeks of chick life, depending on the flock sampled (L1 to L5). During the laying phase, a total of 5 samples were taken: at weeks 23-24 (M4, L1 to L5), 38-39 (M5, L1 to L5), 52-54 (M6, L1 to L5), 67-69 (M7, L1 to L4) and 82-85 (M8, L1 to L4).

In addition, egg samples were also collected at each of the sampling points during the laying phase (M4-M8).

Colistin was administered on an ad hoc basis to animals in batches 1 and 2, at 24 and 23 weeks of age, respectively. No other antibiotics were administered during the egg production cycle on the farm.

Figure 2.1 shows a schematic of the on-farm sampling, including the dates on which each flock was sampled.

Figure 2.1. Schematic of farm samplings

The 10 g of faeces collected from each box were diluted in 90 mL of peptone water, and kept for 1 h at room temperature before serial dilutions in peptone water. 0.1 mL of the last three dilutions was seeded on MacConkey agar plates without antibiotic, with cefotaxime (1 mg/L), ciprofloxacin (0.125 mg/L) and colistin (4mg/L) and incubated at 37°C for 20-24 h. Ten lactose-fermenting colonies from each plate were picked and the bacterial species was identified by amplification of the UidA gene (Cabal et al., 2013). The following tables show the distribution of isolates obtained per batch and sampling, both from animals (table 2.1) and eggs (table 2.2)

Table 2.1. Summary of the distribution of the 603 *E. coli* isolates obtained from animals by batch and sampling . The isolation medium is indicated in brackets.

Batch and sampling	No. isolated (Medium isolation)	Batch and sampling	No. isolated (Medium isolation)
L1M1	21 (10 G, 10 CIP, 1 COL)	L2M1	20 (10 G, 10 CIP)
L1M2	31 (8 G, 10 CIP, 10 CTX, 3 COL)	L2M2	26 (10 G, 10 CIP, 6 CTX)
L1M3	26 (10 G, 10 CIP, 6 CTX)	L2M3	20 (10 G, 10 CTX)
L1M4	30 (10 G, 10 CIP, 10 CTX)	L2M4	20 (10 G, 10 CTX)
L1M5	10 (10 G)	L2M5	10 (10 G)
L1M6	10 (8 G, 2 CIP)	L2M6	9 (9 G)
L1M7	10 (10 G)	L2M7	19 (10 G, 9 CTX)
L1M8	16 (10 G, 6 CTX)	L2M8	10 (10 G)
L3M1	26 (10 G, 9 CIP, 7 CTX)	L4M1	20 (10 G, 10 CIP)
L3M2	28 (8 G, 10 CIP, 10 CTX)	L4M2	20 (10 G, 10 CIP)
L3M3	20 (10 G, 10 CTX)	L4M3	20 (10 G, 10 CTX)
L3M4	23 (10 G, 10 CIP, 3 CTX)	L4M4	30 (10 G, 10 CIP, 10 CTX)
L3M5	10 (10 G)	L4M5	10 (10 G)
L3M6	19 (10 G, 9 CIP)	L4M6	10 (10 G)
L3M7	10 (10 G)	L4M7	20 (10 G, 10 CTX)
L3M8	19 (10 G, 9 CTX)	L4M8	10 (10 G)
L5M3	10 (10 G)	L5M5	10 (10 G)
L5M4	10 (10 G)	L5M6	10 (10 G)

G: Isolate on McK medium without antibiotics. CIP: Isolate on McK medium with ciprofloxacin (0.125 mg/L), CTX: Isolate on McK medium with cefotaxime (1 mg/L), COL: Isolate on medium with colistin (x mg/L).

Table 2.2. Distribution of the 64 *E. coli* isolates obtained from eggs by batch and sampling . The isolation medium is indicated in brackets.

Batch and sampling	No. isolated (Medium isolation)	Batch and sampling	No. isolated (Medium isolation)
L1M4	2 (1 G, 1 CTX)	L2M4	3 (3 G)
L1M5	5 (5 G)	L2M5	2 (2 G)
L1M6	4 (2 G, 2 CIP)	L2M6	2 (2 G)
L1M7	2 (2 G)	L2M7	1 (1 G)
L1M8	1 (1 G)	L2M8	2 (2 G)
L3M4	4 (2 G, 2 CIP)	L4M4	2 (2 G)
L3M5	2 (2 G)	L4M5	2 (2 G)
L3M6	4 (2 G, 2 CIP)	L4M6	2 (2 G)
L3M7	2 (2 G)	L4M7	4 (4 G)
L3M8	2 (2 G)	L4M8	7 (7 G)
L5M4	2 (2 G)	L5M6	5 (5 G)
L5M5	2 (2 G)		

G: Isolated on general medium without antibiotics. CIP: Isolate on medium with ciprofloxacin (0.125 mg/L), CTX: Isolate on medium with cefotaxime (1 mg/L).

Antibiograms were performed on 44 *E. coli* isolates obtained on cefotaxime medium. These isolates corresponded to the last samples of the first four batches (L1M8, L2M7, L3M7 and L4M8) and the third sample of batch 4 (L4M3). Antibiograms were performed using the broth dilution method with commercial EUVSEC plates (Sensititre®, ThermoFisher) (see methods section 2).

2. Culture media, Antibiotics and commercial kits

2.1. Culture media

Brain-Heart Infusion (BHI) (Laboratorios conda S.A., Madrid, Spain). Fifty-two g of medium was suspended in 1 L of distilled water.

- Muller-Hinton liquid (Oxoid Lda., Basingstoke, Hampshire, GB). Twenty-one g of the medium was suspended in 1 L of distilled water.
- Saline solution (SS) 0.85%. 8.5 g NaCl was suspended in 1 L of distilled water. All media, once prepared, were autoclaved for 15 min at 121°C.
- Blood Agar (Oxoid Lda., Basingstoke, Hampshire, GB)

2.2. Antibiotics

Antibiotic powders (Sigma-Aldrich) were dissolved in the solvent indicated by the manufacturer, and

prepared in 1000x concentration stocks (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3. Antibiotics used, final and stock concentrations, and solvent in which each antibiotic was dissolved.

Antibiotic used	Final concentration of work	Stock concentration	Solvent
Chloramphenicol	64 mg/L	64 mg/mL	Ethanol
Trimethoprim	32 mg/L	32 mg/mL	Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)
Cefotaxime	1 mg/L	1 mg/mL	Water

2.3. Commercial kits

- Syber safeH (Invitrogen, Eugene, OR, USA)
- Taq PCR MasterMix (Qiagen)
- H₂O RNase-Free (Qiagen)
- Commercial EUVSEC and EUVSEC2 Enterobacteriaceae plates (Sensititre®, ThermoFisher)

3. Oligonucleotides

All the oligonucleotides used (STAB VIDA, Spain) to carry out the PCRs were used at a concentration of 100 µM. Table 2.4 lists the oligonucleotides used, the recommended hybridisation temperature for each pair of oligos, and the size of the fragment they amplify

Table 2.4. Oligonucleotides used in PCR reactions

Name	5'→3' sequences	Appropriate hybridisation temperature (°C)	Amplifying fragment size (bp)
dfrA36-F	TCGAATCAATCCCTGAAAGG	55	249
dfrA36-R	CCGCACCAAAGTATGATCC		
UidA-U	TGTGGGCATTTCAGTCTGGAT	55	168
UidA-L	ACTCCACACATACCACCACGCTTG		

METHODS

1. Isolation and identification of *E. coli*

In order to find isolates simultaneously resistant to trimethoprim and chloramphenicol to identify isolates similar to those in which the dfrA36 resistance gene was identified, 1 g of faeces was diluted in 9

mL of peptone water following the same methodology used for the isolation of the initial collection of bacteria (Moreno et al., 2019). MacConkey agar plates were used at final Trimethoprim and Chloramphenicol concentrations of 32 mg/L and 64 mg/L, respectively.

Samples 7 and 8 of the first four batches were also seeded on cefotaxime (1mg/L) medium to identify cephalosporin-resistant isolates.

The bacterial species of the colonies was identified by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), amplifying the UidA gene. Table 2.4 shows the conditions of the PCR, which was performed in a final volume of 20 μ L

2. Antimicrobial susceptibility study of E. coli

Antibiograms were performed using the broth microdilution method on the 44 isolates for which the phenotypic resistance profile was not previously known. Antibiograms were performed in the same way as for the isolates in the collection. For inoculum preparation, a bacterial colony of each isolate, previously seeded on blood agar, was taken and suspended in 5 mL of SS until a turbidity of 0.5 on the McFarland scale was obtained. 50 μ L of this suspension was inoculated into 9.950 mL of Muller Hinton broth to obtain a 1:1000 dilution. This dilution was dispensed onto commercial EUVSEC plates (Sensititre®, ThermoFisher), containing serial dilutions of 14 different antimicrobials: Nalidixic acid, Ampicillin, Azithromycin, Cefotaxime, Ceftazidime, Ciprofloxacin, Chloramphenicol, Colistin, Gentamicin, Meropenem, Sulfonamides, Tetracycline, Tigecycline and Trimethoprim (Table 2.5). The inoculated plates were incubated at 37°C for 20-24 hours. After the incubation time, the panels were read with a mirror. The epidemiological cut-off points suggested by the European Committee for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) were used for MIC interpretation (Table 2.5).

Table 2.5. Antibiotics contained in the EUVSEC commercial panel (Sensitre@, ThermoFisher) and the range of dilutions of each in mg/L . The third column shows the cut-off point in mg/L, above which a bacterium is considered microbiologically resistant to the antibiotic.

Antibiotic	Dilution range (mg/L)	Cut-off points (mg/L) EUCAST
Ampicillin	1-64	>8
Azithromycin	2-64	>16
Cefotaxime	0.25-4	>0.25
Ceftazidime	1.5-8	>0.5
Chloramphenicol	8-128	>16
Ciprofloxacin	0.015-8	>0.064
Colistin	1-16	>2
Gentamicin	0.5-32	>2
Meropenem	0.03-16	>0.125
Nalidixic acid	4-128	>16
Sulfamethoxazole	8-1024	>64
Tetracycline	2-64	>8
Tigecycline	0.25-8	>1
Trimethoprim	0.25-32	>2

Isolates found to be resistant to cefotaxime or ceftazidime and sensitive to meropenem were tested with a commercial EUVSEC2 microdilution panel (Sensitre@, ThermoFisher) using the same methodology as for the EUVSEC panels. In case of FOT and/or TAZ resistant isolates with the same resistance profile from the same batch and sampling, only one of the isolates, i.e. a total of 100 isolates, was subjected to a second antibiogram.

This plate is used to confirm the presence of beta-lactamase enzymes ESBL and AmpC (Table 2.6) and contains serial dilutions of the following β -lactam antibiotics: cefepime, cefotaxime, cefotaxime + clavulanic acid, ceftazidime, ceftazidime + clavulanic acid, ertapenem, imipenem, meropenem and temocycline (Table 2.6). FOT/CLAV and TAZ/CLAV are considered positive when clavulanic acid inhibits the β -lactam antibiotic, i.e. when the MIC of these antibiotics together is lower by at least two dilutions than the MIC obtained in the EUVSEC panel.

Table 2.6. Antibiotics contained in the EUVSEC2 commercial panel (Sensititre®, ThermoFisher) and the range of dilutions of each in mg/L . The third column shows the cut-off point in mg/L, above which a bacterium is considered resistant to the antibiotic.

Antibiotic	Dilution range (mg/L)	Cut-off points (mg/L)
Cefepime	0,06-32	0,125
Cefotaxime	0,25-64	0,25
Cefotaxime + clavulanic acid	0,06/4 - 64/4	NA
Cefoxitin	0,5-32	8
Ceftazidime	0,25-128	0,5
Ceftazidime + clavulanic acid	0,12/4 - 64/4	NA
Ertapenem	0,015-2	0,06
Imipenem	0,12-16	1/0,5
Meropenem	0,03-16	0,125
Temocycline	0,5-128	16

Table 2.7. Criteria for classification of isolates with beta-lactamase enzymes

EUVSEC Panel	EUVSEC2 panel	Betalactamase enzyme
-FOT R -TAZ R -MERO S	-FOX S -FOT/CLAV and/or TAZ/CLAV +	ESBL
	-FOX R -FOT/CLAV and/or TAZ/CLAV -FOT/CLAV and/or TAZ/CLAV -FOT/CLAV and/or TAZ/CLAV	AmpC
	-FOX R -FOT/CLAV and/or TAZ/CLAV +	ESBL + AmpC

FOT: Cefotaxime, TAZ: Ceftazidime, FOX: Cefoxitin, CLAV: Clavulanic Acid

Isolates that were simultaneously resistant to three or more different antimicrobial groups were considered multidrug-resistant (MR), while those isolates that were sensitive to all 14 antimicrobials were considered fully sensitive (FS).

3. Whole genome sequencing

The isolates were sequenced at the Instituto Tecnológico Agrario de Castilla y León (ITACYL).

Libraries for sequencing were prepared using the Nextera XT commercial kit and sequenced using the Illumina MiSeq system, with 2 x 300 cycles. Reads were analysed at ITACYL with their own TORMES Software® (Quijada et al., 2019).

4. In silico studies

The ".fastq" format data resulting from sequencing were assembled using SPAdes software with the --careful parameter (reduces the number of mismatches and short deletions in small genomes) (Bankevich et al., 2012) and converted into ".fasta" format data for further analysis.

4.1. Detection of antibiotic resistance encoding genes and chromosomal mutations conferring antibiotic resistance

The ResFinder v4.1 (and earlier versions) and PointFinder software (Camacho et al., 2009; Bortolaia et al., 2020; Zankari et al., 2020), developed by the Centre for Genetic Epidemiology (CGE) at the Technical University of Copenhagen (DTU) (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/>), were used to specifically search for genes and mutations encoding antibiotic resistance. In both Resfinder and Pointfinder, the parameters selected for analysis were 60% and 90% minimum length and identity threshold, respectively.

When no resistance genes or point mutations were identified to explain the detected phenotypic resistance to any antibiotic, the complete sequences were annotated using Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation software (Seeman, 2014), blastx software (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) (Zhang et al., 2000) and Artemis v12 software (Carver et al. 2012).

4.2. Multilocus sequence typing (MLST) and E. coli phylogroup determination

The MLST profile was characterised using MLST v2.0 (CGE-DTU) MLST v2.0 software (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/MLST/>) (Wirth et al., 2016; Jauregui et al., 2008; Camacho et al., 2009; Larsen et al., 2012), and the phylogroup of isolates was determined using CermonTyping v21.03 software (<http://clermonttyping.iame-research.center/>) (Clermont et al., 2019; Beghain et al., 2019). In isolates where the phylogroup could not be determined, the result of an alternative method for detecting phylogroups based on the complete sequence, called a "mash" group, was added to the most likely phylogroup. The sequences of isolates where the MLST could not be identified due to the appearance of a new allele were submitted to EnteroBase (<https://enterobase.warwick.ac.uk/>) (Zhou et al., 2020) to assign each isolate a new MLST.

4.3. Plasmid detection and typing

Plasmid replication origins were identified using PlasmidFinder v2.1 software (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/PlasmidFinder/>) (Camacho et al., 2009; Carattoli et al., 2014), and typed using pMLST v2.0 software, selecting in each case the plasmid to be typed (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/pMLST/>) (Carattoli et al., 2014), (CGE-DTU). The parameters selected in PlasmidFinder were 95% and 60% threshold for minimum identity and minimum coverage, respectively.

Once the replication origins of the plasmids were identified, the contigs in which they were located were analysed for possible resistance genes that might be part of the mobile genetic element.

In addition, the complete sequences were aligned, using `blastn` (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) (Zhang et al., 2000), with plasmids already published and with the same origin of replication as those identified in our sequences. The contigs of the sequences that obtained after alignment more than 70% coverage (sum of the percentages of each contig) and more than 80% identity with the reference plasmid, were joined using the CONTIGuator software (Galardini et al., 2011), using as reference the already published plasmid, thus obtaining a single contig formed by the ordered contigs that aligned with the reference plasmid. The parameters selected in CONTIGuator were the default ones.

Each resulting contig was again compared to the reference plasmid to obtain identity and coverage values using `blastn` (Zhang et al., 2000).

Diagrams of the genes that were identified in the plasmids were constructed using the Python DNA Features Viewer library (<https://github.com/Edinburgh-GenomeFoundry/DnaFeaturesViewer>) (Zulkower et al., 2020) using Prokka annotations. Where the gene could not be annotated in Prokka, the gene was given the name of the product it encodes.

In addition, the complete sequences were analysed using `mplasmids` software (Arredondo-Alonso et al., 2018) to predict the position in the genome of contigs. This tool classifies contigs into plasmid or chromosomal contigs by obtaining a percentage probability.

4.4. Phylogenetic analysis

To study phylogenetic distances between isolates, sequences were analysed with the CSI Phylogeny v1.4 software (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/CSIPhylogeny/>) (Rolf et al., 2014) (CGE-DTU) with the default parameters, except for the minimum SNP quality, which was increased to 40. A matrix with information on differences in single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) between sequences was obtained.

Isolates differing by less than 40 SNPs were considered clones. The complete sequence of *E. coli* K12 MG1655 (genbank accession no. NC_000913.3), which constituted the outgroup of the tree, was used as the reference genome.

The resulting trees were annotated using iTOL v5 software (<https://itol.embl.de/>) (Letunic et al., 2021).

4.5. Integron detection

Integrations were localised by identification of the gene encoding the integrase protein. The sequences of the 272 sequenced isolates were compared in `blastn` (Zhang et al., 2000) with the sequences of the three most common integrases: `IntI1`, `IntI2` and `IntI3` (genbank accession no.s : NC_017659.1: c53817-52699, NZ_QOGE01000029.1: c55655-56632 and HE616889.1: c490-4530). Sequences in which the sequence of any of the three integrases was identified were annotated with Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation software (Seeman, 2014) to identify both other integron elements and resistance genes that were part of the integron gene cassette. The resulting integrations were

searched against the Integrall database (Moura et al., 2009) to determine the GenBank accession number of the complete integron.

The genetic environment, potential transposable elements and insertion sequences that were close to the previously located resistance genes were identified by annotating the complete sequences with Artemis v12 software (Carver et al. 2012). Diagrams of the genes that were identified in the integrons were constructed using the Python DNA Features Viewer library (<https://github.com/Edinburgh-Genome-Foundry/DnaFeaturesViewer>) (Zulkower et al., 2020) using Prokka annotations. When the gene could not be annotated in Prokka, the gene was given the name of the product it encodes.

4.6. Definition of multi-resistance region

To define a multi-resistance region, the criterion proposed by Leekitcharoenphon et al. (2021) was followed: antibiotic resistance genes that were found within 31 kbp of a mobile genetic element were considered to be associated, meaning that they have the potential to be mobilised. The threshold corresponds to the length of the longest of the largest composite transposon of Enterobacteriaceae (Tn6108).

5. Measurement of *E. coli* diversity

In order to know the population diversity of *E. coli* in the different samplings of the farm, Simpson's index was calculated in which there were at least eight isolates typed by the same procedure, and isolates in general medium.

Simpson's index (D), based on the probability that two unrelated strains chosen from the population are classified into different groups, is calculated by the following formula (Hunter et al., 1988):

$$D = 1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^s n_j - (n_j - 1)}{N(N - 1)}$$

N: total number of isolates, s: total number of different groups identified, n_j : number of isolates belonging to group j . This equation is derived as follows: the probability that a randomly sampled strain belongs to group j is n_j/N . The probability that two consecutively chosen strains belong to the same group is $n_j(n_j - 1)/N(N - 1)$.

The index D can vary from 0 to 1, where 0 means that there is no diversity in the population under study, i.e. all individuals belong to the same group and 1 means that all individuals in the population under study belong to different groups

6. Scientific Results and Discussion

RESULTS

CHAPTER 1. Levels of antibiotic resistance

The initial isolate collection included phenotypic resistance data from 637 isolates. In addition, resistance levels to 14 antimicrobials were determined for 50 isolates from samples 3 and 8 of batch 1, sample 7 of batch 2, sample 8 of batch 3, and samples 3 and 7 of batch 4. Figure 4.1 shows the

percentage of isolates resistant to each of the 14 antimicrobials included in the EUVSEC antibiogram plates of the 687 isolates, distributed by isolate medium.

Figure 4.1. Percentage of antibiotic resistant isolates classified by isolation (SMX: Sulfamethoxazole; TMP: Trimethoprim; TET: Tetracycline; AMP: Ampicillin; CIP: Ciprofloxacin; NAL: Nalidixic acid; CHL: Chloramphenicol; FOT: Cefotaxime; TAZ: Ceftazidime; GEN: Gentamicin. FS: Sensitive to all 14 antimicrobials tested. MR: Multiresistant; SA: medium without antibiotics).

Phenotypic resistance to colistin, meropenem or tigecycline was not detected in any isolate, irrespective of the isolation medium (Figure 4.1).

In the isolates corresponding to the general culture medium (n=414), the antibiotics against which most resistant isolates were identified were tetracycline (27.8%) and sulphonamides (18.1%). Isolates sensitive to all antibiotics (FS) accounted for 55.2% of the total and multiresistant (MR) for 12.8% of the total.

Among the isolates obtained on CTX medium (n=137), some isolates were sensitive to ampicillin (10.9%), cefotaxime (11.7%) and ceftazidime (13.9%). In addition, high and very high levels of resistance to fluoroquinolones were observed (Figure 4.1).

Among the isolates obtained on IPC medium (n=136), some isolates not resistant to fluoroquinolones were detected (1.5% to ciprofloxacin and 30.1% to nalidixic acid) (Figure 4.1).

In addition, ESBL phenotypic profiles of those isolates resistant to cefotaxime and/or ceftazidime (n=100) were obtained by performing EUVSEC2 panels. 57 were found to be producers of extended spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL), 40 were found to be producers of AmpC beta-lactamases, and three were found to be producers of both beta-lactamases.

In the medium without antibiotics, animal isolates from the first sample had the least number of isolates sensitive to all antibiotics (12.19%), while the highest number of sensitive isolates were detected in samples 5 and 7 (76% and 70%, respectively) (Figure 4.2A).

In egg isolates, fewer FS isolates were detected in sample 4 (10%) and, in sample 7, a percentage of 33.3% of multi-resistant isolates was detected, being the egg sample where higher levels of multi-resistance were detected (Figure 4.2A). It should be noted that sample 2 was the only sample in which an isolate was found with seven different antibiotic groups (resistance profile: SMX-TET-TMP-CIP/NAL-CTX/TAZ-CHL-AMP).

In the CTX medium, isolates sensitive to all antimicrobials were detected in sample 7 (5.3%) (Figure 4.2B), although it was the only sample in the farm where an isolate resistant to eight different antibiotic groups (SMX-TMP-TET-CIP/NAL-AZI-AMP-CTX/TAZ-GEN) was found, while in samples 1, 3 and 4, 100% of the isolates were found to be multi-resistant (Figure 4.2B).

In the CIP medium, isolates sensitive to all antibiotics were identified in egg sample 6 (50%), while the samples in which the highest levels of multi-resistance were detected were samples 4 and 2 (84.1% and 70%, respectively) (Figure 4.2C). Sampling 4 was the only one in which isolates resistant to seven different antibiotic groups (SMX-TET-CIP-CIP-AZI-AMP-CTX/TAZ-CHL) were found (Figure 4.2C).

Figure 4.2. Percentages of antibiotic resistance of *E. coli* isolates classified by sampling . The green colour corresponds to isolates sensitive to all tested antimicrobials, the blue colours correspond to isolates resistant to 1 or 2 different antimicrobial groups, and the yellow, orange and black colours correspond to isolates considered multi-resistant. The last column corresponds to the total number of isolates in the collection. A: Isolates on medium without antibiotics. B: Isolates on medium with CTX. C: Isolates on medium with CIP. H: Egg samples

CHAPTER 2. Typing of *E. coli* isolates

The complete genome of 271 *E. coli* isolates (240 from animals and 31 from eggs) was sequenced (Table 4.1). Initially, isolates from samples 1, 2, 4 and 6 from all batches were sequenced. This was completed by selecting isolates resistant to cefotaxime, and isolates from eggs.

Table 4.1. Distribution of sequenced *E. coli* isolates by means of isolation and type of sampling (animals or eggs)

Insulation medium	Total	Animals	Eggs
No antibiotic	203	174	29
With cefotaxime (1 mg/L)	44	44	0
With ciprofloxacin (0.125 mg/L)	24	22	2

Among the 271 isolates, 11 different phylogroups (B1, A, B2, D, G, F, E, clade I, clade IV and clade III) were identified, with B1 and A being the most represented: 116 isolates (42.8%) belonged to B1 and 81 (29.9%) to A. In 7 of the isolates the phylogroup could not be determined and, after adding the "mash" result to the most probable phylogroup, their phylogroup was determined: four of the isolates had phylogroup A/B1, two had E/D, one had B1/A and one had B1/E.

A total of 94 different MLSTs were identified. The most frequent was ST155 (52 isolates, 19.2%), followed by ST10 (28 isolates, 10.3%) (Table 4.2). All isolates from the same MLST profile shared the same phylogroup.

Table 4.2. Distribution by MLST of the 271 *E. coli* isolates

MLST	No. of isolates
155	52
10	28
48	18
355, 93 y 4243	8
162	7
117, 1403 y 58	6
2726, 602 y 746	4
101, 1276, 4038, 429, 7547 y 937	3
1158, 1286, 1303, 1308, 140, 154, 165, 1706, 1828, 2253, 2944, 394, 4456, 5826, 5853, 6616, 770, 8516, 919 y 95	2
1011, 1056, 10589*, 1079, 11410, 1246, 13, 13021, 13030, 1304, 1324, 135, 141, 1431, 1484, 1629, 170, 1716, 1850, 205, 212, 2165, 224, 226, 23, 2329, 2371, 2557, 2599, 2614, 2698, 2750*, 278, 2792, 2935, 295, 3076, 3270, 3672, 38, 3953*, 3998, 4481, 453, 457, 46, 5797, 580, 616, 69, 695, 6969, 738 y 88	1

* Nearest MLST

CHAPTER 3. On-farm *E. coli* diversity

To study the diversity of *E. coli*, the D-index was calculated with both phenotypic (resistance profile against 14 antibiotics) and genotypic (MLST) data of isolates obtained on medium without antibiotic from batches 1, 2, 3 and 4 (samples 1, 2, 4 and 6) (n=16).

When using the antibiotic resistance profiles, the maximum number of different profiles per sample was 7 (detected in sample 6 of batch 4), while with the genotypic data the highest number of different groups was 10 (detected in sample 6 of batches 3 and 4) (Tables 4.3 and A.1). Higher diversity was identified in all samplings when analysing genotypic data, except in sampling L1M2, where the same number of antibiotic resistance profiles and MLST were identified (Tables 4.3 and A.1).

Diversity was found to be relatively high regardless of the data used for the analysis (0.836 and 0.622 mean analysing genotypic and phenotypic data, respectively) (Tables 4.3 and A.1).

It was also observed that the same phenotypic resistance profile often occurred in phylogenetically distinct isolates (Table A.1). In most of the samples analysed, more MLST than phenotypic resistance profiles were identified, especially in the case of phenotypic profiles sensitive to all antibiotics tested (FS). In 11 of the 13 profiles where isolates with FS phenotypic profile were identified, at least two different MLSTs with this phenotypic resistance profile were identified (Table A.1).

On the other hand, in two of the samples (L1M6 and L4M2), one MLST was identified with different antibiotic resistance phenotypic profiles (Table A.1). In sampling L1M6, six ST1403 isolates were identified, five of them with an FS antibiotic resistance profile and one with a gentamicin-resistant phenotypic profile. In sampling L4M2, of the four MLST10 isolates identified, three had an FS phenotypic profile and one had a tetracycline-resistant phenotypic profile (Table 4.4). In neither case was it possible to differentiate between isolates by analysing genotypic data, as no genes were located to support gentamicin or tetracycline resistance.

Table 4.3. Number of phenotypic and genotypic profiles distributed by sampling, and Simpson's index (D) calculated with the phenotypic (antibiotic resistance profiles) and genotypic data (phylogenetic distances). The row row shows the mean of both the number of phenotypic and genotypic profiles and the indices.

Batch and Sampling (no. of isolates)	number of different phenotypic profiles	no. of different MLST profiles	Diversity by antibiotic resistance profiles	Diversity by MLST
L1M1 (n=10)	4	5	0,778	0,822
L1M2 (n=8)	5	5	0,778	0,778
L1M4 (n=10)	4	9	0,778	0,978
L1M6 (n=8)	2	3	0,25	0,464
L2M1 (n=10)	3	5	0,644	0,8
L2M2 (n=10)	4	4	0,644	0,756
L2M4 (n=10)	6	10	0,844	1
L2M6 (n=8)	2	6	0,429	0,893
L3M1 (n=10)	4	5	0,733	0,867
L3M2 (n=8)	3	4	0,679	0,75
L3M4 (n=10)	2	4	0,356	0,733
L3M6 (n=10)	4	10	0,533	1
L4M1 (n=10)	3	5	0,644	0,8
L4M2 (n=10)	3	6	0,378	0,8
L4M4 (n=10)	3	7	0,6	0,933
L4M6 (n=10)	7	10	0,867	1
MEDIA	3,8	6	0,622	0,836

Table 4.4. Isolates with the same genotypic profile showing different antibiotic resistance profiles by batch and sampling . The MLST profiles, the antibiotic resistance profiles they exhibit and the MIC of the antibiotics in which they differ are shown.

Batch and sampling	MLST (No. isolated)	ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE PROFILES (No. of isolates) and samples they belong to	CMI OF ANTIBIOTICS ON WHICH THEY DIFFER
L1M6	ST1403 (6)	FS (5) -L1M6-01 -L1M6-02 -L1M6-03 -L1M6-07 -L1M6-09	MIC GEN: 1 µg/mL
		GEN (1) -L1M6-05	MIC GEN: 8 µg/mL
L4M2	ST10 (4)	FS (3) -L4M2-01 -L4M2-02 -L4M2-03	TET MIC: 2 µg/mL
		TET (1) -L4M2-08	MIC TET: 64 µg/mL

GEN: Gentamicin; TET: Tetracycline; FS: Sensitive to all 14 antimicrobials tested; MIC: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration; MIC: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration.

CHAPTER 4. Phylogenetic analysis

A phylogenetic tree was made from the 271 isolates that were sequenced by WGS (Figure 4.3).

It shows three main groups: group A (red), consisting of 88 isolates belonging mostly to phylogroup A; group B (green), consisting of 121 isolates belonging mostly to B1; and a third group, group C (yellow), consisting of 60 isolates belonging to different phylogroups (Figure 4.3). Three isolates were not included in any of the three groups (Figure 4.3).

In group A, 29 different STs were found (10, 48, 93, 746, 1286, 1303, 165, 2253, 6616, 8516, 8516, 1011, 10589*, 13030, 1629, 170, 1716, 1850, 226, 2614, 2750*, 2792, 2935, 3270, 46, 580, 695 and 6969), in group B, 36 STs (155, 162, 1403, 58, 2726, 602, 101, 4038, 937, 1308, 154, 1706, 5826, 1056, 1079, 11410, 1246, 13, 1304, 1324, 1431, 205, 212, 2165, 224, 2329, 2599, 2698, 278, 295, 3076, 3953*, 3998, 4481, 453 and 616) and in group C, 29 different STs (355, 4243, 117, 429, 1276, 95, 140, 394, 770, 919, 1158, 1828, 2944, 4456, 5853, 23, 38, 69, 88, 135, 141, 457, 738, 1484, 2557, 3672, 5797, 7547 and 13021) (Figure 4.3).

Following the criteria set out in section 4.5 of material and methods, i.e. considering clones to be those isolates that differed by less than 40 SNPs between them, 51 clones were identified.

Figure 4.3.

Phylogenetic tree of the 271 isolates sequenced by WGS. Phylogroups are represented in the inner ring (n=11). Isolates where the phylogroup could not be identified have been annotated in the tree with the most likely phylogroup. The second ring represents the MLST profiles (n=95), the third ring represents the batch (L1, L2, L3, L4 and L5) to which each isolate belongs, and the outer ring represents the sampling of each isolate (M1, M2, M3, M4, M5, M6, M7 and M8). The reference isolate, *E. coli* K12, is marked with a green background, while the egg isolates are marked with an orange background. The red dots represent isolates that are considered clones, i.e. those that differ by less than 40 SNPs from each other. The clade colours represent the three major groups of isolates identified: the red clade corresponds mostly to group A isolates, the green clade corresponds mostly to group B isolates, and the yellow clade corresponds to group C isolates.

Two or more isolates from the same clone were considered to be the same when they came from the same batch, sampling, shared MLST, phylogroup, phenotypic resistance profile and antibiotic resistance genes. Using this criterion, 53 isolates were eliminated and the remaining 217 isolates were identified to construct the second phylogenetic tree (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4 shows the phylogenetic tree of the resulting 217 non-repeat (NR) isolates after deletion of the 53 isolates. In these 217 isolates, 30 clones were identified, 21 less than with the phylogenetic tree of the 271 isolates. The clones were numbered according to their position in the phylogenetic tree in clockwise order starting with the reference strain *E. coli* K12 (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4. Phylogenetic tree of the 218 NR isolates sequenced by WGS from the collection after having grouped the duplicate isolates.

CHAPTER 5. Mechanisms of antibiotic resistance

At least one antibiotic resistance gene was found in 113 of the 211 NR isolates (53.6%). Three sulfa resistance genes (*sul1*, *sul2* and *sul3*), five trimethoprim resistance genes (*dfrA1*, *dfrA5*, *dfrA14*, *dfrA17* and *dfrA36*), two tetracycline resistance genes (*tetA* and *tetB*), two fluoroquinolone resistance genes (*qnrS1* and *qnrB19*), seven beta-lactam resistance genes (*bla_{SHV-12}*, *bla_{CMY-2}*, *bla_{CTX-M-1}*, *bla_{CTX-M-14}*, *bla_{TEM-1B}*, *bla_{TEM-1D}* and *bla_{OXA-1}*), three phenicol resistance genes (*cmlA1*, *floR* and *catA1*), one resistance gene to gentamicin and sisomicin (*aac(3)-Vla*), one to gentamicin and amikacin (*aac(3')-IId*) and one resistance gene to azithromycin (*mphA*) (Table 4.5).

In addition, other genes conferring resistance to antibiotics not included in the antibiogram and for which the phenotypic resistance profile was not studied were also found. These genes conferred resistance to streptomycin/spectinomycin (*aadA1*, *aadA2*, *aadA5* and *strA/B*), neomycin/kanamycin/lividomycin/paromomycin/ribostamycin (*aph(3')-Ia*), streptothricin (*sat1*) and fosfomicin (*fosA7*).

Seven mutations were detected in the *gyrA*, 17 in *gyrB*, 10 in *parC* and seven in *parE* conferring different levels of resistance to fluoroquinolones and three mutations in the *ampC* gene, at positions -1 and -18, always identified together, and at position +24, conferring resistance to cephalosporins (Table 4.5).

In 41 isolates, no genes or mutations were identified to explain the phenotypic resistance observed: nine resistant to azithromycin, five resistant to gentamicin, seven resistant to tetracycline, five resistant to fluoroquinolones, six resistant to trimethoprim and nine resistant to sulphonamides.

Table 4.5. Resistance genes and point mutations identified in *E. coli*, sorted by antibiotic family

Resistance phenotype (ECOFF mg/L)	Resistance genes	Point mutations
Fluoroquinolones (CIP>0.06 and/or NAL>16)	<i>qnrS1</i> and <i>qnrB19</i>	<i>gyrA</i> (D678E, A828S, S83L, T258N, V721I, T611S, E728G) <i>gyrB</i> (H652R, S492N, A863V, T616A, E185D, E703D, E656D, R761C, N746D, H652R, A618T, F706Y, N595V, Q657K, R206K, V522I, T590A) <i>parE</i> (p.V136I, p.D475E, p.T172A, p.I355T, p.A512T, p.E545D, p.A243S) <i>parC</i> (p.E62K, p.D475E, p.S80I, p.Q695L, p.T718A, p.R96H, p.L451W, p.A649V, p.I392S, p.R406W)
Betalactams (AMP>8, CTX>0.25 and TAZ>0.5)	<i>blaSHV-12</i> , <i>blaCMY-2</i> , <i>blaCTX-M-1</i> , <i>blaCTX-M-14</i> , <i>blaTEM-1B</i> , <i>blaTEM-1D</i> and <i>blaOXA-1</i>	<i>ampC</i> (-1, -18 and +24)
Trimethoprim (>2)	<i>dfrA1</i> , <i>dfrA5</i> , <i>dfrA14</i> , <i>dfrA17</i> and <i>dfrA36</i>	-
Sulphamides (>64)	<i>sul1</i> , <i>sul2</i> and <i>sul3</i>	-
Chloramphenicol (>16)	<i>cmlA1</i> , <i>floR</i> and <i>catA1</i>	-
Tetracycline (>8)	<i>tetA</i> and <i>tetB</i>	-
Gentamicin (>2)	<i>aac(3')-Vla</i> and <i>aac(3')-IId</i>	-
Azithromycin (>16)	<i>mphA</i>	-
Other aminoglycosides	<i>aadA1</i> , <i>aadA2</i> , <i>aadA5</i> and <i>strA/B</i> , <i>sat1</i> and <i>aph(3')-Ia</i>	-
Fosfomycin	<i>fosA7</i>	

Seven of these genes (*aadA1*, *blaTEM-1B*, *strA/B*, *sul1*, *sul2*, *tetA* and *tetB*) were detected in isolates from all four growth stages and seven in isolates from three growth stages (*blaCMY-2*, *blaCTX-M-1*, *dfrA1*, *dfrA17*, *catA1*, *qnrS1* and *dfrA17*). All genes found at three or four different growth stages were detected in at least one sampling of day-old chicks. Eleven of the genes were identified in isolates from two different growth phases (Figure 4.3) (*blaOXA-1*, *dfrA36*, *floR*, *aac(3')-Vla* and *aadA5*, *dfrA5*, *sat1*, *blaTEM-1D*, *sul3*, *aadA2* and

cmlA1) and seven of them were found in only one growth phase (*aph(3')-Ia*, *mphA*, *bla_{SHV-12}*, *qnrB19*, *aac(3)-III_d*, *bla_{CTX-M-14}* and *fosA7*) (Figure 4.5 and table 4.6) (Figure 4.5 and table 4.6). It should be noted that no genes were found only in isolates from growing pullets.

Figure 4.5. Venn diagram of resistance genes identified by growth stage at which isolates were detected.

Table 4.6. Occurrence of resistance genes in isolates from different growth stages of animals sampled on the farm

Growth phase (n*)	Antibiotic resistance genes
Day-old chicks, growing pullets, laying hens and eggs (n=4)	<i>aadA1</i> , <i>bla_{TEM-1B}</i> , <i>strA/B</i> , <i>sul1</i> , <i>sul2</i> , <i>tetA</i> and <i>tetB</i>
Day-old chicks, growing pullets and laying hens (n=3)	<i>bla_{CMY-2}</i> , <i>bla_{CTX-M-1}</i> , <i>dfrA1</i> , <i>dfrA17</i> and <i>qnrS1</i>
Day-old chicks, growing pullets and eggs (n=3)	<i>catA1</i>
Day-old chicks, laying hens and eggs (n=3)	<i>dfrA7</i>
Day-old chicks and growing pullets (n=2)	<i>bla_{OXA-1}</i> , <i>dfrA36</i> and <i>floR</i>
Day-old chicks and laying hens (n=2)	<i>aac(3')-VIa</i> and <i>aadA5</i>
Growing pullets and laying hens (n=2)	<i>sat1</i> , <i>bla_{TEM-1D}</i> and <i>sul3</i>
Laying hens and eggs (n=2)	<i>aadA2</i> , <i>dfrA5</i> and <i>cmlA1</i>
Day-old chicks (n=1)	<i>aph(3')-Ia</i> and <i>fosA7</i>
Laying hens (n=1)	<i>mphA</i> , <i>bla_{SHV-12}</i> , <i>qnrB19</i> , <i>aac(3')-III_d</i> and <i>bla_{CTX-M-14}</i>

*= number of growth phases

5.1. Genomic location of resistance genes

Thirty-two different resistance genes were found, detected in different locations in the isolates studied, most of them in plasmids (74%). The most frequent resistance gene was *tetA*, detected in 74 *E. coli* isolates, followed by *bla_{TEM-1B}*, detected in 47.

32.5% of these genes were found as part of an integron, either located on the chromosome (80%) or on a plasmid (80%) (Table 4.7).

Table 4.7. Number of isolates and genomic location in which antibiotic resistance genes identified in *E. coli* are detected.

Gen	Number of isolates	Genomic localisation	
		Plasmid (integron)	Chromosome (integron)
<i>tetA</i>	74	54	20
<i>bla</i> TEM-1B	47	44	3
<i>aadA1</i>	35	29 (29)	6 (6)
<i>sul2</i>	35	22	13
<i>strA/B</i>	32	28	4
<i>sul1</i>	28	15 (15)	13 (4)
<i>dfrA1</i>	20	13 (13)	7 (7)
<i>bla</i> CTX-M-1	17	9	8
<i>sul3</i>	15	15 (14)	0
<i>aadA2</i>	14	14 (14)	0
<i>cmlA1</i>	14	14 (14)	0
<i>tetB</i>	15	0	15
<i>bla</i> h _{CMY-2}	13	13	0
<i>qnrS1</i>	11	11	0
<i>bla</i> SHV-12	7	7	0
<i>bla</i> TEM-1D	6	6	0
<i>catA1</i>	4	0	4
<i>dfrA14</i>	3	0	3 (3)
<i>dfrA17</i>	3	3 (3)	0
<i>aadA5</i>	2	2 (2)	0
<i>aac(3)-Vla</i>	2	2 (2)	0
<i>aph(3')-Ia</i>	2	2	0
<i>bla</i> h _{OXA-1}	2	0	2 (2)
<i>dfrA36</i>	2	0	2
<i>dfrA5</i>	2	2 (2)	0
<i>floR</i>	2	0	2
<i>sat1</i>	2	0	2 (2)

<i>mphA</i>	2	2	0
<i>fosA7</i>	2	0	2
<i>aac(3)-IId</i>	1	1	0
<i>qnrB19</i>	1	0	1
<i>blaCTX-M-14</i>	1	0	1

Thirteen genes were found only in plasmids (*sul3*, *aadA2*, *cmlA1*, *bla_{CMY-2}*, *qnrS1*, *bla_{SHV-12}*, *bla_{TEM-1D}*, *aadA5*, *aac(3)-Vla*, *aph(3')-Ia*, *dfrA5*, *mphA* and *aac(3)-IId*), while ten were only detected in chromosomal DNA (*tetB*, *catA1*, *dfrA14*, *bla_{OXA-1}*, *dfrA36*, *floR*, *sat1*, *qnrB19*, *bla_{CTX-M-14}* and *fosA7*). The remaining nine were identified in both chromosomal DNA and plasmids (*tetA*, *bla_{TEM-1B}*, *aadA1*, *sul2*, *strA/B*, *sul1*, *dfrA1*, *dfrA17* and *bla_{CTX-M-1}*), with plasmid localisation predominating (Table 4.7).

13 of the 32 genes were found as part of integrons in some of the isolates. Eleven were detected in all cases in integrons (*aadA1*, *aadA2*, *aadA5*, *sat1*, *aac(3)-Vla*, *bla_{OXA-1}*, *cmlA1*, *dfrA1*, *dfrA5*, *dfrA14* and *dfrA17*), while the remaining two (*sul1* and *sul3*) were not always, but mostly, detected as part of integrons (Table 4.7).

CHAPTER 6. Transmission of antibiotic resistance genes

6.1. Clones

As mentioned above, 30 clones were identified. All isolates of each clone shared a phylogroup and ST, except in clone 30, where two distinct ST profiles were detected (B1-ST155 and B1-ST3935*). In only two clones (6 and 12) no resistance genes or associated mutations were detected in any of the isolates.

Clones 5, 11, 16, 30 and 31 were only found in one sampling (Table 4.8).

Table 4.8. Clones identified in a single sample

Clone (ST-philogroup)	No. isolated	Batch and sampling	Common characteristics	Differences
5 (A-ST48)	3	L3M2	<i>bla</i> _{TEM-1B}	<i>IncK2 (bla)_{CMY-2}</i> (n=2) <i>sulI</i> on chromosome (n=2)
11 (D-ST1158)	2	L2M2	<i>ampC</i> +24 mutation in the promoter	<i>IncK2 (bla)_{CMY-2}</i> (n=1) <i>gyrA</i> p.D678E (n=1)
16 (B2-ST4456)	2	L1M2	<i>IncF</i> plasmid (F18:A5:B1) with MR1(<i>bla</i> _{TEM-1B-tetA}) region + mutations in <i>gyrA</i> (p.S83L) and <i>parC</i> (p.E62K)	FOT/TAZ ^S (MIC=0,25/0,5 mg/L) FOT/TAZ ^R (CMI _s = 2/16 mg/L) -> <i>ampC</i> +24 mutation in the promoter
30 (B1-ST155 and B1-ST3935*)	2	L4M1	<i>sulI</i> on chromosome	MR8 (<i>sulI-tetA</i>) (n=1)
31 (B1-ST155)	2	L2M1		<i>IncF</i> plasmid with <i>tetA</i> (n=1)

*MLST could not be determined and was assigned to the nearest MLST

Clone 5 (A-ST48) consisted of three isolates from growing chicks from batch 3 with three gene combinations with different locations: unidentified plasmid (*bla*_{TEM-1B}) + chromosome (*sulI*), unidentified plasmid (*bla*_{TEM-1B}) + chromosome (*sulI*) + *IncK2* plasmid (*bla*_{CMY-2}) and unknown plasmid (*bla*_{TEM-1B}) + *IncK2* plasmid (*bla*_{CMY-2}). (Table 4.8).

Clone 11 (D-ST1158) consisted of two isolates from growing chicks from batch 2, one of which carried the *IncK2* plasmid with the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} mentioned above and a mutation in the *gyrA* gene (p.D678E). No antibiotic resistance genes were detected in the second isolate. A mutation in the promoter of the *ampC* gene (+24) was detected in both isolates (Table 4.8).

Clone 16 (B2-ST4456) consisted of two isolates from growing chicks from batch 1. In both, the MR1 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-tetA}) was found in an *IncF* plasmid (section 6.4.1.1) and mutations in the *gyrA* (p.S83L) and *parC* (p.E62K) genes. A mutation in the promoter of the *ampC* gene (+24) and phenotypic resistance to cephalosporins was detected in one of them (Table 4.8).

Clone 30 was formed by two isolates (day-old chicks / batch 4) of different ST (B1-ST155 and B1-ST3935*), being the only clone with this peculiarity. Both isolates showed phenotypic resistance to sulphonamides and tetracycline and in both of them the *sulI* gene was detected on the chromosome, but only in one of them (ST155) the *tetA* gene (MR8 region (*sulI-tetA*)) (section 6.7 of results) was detected on the chromosome (Table 4.8).

Clone 31 (B1-ST155) consisted of two isolates from day-old chicks from sample 2 that differed in that only one had the *tetA* gene on an IncF plasmid, while the other had no resistance gene and was sensitive to all antimicrobials tested (Table 4.8).

6.2. Clone dynamics

Twenty-five of the 30 clones were detected in more than one sampling. Clones that were identified in day-old chicks entering the farm (first sampling) were considered to be from a source external to the farm, thus constituting a possible source of antibiotic resistance genes.

6.2.1. Clones detected in day-old chicks

Six clones were detected in the first sampling of one of the batches: three in batch 1, one in batch 2, one in batch 3 and one in two batches (2 and 3) (Table 4.9).

In four of these clones (15, 17, 19 and 25), the isolates always carried the same antibiotic resistance genes and mutations. In contrast, isolates from clones 24 and 27 differed from each other in the resistance genes that were identified.

Table 4.9. *E. coli* clones occurring in day-old chick samples

Clone no.	Appearances	Batch(es)	Eggs	Time (months)	Philogroup-ST	Resistance platforms
15	2	1	0	0.5	B1-ST58	Int1.7 + MR10 region (<i>sul2-dfrA36-floR</i>) + <i>catA1</i> on chromosome + IncF plasmid (MR1.1 region (<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA</i>))
17	2	1	1	9	B2-ST429	<i>gyrA</i> (p.S83L)
19	2	1	0	0.5	B2-ST355	<i>gyrA</i> (p.S83L)
24	3	2/3	0	5	B1-ST602	IncF plasmid (<i>strA/B</i>) and <i>tetB</i> on chromosome (n=2) Plasmid IncF (<i>strA/B</i>), <i>tetB</i> on chromosome and Plasmid IncI/ST3 (<i>blaCTX-M-1</i> + MR2 region (<i>sul1-tetA</i>)) (n=1)
25	3	3	0	10	G-ST117	IncI/ST3 plasmid (<i>blaCTX-M-1</i> + MR2 region) + <i>gyrA</i> (p.S83L)
27	3	2	0	4	B1-ST155	IncF (<i>tetA</i>) plasmid (n=2)

Clone 15 (B1-ST58): was detected in the first two samplings of batch 1, half a month apart. This is a multi-resistant and complex clone carrying resistance genes in the chromosome (MR10 region (*sul2-dfrA36-*

floR) and *catA1*, plus a type I integron with *bla_{OXA-1}*, *aadA1* and *sul1* [integron 1.7]) and in an IncF plasmid the MR1.1 region (*bla_{TEM-1B-tetA}*) (see section 6.4.1.1).

Clone 17 (B2-ST429): after its appearance in day-old chicks from batch 1, this clone was only detected again nine months later in a sample of eggs from the same batch (sampling 5). In these two fluoroquinolone-resistant isolates, a mutation in the *gyrA* gene (p.S83L) was detected (Table 4.9).

Clone 19 (B2-ST355) was found in the first two samplings of batch 1, i.e. half a month apart. As with clone 17, a mutation in the *gyrA* gene (p.S83L) was detected in both isolates, both being resistant to CIP/NAL (Table 4.9).

Clone 25 (G-ST117): this is the clone from this group that was found for the longest time as it was detected in three samples (day-old and growing pullets and laying hens) from the third flock 10 months apart. All three isolates had a mutation in the *gyrA* gene (p.S83L) and an IncII/ST3 plasmid carrying the *bla_{CTX-M-1}* gene and the MR2 region (*sul1-tetA*) (section 6.4.1.2) (Table 4.9). It has been published as clone 2 in Aldea *et al.* (2022).

Clone 24 (B1ST602): this is the only clone found in samples of day-old chicks from two different flocks (flocks 2 and 3). Two isolates (day-old chicks from flocks 2 and 3) had the *strA/B* (on IncF plasmid) and *tetB* (on chromosome) genes, while the third CTX isolate (day-old chicks from flock 3) also carried an IncII/ST3 plasmid with the MR2 region and the *bla_{CTX-M-1}* gene (section 6.4.1.2) (Table 4.9).

Clone 27 (B1-ST155) was found in day-old and growing chicks (two isolates) from batch 2, 4 months apart. The isolate from day-old chicks and one from growing chicks had the *tetA* gene on an IncF plasmid, while in the remaining isolate from growing chicks, the F plasmid was detected without the *tetA* gene (Table 4.9).

6.2.2. Undetected clones in day-old chicks

Of the 24 clones that appeared in more than one sampling, 19 were not detected in day-old chick sampling, but only in subsequent sampling.

6.2.2.1. Clones that were detected in animals and/or eggs from the same flock

Of the 19 clones, 8 were detected in a single batch (Table 4.10).

Table 4.10. Clones occurring on the farm in a single flock in successive samplings to M1.

Clone no.	Appearances	Lot	Eggs	Time (months)	Philogroup-ST	Resistance platforms
1	3	1	0	15	A-ST10	
3	2	4	1	3	A-ST48	IncI1/ST3 plasmid (MR2 (<i>sul1-tetA</i>)) + integron 1.9 and <i>catA1</i> on chromosome (n=1) Region MR11 (<i>catA1-tetA-sul2</i>) (n=1)
4	2	3	2	2	A-ST48	IncX (region MR3 (<i>blaTEM-1B-qnrS1</i>)) + Int 1.2 (n=1) IncF (<i>blaTEM-1B</i>) (n=1)
6	2	3	1	3	A-ST48	
10	2	2	0	5	Clade I-ST770	IncN (MR14 region (<i>qnrS1-blaTEM-1B-tetA-strA/B</i>))
14	3	3	1	5	G-ST117	<i>gyrA</i> (p.S83L/p.D678E)
18	2	4	1	19	B2-ST95	
23	2	1	1	3	B1-ST1706	<i>tetA</i> on chromosome

Clone 18 (B2-ST95): was identified twice at an interval of 19 months, in growing chicks (sample 2) and then in eggs (sample 8). The first isolate showed resistance to sulphonamides (MIC= 256 mg/L), although no gene explaining this resistance was detected, while no phenotypic resistance to any antibiotic was observed in the egg isolate (Table 4.9).

Clone 1 (A-ST10) was identified three times in batch 1 during 15 months, in growing pullets (sample 2) and in laying hens (samples 5 and 7). No resistance genes or mutations were found in any of the isolates, although phenotypic resistance to azithromycin (MIC=32 mg/L) was detected in the two isolates from laying hens (Table 4.9).

In batch 2 only one clone (clone 10 (Clade I-ST770)) was identified and only disseminated in batch 2. The first time (growing pullets of the second sampling) the isolate was fully sensitive to all antibiotics tested and no resistance gene was detected. However, at the second occurrence five months later (laying hens of the fourth sampling) the isolate carried the MR14 region (*qnrS1-blaTEM-1B-tetA-strA/B*) (section 6.7 of results) on an IncN plasmid (section 6.4.1.8) (Table 4.9).

Clone 14 (G-ST117) was identified three times in batch 3 at an interval of five months in growing pullets (sample 2) and hens and eggs in sample 4, always carrying a mutation in the *gyrA* gene (p.S83L/p.D678E) and being CIP/NAL^R (Table 4.9).

Clone 3 (A-ST48) was identified twice in batch 4 during 9 months. The first isolate (eggs from sample 5) had an integron 1.9 (section 6.6.3) and the *catA1* gene on the chromosome; and the MR2 region (*sul1-*

tetA) on an Inc11/ST3 plasmid (see section 6.4.1.2). The second (laying hens in sample 6) had the MR11 region (*catA1-tetA-sul2*) on the chromosome (see section 6.7) (Table 4.9).

Clone 6 (A-ST48) showed no resistance mechanisms and was identified twice within three months (eggs from sample 5 and laying hens from sample 6), (Table 4.9).

Clone 23 (B1-ST1706) was detected in laying hens and eggs at an interval of 3 months. In both isolates the *tetA* gene was detected on the chromosome (Table 4.9).

Clone 4 (A-ST48) was detected in two consecutive egg samples, two months apart. The first isolate had only the *bla*_{TEM-1B} resistance gene, located on an IncF plasmid, while in the second isolate no IncF plasmid was detected, but an IncX plasmid carrying the MR3 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-qnrS1}) (see section 6.4.1.3) and an unidentified plasmid carrying the 1.2 integron (see section 6.6.2) were detected (Table 4.9).

6.2.2.2. Clones that were detected in animals and/or eggs from several batches

Eleven of the clones were identified on the farm in more than one batch. Only isolates from five of these clones remained the same in all occurrences (Table 4.11).

Table 4.11. Clones occurring on the farm in more than one batch in successive samplings to M1

Clone no.	Appearances	Batch(es)	Eggs	Time (months)	Philogroup-ST	Resistance platforms
7	2	2/4	0	13	A-ST1303	IncF (region MR1.2 (<i>bla</i> _{TEM-1B-tetA})) (n=2) Unidentified plasmid (<i>sul3</i>) + <i>ampC</i> (p.E62K) (n=1)
8	2	2/5	0	10	A-ST165	IncF (Multi-resistance region 1) (n=1)
9	5	1/2/3/4	0	14	A-ST93	<i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-1} on + chromosome IncA/C2 (Int1.1) + IncF (<i>srtA/B</i>) (n=1) <i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-1} on chromosome + IncA/C2 (Int1.1) + IncF (<i>strA/B</i>) + IncX (MR4 region (<i>bla</i> _{TEM-1D-tetA})) (n=4)
12	2	3/4	0	2	D-ST394	
13	4	1/2/3/4	0	14	D-ST4243	IncK (<i>bla</i>) _{CMY-2} <i>sul2</i> on chromosome
20	2	2/4	0	11	B1-ST4038	Inc11/ST12 (<i>bla</i> _{CMY-2}) + Unidentified plasmid (Int 1.2)
21	2	1/3	1	7	B1-ST162	Inc11/ST271 (<i>mphA</i>) (n=1)
22	2	2/4	0	12	B1-ST937	<i>gyrA</i> (p.S83L)
26	2	2/4	2	1	B1-ST155	IncF plasmid (<i>tetA</i>)

33	2	3/4	1	9	B1-ST155	Unknown plasmid (Int 1.2) + IncF (Region MR9 (<i>bla</i> _{TEM-1B} . <i>tetA-sul2</i>))
34	4	2/3	0	13	B1-ST155	IncII/ST26 (<i>bla</i> _{SHV-12} + <i>int1.2</i>) + IncX (Region MR3 (<i>bla</i> _{TEM-1B-qnrS1})) (n=3) IncX (Region MR3) + IncII/ST271 (<i>mphA</i>) (n=1)

Clone 34 (B1-ST155) was found four times during 13 months in two flocks. It was first identified in growing pullets from batch 2; then in laying hens from batch 2 and laying hens from batch 3; and finally in laying hens from batch 3. Except for the last occurrence of the clone (laying hens (M6) from batch 4), all isolates carried an IncII/ST26 plasmid with an integron 1.1 and the *bla*_{SHV-12} and *tetA* genes (section 6.4.1.2). An IncX plasmid (section 6.3.1.3) with the MR3 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-qnrS1}) was identified in isolates from batch 34 (results section 6.7). In addition, an IncII/ST271 plasmid carrying the *mphA* gene was identified in its last appearance (section 6.4.1.2) (Table 4.10). It has been published as clone 3 in Aldea *et al.* (2022).

Clone 9 (A-ST93): was identified five times over 14 months in the first four batches. An integron 1.1 on an IncA/C2 plasmid (section 6.6.1) and the genes *strA/B* (on an IncF plasmid) and *bla*_{CTX-M-1} (on the chromosome) were detected in all isolates. In addition, isolates from batches 1, 2, and two of the three isolates from batch 4 had the MR4 region (*bla*_{TEM-1D-tetA}) on an IncX plasmid (section 6.4.1.3) (Table 4.10). It has been published as clone 1 in Aldea *et al.* (2022).

Clone 13 (D-ST4243) was identified in four batches, being detected four times over 14 months. All isolates carried the *sul2* genes on the chromosome and *bla*_{CMY-2} on an IncK-type plasmid (see section 6.4.1.4) (Table 4.10). It has been published as clone 4 in Aldea *et al.* (2022). Clone 7 (A-ST1303) was identified in laying hens from batches 2 and 4, thirteen months apart. In both isolates, the MR1.2 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-tetA}) was detected on an IncF35:A-:B- plasmid (section 6.4.1.1). In addition, the sulphonamide resistance gene *sul3* located on a plasmid that could not be identified and a mutation in the *ampC* gene (p.E62K) were detected in the isolate from batch 4. In addition, this isolate showed phenotypic resistance to TMP (MIC=64 mg/L), and no TMP resistance gene was identified (Table 4.10).

Clone 7 (A-ST1303) was identified in laying hens from batches 2 and 4, thirteen months apart. In the first isolate in which it was identified, the MR1.2 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-tetA}) was detected on an IncF35:A-:B- plasmid (section 6.4.1.1), while in the second isolate this same plasmid was identified with the *tetA* resistance gene, having lost the *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene. In the isolate from batch 4, the sulphonamide resistance gene *sul3* located on a plasmid that could not be identified and a mutation in the *ampC* gene (p.E62K)

were also detected. In addition, this isolate showed phenotypic resistance to TMP (MIC=64 mg/L), and no TMP resistance gene was identified (Table 4.10).

The two isolates of clone 22 (B1-ST937) were from growing pullets from flocks 2 and 4 respectively, and the clone was found for 12 months. Both had a mutation in the *gyrA* gene (Table 4.10).

Clone 20 (B1-ST4038) was detected in laying hens from sample 4 of batches 2 and 4, 14 months apart. Both isolates had the same resistance genes: *bla_{CMY-2}*, located on an IncII/ST12 plasmid (see section 6.4.1.2) and an integron 1.2 located on an unidentified plasmid (section 6.6.2) (Table 4.10). It has been published as clone 5 in Aldea *et al.* (2022).

Clone 8 (A-ST165): was detected in laying hens from batches 2 and 5, 10 months apart. The isolate from batch 2 carried the multi-resistance region 1.1 on an IncF plasmid (section 6.4.1.1), while no antibiotic resistance genes were detected in the isolate from batch 5, although phenotypic resistance to sulfonamides (MIC=2048 mg/L), tetracycline (MIC=128 mg/L), ampicillin (MIC=128 mg/L) and trimethoprim (MIC=64 mg/L) was observed (Table 4.10).

Clone 33 (B1-ST155) was identified in laying hens from batch 3, and in eggs from batch 4. A 1.2 integron was detected in both isolates, located on a plasmid that could not be identified (section 6.6.2) and MR9 (*bla_{TEM-1B-tetA-sul2}*) (results section 6.7) on an IncF plasmid (Table 4.10).

Clone 21 (B1-ST162) was detected twice during seven months (laying hens from batch 1 and eggs from batch 3). An IncII/ST271 plasmid with the resistance gene (*mphA*) was found in the laying hen isolate (Table 4.10).

Clone 12 (D-ST394) was identified during two months in laying hens from batches 3 and 4. Both isolates from this clone were sensitive to all antimicrobials tested (Table 4.10).

Clone 26 (B1-ST155) consisted of two egg isolates (batches 2 and 4), identified one month apart. The isolate from batch 4 carried an IncF plasmid with the tetracycline resistance gene *tetA*, while the isolate from batch 2 carried the same plasmid without resistance genes (results section 6.4.1.1) (Table 4.10).

6.3. Plasmids

At least one origin of replication was detected in 195 of the 217 NR isolates analysed (72%). In 87, only one type of replication origin was identified, in 64 two, in 30 three, in 13 four, and in one isolate five.

Eleven distinct replication origins were detected (Figure 4.22). Three of them were never associated with antibiotic resistance genes: Col (n=87), p0111 (n=58) and IncY (n=14). In contrast, the remaining eight (IncF, IncI, IncX, IncK/B/O/Z, IncA/C2, IncQ, IncH and IncN) carried antibiotic resistance genes in at least one isolate.

The most frequent origin was IncF (n=153, of which 42 carried resistance genes). The genes *strA/B*, *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA*, *sul2*, *aadA1*, *aadA2*, *cmlA1* and *sul3* were found in this type of plasmids. In addition, 52 different RSTs were identified, with antibiotic resistance genes found in only 14 of them.

The second most frequent replication origin was IncI (n=31). Eight IncI1 replication origins were detected (ST3, n=10; ST26, n=5; ST12, n=2; ST36, n=3; ST271, n=2; ST2, n=1; ST26*, n=2, and ST248*, n=2), and one IncI2 origin (n=4). Thirteen antibiotic resistance genes were detected in five of these plasmids (ST3, ST26, ST12, ST36, ST271 and ST26*): *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{SHV-12}, *bla*_{CMY-2}, *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA*, *sul1*, *sul2*, *sul3*, *aadA1*, *aadA2*, *cmlA1*, *aac(3)-Vla* and *mphA*.

The IncX replication origin (n=28) was the third most frequent. Two distinct replication origins were found: IncX1 (n=27) and IncX4 (n=1) and resistance genes were detected in 16 of them. Four resistance genes were identified in these plasmids: *qnrS1*, *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *bla*_{TEM-1D} and *tetA*.

The IncB/O/K/Z replication origin was detected in 16 isolates, of which 11 were IncK2 and carried the resistance gene *bla*_{CMY-2}. In the remaining isolates, the plasmid type could not be known and, in addition, they did not carry antibiotic resistance genes.

All isolates carrying IncA/C2 (n=8), IncQ (n=6), IncHI (n=2) and IncN (N=1) plasmids carried resistance genes. IncA/C2 plasmids were found with three resistance genes: *aadA1*, *dfrA1* and *sul1*; IncQ plasmids with seven: *strA/B*, *sul2*, *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA*, *aadA1*, *dfrA1* and *sul1*; IncHI plasmids with five: *aadA1*, *aadA2*, *cmlA1*, *sul3* and *tetA*; and IncN plasmid with four: *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *strA/B*, *tetA* and *qnrS1*.

Figure 4.6. Distribution of plasmid replication origins identified in *E. coli* isolates. On the X-axis are represented the different plasmid replication origins identified on the farm, classified by those replication origins with antibiotic resistance genes and associated integrons (red), with associated antibiotic resistance genes but without integrons (orange) and without any of them (green), and ordered from highest to lowest frequency.

6.4. Plasmid Dynamics

The origins of replication identified in the *E. coli* isolates were tracked. In some cases, reconstruction of complete plasmids was possible, and the schematic of the reconstructed plasmid is shown.

6.4.1. Plasmids with resistance genes

6.4.1.1. IncF plasmids

A total of 153 *E. coli* isolates (69.9%) were identified with at least one IncF origin of replication in their genome, being the most frequent origin of replication. In 80 (52.3%) isolates, only one origin of replication was identified (67 FIB type, 12 FII type and one FIC(FII) type), in 63 (41.2%) two origins of replication were identified in the same IncF plasmid (31 FIB + FIC(FII), 31 FIB + FII, 31 FIB + FII, and 31 FIB + FII, respectively); 31 FIB + FII, and one FIA + FIB), while in 10 (6.6%) isolates three replication origins were identified (seven isolates FIA + FIB + FIC(FII) and three FIA + FIB + FII) (Figure 4.7).

None could be reconstructed except for one isolate that underwent long-read sequencing (L1M1-01/05/08/10).

Figure 4.7. Isolates with IncF replication origins. The orange bars correspond to isolates in which only one origin of replication has been identified, the green bars correspond to isolates in which two origins of replication have been identified and the blue bars correspond to isolates in which three origins of replication have been identified.

Of the 153 isolates, antibiotic resistance genes were detected on the IncF plasmid in only 42 (27.5%): *strA/B* (n=22), *bla_{TEM-1B}* (n=20), *tetA* (n=20), *sul2* (n=6), *dfrA5* (n=2), *aadA1* (n=1), *aadA2* (n=1), *cmlA1* (n=1) and *sul3* (n=1).

Replicon sequence typing (RST) of IncF plasmids identified 52 distinct RSTs, the most frequent being F24:A-:B1 (n=20) and F18:A-:B1 (n=14). The RST type F24:A-:B1 was mostly identified in isolates with a single IncFIB replication origin, except in one isolate that had both IncFIB and IncFII replication origins,

while the RST type F18:A-:B1 was mostly identified in isolates with two replication origins (IncFIB and IncFIC(FII)), except in two isolates where only one IncFIB origin was identified. In nine of the isolates, the RST type (F-:A-:B-) could not be determined (Figure 4.24).

Regarding the individual replicons, 22 distinct F alleles were identified, the most common being F18 (n=33) and F24 (n=31); of the 17 A alleles the most frequent was A5 (n=6); finally, the most frequently identified B allele was B1 (n=62), followed by B27 (n=22). In 32 plasmids, the B allele (B-) could not be identified (Figure 4.23).

Antibiotic resistance genes were found in only 16 of the 52 identified RSTs (30.8%). In seven RSTs (F35:A-:B1, F33:A-:B42, F55:A-:B1, F2:A-:B1, F78:A19:B47, F29:A-:B1 and F18:A6:B1) all isolates in which the plasmid was detected carried resistance genes; in nine (F24:A-:B1, F18:A-:B1, F64:A-:B27, F24:A-:B40, F-:A-:B1, F-:A-:B-, F18:A5:B1, F43:A-:B1 and F2:A-:B-), some carried resistance genes and some did not; and in the remaining 36, no antibiotic resistance genes were detected in any case (Figure 4.8).

Figure 4.8. IncF plasmids classified by RST detected in *E. coli*. Data are ordered from highest to lowest frequency. Green bars represent total isolates in which the plasmid was found, and red bars represent isolates carrying antibiotic resistance genes in the IncF plasmid.

IncF plasmids with antibiotic resistance genes

An IncF24:A-B1 plasmid was found in 20 isolates, although resistance genes were detected in only nine of them (45%) in isolates from 14 different STs, including clones 3, 20, 24 and 33 (Table 4.12).

Three distinct multi-resistance regions (results section 6.7) were identified in these plasmids: the MR5 region (*blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2-tetA*) (see section 6.7) which was detected in a single isolate of day-old chicks from batch 1; the MR12 region (*sul2-strA/B-b-blaTEM-1B*) (see section 6.7) which was found in an isolate of laying hens; and the last region detected, MR9 (*blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2*) (see section 6.7) which was found in an isolate of laying hens.7) which was found in one isolate from laying hens and, the last region

detected, MR9 (*blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2*) (see section 6.7), which was found in two isolates from clone 33 (B1-ST155). The *strA/B* resistance gene was also detected in two isolates from clone 24 (B1-ST602), one isolate F-ST1276 and one isolate E/D-ST2944 (Table 4.12).

In isolates where the *strA/B* gene was found on the plasmid, it was found 207 bp away from an IS1133 transposase (Figure 4.9).

Table 4.12. Isolates in which an IncF F24:A-:B1 plasmid was detected

Isolated (n)	Clone No. (Phylogroup-MLST) (nn)	Resistance genes (nnn)
L1/M1/A-18/03/2016 (2)	A-ST2253 (1) B1-ST1304 (1)	MR5 region (<i>blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2-tetA</i>) (1); MR5 region (<i>blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2-tetA</i>) (1) No resistance genes (1)
L1/M4/C- (1)	B1-ST4481	No resistance genes
L2/M1/B-27/05/2016 (1)	Clone 24 (B1-ST602)	<i>strA/B</i> (Figure 4.9)
L2/M4/C- (2)	A/B1-ST1850 (1) Clone 20 (B1-ST4038) (1)	No resistance genes
L3/M1/B-11/10/2016 (3)	Clone 24 (B1-ST602) (2) F-ST1276 (1)	<i>strA/B</i> (Figure 4.9)
L3/M4/E-22/03/2017 (1)	B1-ST101	MR12 region (<i>sul2-strA/B-blaTEM-1B</i>)
L2/M6H/D/15/06/2017 (1)	E/D-ST2944	<i>strA/B</i> (Figure 4.9)
L3/M6/E-30/10/2017 (1)	Clone 33 (B1-ST155)	MR9 Region (<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2</i>)
L3/M8H/E- (1)	A-ST695	No resistance genes
L4/M1/B- (2)	B1-ST2726 (2)	No resistance genes
L4/M4/F- (1)	Clone 20 (B1-ST4038)	No resistance genes
L4/M5H/F- (1)	Clone 3 (A-ST48)	No resistance genes
L4/M6/F- (2)	A-ST746 (1) Clone 3 (A-ST48) (1)	No resistance genes
L4/M7H/F-02/07/2018 (1)	Clone 33 (B1-ST155)	Region MR9

Figure 4.9. Genetic environment of the resistance genes detected in the IncF24:A-:B1 plasmids .

The F18:A-:B1 plasmid was found in 14 isolates, carrying antibiotic resistance genes in only three of them.

This RST was detected in isolates from clones 14 (G-ST117), 18 (B2-ST95) and 19 (B2-ST355), as well as in isolates from eight other STs (Table 4.13). The plasmid carrying resistance genes was detected only in batch 2, in isolates from three different STs. In each of these three isolates, different multi-resistance regions were observed in the plasmid: in one isolate only the *tetA* gene was detected (Figure 4.10), in another isolate the MR6 region (*strA/B-sul2*) was detected and, in the last isolate, the MR5 region (*blaTEM-1B, strA/B, sul2* and *tetA*) was detected in the plasmid (results section 6.7).

Table 4.13. Isolates in which the IncF F18:A-:B1 plasmid was detected

Isolated	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	Resistance genes
L1/M1/A-18/03/2016 (2)	Clone 19 (B2-ST355) (1) B1-ST162 (1)	No resistance genes
L1/M2/B-05/04/2016 (2)	Clone 19 (B2-ST355) (1) B2-ST140	No resistance genes
L2/M1/B-27/05/2016(1)	B2-ST135	<i>tetA</i> (Figure 4.10)
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016 (1)	B1-ST162	MR6 region (<i>strA/B-sul2</i>) (Figure 4.10B)
L2/M3/B-14/09/2016 (1)	B2-ST140	No resistance genes
L2/M7/D-25/09/2017 (1)	B1-ST2599	MR5 Region (<i>blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2-tetA</i>)
L3/M1/B-11/10/2016 (1)	B2-ST1828	No resistance genes
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016 (1)	Clone 14 (G-ST117)	No resistance genes
L4/M1/B-12/03/2017 (1)	B2-ST141	No resistance genes
L4/M2/B-17/03/2017 (1)	Clone 18 (B2-ST95)	No resistance genes
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017 (2)	B1-ST155 (1) A-ST10 (1)	No resistance genes

Figure 4.10. Genetic environment of the *tetA* gene detected in IncF18:A-:B1 plasmids.

The IncF F64:A-:B27 plasmid was found carrying only the *strA/B* resistance gene in five of the 12 isolates in which it was detected, all of them from clone 9 (Table 4.14). This plasmid was identified for 16 months in isolates from five different STs, including isolates from clades 9 (A-ST93), 10 (Clade I-ST770) and 22 (B1-ST937).

The *strA/B* gene was detected with the same genetic environment as in the F24:A-:B1 plasmid (Figure 4.9).

Table 4.14. Isolates in which the IncF F64:A-:B27 plasmid was detected.

Isolated	Clone (SLST-Philogroup)	Resistance genes
L1/M2/A-05/04/2016 (2)	D-ST38 (1) B1-ST937 (1)	No resistance genes
L1/M3/A-24/06/2016 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	<i>strA/B</i>
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016 (1)	Clone 10 (Clade I-ST770)	No resistance genes
L2/M3/B-14/09/2016 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	<i>strA/B</i>
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016 (2)	Clone 9 (A-ST93) (1) F-ST457	<i>strA/B</i> (1) No resistance genes (1)
L3/M3/B-17/01/2017 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	<i>strA/B</i>
L4/M3/B-15/06/2017 (1)	Clone 22 (B1-ST937)	No resistance genes
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017 (3)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	<i>strA/B</i>

The IncF F24:A-:B40 plasmid was detected in 10 isolates, mostly in isolates from ST155 (including isolates from clones 27 and 31), and in isolates from two other STs (Table 4.15).

The plasmid was observed in four of the ten isolates with the *tetA* resistance gene, in isolates from day-old chicks and in batch 2 growth of clones 27 and 31. Three isolates from clone 27 were detected with this plasmid, although the *tetA* gene was found in only two of them (Table 4.15).

The genetic environment of the *tetA* gene was the same as that observed in isolates with the F18:A-B1 plasmid (Figure 4.10).

Table 4.15. Isolates in which the IncF F24:A-:B40 plasmid was detected.

Isolated	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	Resistance genes
L1/M6H/C-27/03/2017 (1)	B1-ST155	No resistance genes
L2/M1/B-27/05/2016 (5)	Clone 27 (B1-ST155) (1) Clone 31 (B1-ST155) (2) B1-ST155 (2)*	<i>tetA</i> (3) No resistance genes (2)*.
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016 (2)	Clone 27 (B1-ST155) (2)	<i>tetA</i> (1)
L4/M6/F-19/03/2018 (2)	A-ST2750* (1) A-ST3270 (1)	No resistance genes

In nine isolates the IncF plasmid could not be typed (F-:A-:B-) (Table 4.16). Four carried antibiotic resistance genes. Two distinct resistance regions were detected in these isolates: in one isolate from laying hens from batch 1, the plasmid carried the MR12 region (*blaTEM-1B-strA/B-tetA*) and in two isolates from laying hens from batch 2, one of them corresponding to clone 8 (A-ST165), the MR1.2 region

(*bla*TEM-1B-*tetA*) was identified (see section 6.7). In an isolate of clone 4 (A-ST48) from batch 3 eggs, the plasmid was found to carry only the *bla*TEM-1B gene at the 3' end of the *tnpR* resolvase of the *Tn3* transposon (Figure 4.11).

Table 4.16. Isolates in which the IncF plasmid could not be typed.

Isolated	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	Resistance genes
L1/M4/C-08/09/2016 (2)	B1-ST1308 (1) D-ST5853 (1)	MR12 region (<i>bla</i> TEM-1B- <i>strA/B-tetA</i>) (1); MR12 region (<i>bla</i> TEM-1B- <i>strA/B-tetA</i>) (1) No resistance genes (1)
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016 (1)	D-ST69	No resistance genes
L2/M6/D-15/06/2017 (1)	Clone 8 (A-ST165)	MR1.2 Region (<i>bla</i> TEM-1B- <i>tetA</i>)
L2/M7/D-25/09/2017 (1)	A-ST170	Region MR1.2
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016 (1)	B1-ST101	No resistance genes
L3/M5H/E-13/07/2017 (1)	Clone 4 (A-ST48)	<i>bla</i> TEM-1B (Figure 4.13)
L3/M8/E-06/06/2018 (1)	A-ST6616	No resistance genes
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017 (1)	A-ST1818	No resistance genes

Figure 4.11. Genetic environment of the *bla*TEM-1B gene detected in the IncF-:A-:B plasmids -

The IncF F-:A-:B1 plasmid was found in nine isolates from batches 2 and 3. These isolates belonged mostly to clone 34 (n=6), although three other STs were also observed. The *bla*TEM-1B gene was only detected in one isolate B1-ST453 from eggs (M7) from batch 3, i.e. in the last sampling from the farm where the IncF-A-:B1 plasmid was detected (Table 4.17). The *bla*TEM-1B gene was found located at the 3' end of the *Tn2* transposase and the *tnpR* resolvase, both elements of the *Tn3* transposon (Figure 4.12).

Table 4.17. Isolates in which the IncF F-:A-:B1 plasmid was detected

Isolated	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	Resistance genes
L2/M3/B- 14/09/2016 (1)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	No resistance genes
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	No resistance genes
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016 (1)	A-ST1716	No resistance genes
L3/M4/E-22/03/2017 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	No resistance genes
L3/M6/E-30/10/2017 (1)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	No resistance genes
L3/M6H/E-12/02/2018 (1)	B1-ST3672	No resistance genes
L3/M7H/F-06/06/2018 (1)	B1-ST453	blaTEM-1B

Figure 4.12. Genetic environment of the *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene detected in the IncF:A:B1 plasmid.

The IncF F18:A5:B1 plasmid was found in seven isolates from batch 1, belonging to clones 15 (B1-ST58) and 16 (B2-ST4456) and three other STs. In six of these seven isolates the plasmid was detected carrying antibiotic resistance genes (Table 4.18). Two distinct multi-resistance regions were identified: the MR1.1 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-tetA}) (see section 6.7) was found in isolates from clones 15 and 16 and in one isolate from eggs ST1056 while the second region identified was the MR5 region (*bla*_{TEM-1B-strA/B-sul2-tetA}) (see results section 6.7), which was found in one isolate ST1484 from growing chicks (Table 4.18).

Table 4.18. Isolates in which the IncF F18:A5:B1 plasmid was detected.

Isolated	SLST-Phlogroup (Clone)	Resistance genes
L1/M1/A-18/03/2016 (2)	B1-ST58 (Clone 15) (1)* (1) B2-ST429 (1)	MR1.1 (<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA</i>) region (Figure 4.13) (1)*. No resistance genes (1)
L1/M2/A-05/04/2016 (4)	F-ST1484 (1)*. B2-ST4456 (Clone 16) (2) B1-ST58 (Clone 15) (1)	MR5 region (<i>blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2-tetA</i>) (1)*. Region MR1.1 (Figure 4.13) (3)
L1/M8H/C-30/10/2017 (1)	B1-ST1056	Region MR1.1 (Figure 4.13)

F18:A5:B1 plasmids carrying the MR1.1 region could be reconstructed, while the one carrying the MR5 region could not be reconstructed. The contigs of the isolates carrying region 1 were compared with a sequence from an *E. coli* plasmid (Tsutsumi et al., 2022 [unpublished]) of 17.1 Kpb (GenBank accession no. AP025663.1). The number of contigs with which the plasmid was reconstructed ranged from 1 (long read sequencing) to 24, and the approximate size was 15.2 - 18.1 Kpb). The reconstructed plasmids showed 96%-97% coverage and 99.98% identity with the reference plasmid.

Figure 4.13.

Reconstruction of the IncF18:A5:B1 plasmid identified in *E. coli* with the MR1 region.

The IncF F43:A-B1 plasmid was found in four isolates from clones 16, 21 and 26, but only one of them detected a resistance gene (*tetA*) (Table 4.19). This isolate was an egg isolate from batch 4 belonging to

clone 26. Its genetic environment is the same as already indicated in the IncF24:A-:B40 plasmid (Figure 4.12).

Table 4.19. Isolates in which the IncF F43:A-:B1 plasmid was detected.

Isolated	Clone (SLST-Philogroup)	Resistance genes
L1/M2/A-05/04/2016 (1)	Clone 16 (B2-ST4456)	No resistance genes
L1/M8/C-30/10/2017 (1)	Clone 21 (B1-ST162)	No resistance genes
L2/M7H/D-25/09/2017 (1)	Clone 26 (B1-ST155)	No resistance genes
L4/M4H/F-09/01/2018 (1)	Clone 26 (B1-ST155)	<i>tetA</i>

The F2:A-:B- plasmid was found in two isolates, although only one of them carried resistance genes (Figure 4.8). These two isolates of different ST (A-ST10 and B1-ST2698), were detected in growing chicks from batch 1 and in hens (M4) from batch 5. In the isolate from batch 5 (A-ST10) a 1.2 integron with a B genetic environment was detected (see section 6.6.2 of the results) (Figure 4.45).

The IncF F33:A-:B42 plasmid was found in two isolates, both carrying the *strA/B* gene. These two isolates, with profile A-ST10, corresponded to laying hens from batch 2 and eggs (M6) from batch 4. The *strA/B* gene was found with the same genetic environment as in the plasmids described above (Figure 4.9B).

The IncF F35:A-:B- plasmid was found in the two isolates of clone 7 (A-ST1303) carrying the multi-resistance region 1.2. These two isolates were from laying hens from samples 6 and 7 of batches 2 and 4, respectively.

The IncF F29:A-:B1 plasmid was found in an egg isolate (M8) from batch 2 (B1-ST162) carrying the *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene and presenting the same genetic environment as the gene identified in the F-:A-:B- plasmid (Figure 4.11).

The IncF plasmid F78:A19:B47 was found in a single B1-ST195 isolate of growing chicks from batch 1, carrying the *strA/B* gene. In addition to detecting the IS1133 transposase, as in other IncF plasmids, at the 3' end of the gene, the TnAs1 transposase from the *Tn3* transposon was also found (Figure 4.14).

Figure 4.14. Genetic background of the *strA/B* resistance gene detected in the F78:A19:B47 plasmid.

The IncF55:A-:B1 plasmid was detected in an egg isolate from batch 5 (B1-ST1431) carrying integron 1.5 (*dfrA5*) with genetic environment B (see results section 6.6.3).

Finally, the F2:A-:B1 plasmid was detected in a laying hen isolate from batch 4 (B1-ST58) carrying an integron 1.5 (*dfrA5*) with the genetic environment A (see section 6.6.3 of the results) and the multi-resistance region 1.1 (see section 6.7 of the results).

6.4.1.2. *IncI* plasmids

An *IncI* replication origin was detected in 31 isolates. In 27 the replication origin was *IncI1* distributed in eight different pMLSTs (ST3 (n=10), ST26 (n=5), ST12 (n=2), ST36 (n=3), ST271 (n=2), ST2 (n=1), ST near 26 (n=2) and ST near 248 (n=2)). An *IncI2* replication origin was detected in four of the isolates.

IncI1/ST3 plasmids

Ten isolates carrying an *IncI1/ST3* plasmid were detected. In nine of these isolates, the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene and the MR2 (*sul2-tetA*) region were identified (see results section 6.7), while in one egg isolate from batch 4, only the MR2 region was detected (Table 4.15).

The *IncI1/ST3* plasmid carrying the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene and the MR2 region was found in two clones (24 and 25) and in four non-clone isolates (B1-ST13021, D-ST5853, B1-ST155, A-ST10 and A-ST1716), with isolates from clone 25 being the most frequent (n=3) (Table 4.15). The isolate with only the MR2 region on the plasmid belonged to clone 3 (A-ST48).

The contigs from each of the isolates were compared to a 107.9 Kpb plasmid detected in chicken *E. coli* isolates (GenBank accession no. KM377240.1) (Published in Zurfluh *et al.*, 2014), yielding coverage and identity percentages of 97-98% and 99.99-100%, respectively. The number of contigs with which the plasmid was reconstructed differed between isolates, ranging from three to 15. The estimated plasmid size ranged from 102.8 to 134.9 Kpb (Table 4.20) (Figure 4.15). The contigs of the isolate containing only the MR2 region in the plasmid showed 95% coverage with the reference sequence in 16 contigs (104.8 Kpb) (Table 4.20).

Table 4.20. Tracking and reconstruction of IncII/ST3 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates.

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date (n)	No. of Clone (Phylogroup-ST) (nn)	Antibiotic resistance genes	No. of contigs from which the plasmid was reconstructed (estimated plasmid size in Kpb) (nnn)	Identity to reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L1/M4/C-08/09/2016	D-ST5853	MR2 region (<i>sul2</i> , <i>tetA</i>) + blaCTX-M-1	15 (120.8 Kpb)	99,9	97
L3/M1/B-11/10/2016 (3)	Clone 24 (B1-ST602) (1)* (1) Clone 25 (G-ST117)** (1) B1-ST155*** (1)	Region MR2 + blaCTX-M-1	3 (134,3 Kpb)* (1) 9 (133,3 Kpb)** (1) 7 (110,6 Kpb)*** (1)	99,99-100	97-98
L3/M2-B-25/10/2016 (3)	Clone 25 (G-ST117) (1)* (1) A-ST10 (1)** A-ST1716 (1)***	Region MR2 + blaCTX-M-1	10 (132,5 Kpb) (1)* (1) 6 (102,4 Kpb) (1)** (1)** (2) 5 (125,7 Kpb) (1)*** (1)***	100	98
L3/M4/E-22/03/2017	Clone 25 (G-ST117)	Region MR2 + blaCTX-M-1	5 (121.8 Kpb)	100	98
L1/M8/C-30/10/2017 (1)	B1-ST13021	Region MR2 + blaCTX-M-1	3 (120.8 Kpb)	99,99	98
L4/M5H/F-15/12/2017 (1)	Clone 3 (A-ST48)	Region MR2	16 (104.8 Kpb)	95	99,97

*GenBank Accession No. of the reference sequence: KT779550.1

Figure 4.15.

Reconstruction of IncII/ST3 plasmids identified in *E. coli* with the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene.

IncII/ST26 plasmids

The IncII/ST26 origin of replication was found in all five isolates of clone 34 carrying the resistance genes *tetA*, *bla*_{SHV-12}, and an integron 1.2 (*aadA2*, *cmlA1*, *aadA1* and *sul3*) (section 6.4.2) in a region of 18.3 kB (Figure 4.16).

The contigs from the isolates were compared to a reference plasmid (GenBank accession no.: LT669764.1) of 117.4 Kpb (Published in Alonso *et al.*, 2016), obtaining minimum coverage and identity values of 96-97% and 99.93-99.99%, respectively. The number of contigs with which the plasmid was reconstructed ranged from two to five, with the estimated size between 115.2 and 128.6 Kpb (Table 4.21).

At the 5' end of the *tetA* gene, at 877 bp, the *tnsB* gene was found, which encodes a protein required for transposition of the Tn7 transposon (Figure 4.16).

Table 4.21. Tracking and reconstruction of IncI1/ST26 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates.

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	No. of contigs forming the plasmid (size of contigs together)	Identity to reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L2/M3/B-14/09/2016	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	2 (115.2 Kpb)	99,99	97
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	3 (118.5 Kpb) 4 (121.7 Kpb)	99,93	96
L3/M4/E-22/03/2017 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	5 (128.6 Kpb) 2 (116.4 Kpb)	99,93-99,99	96-97

*GenBank accession no. of the reference sequence: LT669764.1

Figure 4.16. Reconstruction of IncI1/ST26 plasmids identified in *E. coli* .

IncI1/ST12 plasmids

This plasmid, with the resistance gene *bla*_{CMY-2}, was only found in the two isolates of clone 20 (Table 4.17).

At the 5' end (at 324 bp) of the *bla* gene_{CMY-2}, an IS1380 insertion sequence was identified, encoding an ISEcp1 transposase (Figure 4.17).

The complete sequence of these two isolates was compared to a 101.6 Kpb IncI1 plasmid isolated from *E. coli* (Published in Roer *et al.*, 2018) (GenBank accession no.: MH472638.1), yielding 93% coverage and

99.99% identity in both cases. The number of contigs with which the plasmid was reconstructed was five to six, and the estimated plasmid size between 102.1 and 105.5 Kpb (Figure 4.17).

Figure 4.17. Reconstruction of Inc11/ST12 plasmids identified in *E. coli*.

Inc11-ST36 plasmids

In all three isolates of clone 5, an Inc11/ST36 plasmid carrying the *bla*_{TEM-1B} resistance gene was identified in a Tn3 transposon. A resolvase (*tnpR*) and a transposase from the Tn3 transposon were found at the 3' end of the resistance gene (at 183 bp) (Figure 4.18).

The contigs from the isolates were compared with a sequence from an *E. coli* plasmid isolated from healthy production animals of 89.5 Kbp (Published in Wang *et al.*, 2014) (Genbank accession no.: NC_025180.1), yielding coverage and identity percentages of 94% and 99.93%, respectively. The contigs with which the plasmid was reconstructed were 16 and 26, with an estimated size of 92.6 - 101.1 Kpb.

Figure 4.18. Reconstruction of IncI1/ST36 plasmids identified in *E. coli*.

IncI1/ST271 plasmids

An IncI1/ST271 plasmid carrying the macrolide resistance gene *mphA* was detected in two isolates (one from clone 21 and one from clone 34) from laying hens belonging to different flocks.

The contigs of both isolates were compared to a plasmid published in Liu *et al.*, (2014) of 109.2 Kbp isolated from chicken *E. coli* (GenBank accession no.: NC_024955.2), obtaining 79% coverage and 98.60% identity in both isolates. The plasmid in these isolates consisted of five contigs and the approximate size of the plasmid was between 110.5 and 119.6 kB (Figure 4.19).

An ISKra4, encoding an ISEc51 transposase, was detected at the 5' end of the *mphA* gene. In addition, the *mphA* gene truncated the *Tap* efflux pump gene by 5 bp (Figure 4.19).

Figure 4.19. Reconstruction of IncI1/ST271 plasmids identified in *E. coli*.

*IncI1/ST26** plasmids

An IncI1/ST26* plasmid was identified in two unrelated isolates B1-ST155 and A-ST46 from two different batches. This plasmid could not be typed, its closest pMLST being ST26.

The resistance gene *tetA* was located in this plasmid, as well as an integron 1.8 (*aadA1-aac(3)-Vla-qacEΔ1-sulI*) (see section 6.4.6 of the results) (Figure 4.20). In addition, a number of *mer* genes were identified, encoding proteins involved in mercury resistance.

The contigs of these two isolates were compared with a 122.1 Kbp sequence of *E. coli* isolated from turkeys (Moffat *et al.*, 2020 [unpublished]) (GenBank accession no.: CP059919.1). Sequence comparisons yielded coverage and identity percentages of 93% and 99.98%, respectively. The number of contigs forming the plasmid was 6 and 15, and the size of these contigs together was 124.7 and 147.8 Kbp.

Figure 4.20. Reconstruction of IncI1/ST26* plasmids identified in *E. coli*.

IncI1/ST248 and IncI1/ST2 plasmids*

No antibiotic resistance genes were detected in these IncI1 plasmids. One of the plasmids could not be typed, but its closest ST was ST248 and was found in two isolates from laying hens of the same batch and profile (B1-ST1403).

The IncI1/ST2 plasmid was identified in a single isolate from laying hens from batch 4 (A-ST2750*). The complete genome of this isolate was compared with a 92.3 Kpb sequence of *E. coli* published in Tagg *et al.*, (2014) (GenBank accession no.: NC_025198) obtaining, in six contigs (103.1 Kpb) 89% coverage and 98.89% identity.

IncI2 plasmids

In four of the isolates, an IncI2 type plasmid was identified that did not carry antibiotic resistance genes. This origin of replication was detected in four different isolates, including isolates from clone 1, 13 and 27 (Table 4.22).

The contigs from these four isolates were compared with a sequence from an IncI2 plasmid isolated from 56.7 Kpb APEC strains (Mellata *et al.*, 2012) (GenBank accession no.: NC_019039.1), yielding coverage and identity percentages above 84% and 98.03%, respectively. The number of contigs forming the plasmid in these sequences ranged from 1 to 8, and the sizes of the contigs together ranged from 52.5 to 64.8 Kpb (Table 4.22).

Table 4.22. Tracking and reconstruction of IncI2 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	No. of contigs forming the plasmid (size of contigs together)	identity with reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L1/M2/A-05/04/2016 (2)	Clone 1 (A-ST10) (1)* Clone 1 (A-ST10) (1)* Clone 2 (A-ST10) (1)* F-ST1484 (1)** F-ST1484 (1)**	5 (57.1 kpb)* (57.1 kpb)* (57.1 kpb) 8 (64.8 kpb)** (64.8 kpb)** (64.8 kpb)** (64.8 kpb)	98,03	84-85
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016	Clone 27 (B1-ST155)	1 (54 Kpb)	98,93	85
L1/M3/A-24/06/2016	Clone 13 (D-ST4243)	1 (52.5 Kpb)	98,93	85

*GenBank accession no. of the reference sequence: NC_019039.1

6.4.1.3. *IncX* plasmids

An *IncX* replication origin was detected in 28 isolates, of which 27 were *IncX1* and one *IncX4*.

IncX1 plasmids

In nine of the 27 isolates in which this origin of replication was detected, it was possible to reconstruct the plasmid, which carried the MR3 region (*blaTEM-1B-qnrS1*) (results section 6.7). This plasmid was mostly found in isolates of clone 34 (B1-ST155) (Table 4.23).

The complete sequences of these isolates were compared to a 47.7 Kpb *E. coli* plasmid (Sun *et al.*, 2015) (GenBank accession no. MH121702.1). All isolates showed at least 96% coverage and 99.95% identity (Table 4.18). The isolates differed in the number of contigs with which the plasmid was reconstructed, the minimum being 2 and the maximum 10. The estimated size of the plasmids ranged from 42.2 to 48.5 Kpb (Table 4.23) (Figure 4.21).

Table 4.23. Tracking and reconstruction of IncX1 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates with the multi-resistance region 2.

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date (n)	Clone no. (Phylogroup-ST) (nn)	No. of contigs from which the plasmid was reconstructed (estimated plasmid size) (nnn)	identity with reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L2/M3/B-14/06/2016	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	4 (45.6 Kpb)	99,99	97
L2/M4/D-08/09/2016 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	6 (48,5 Kpb) (1) 3 (47,7 Kpb) (1)	99,99-100	97-99
L3/M1/B- 11/10/2016	B2-ST1828	10 (42.2 Kpb)	99,95	96
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016	C-ST23	7 (45.8 Kpb)	100	97
L3/M4/E-22/03/2017 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	2 (43,7 Kpb) (1) 3 (46,3 Kpb) (1)	99,89	100
L3/M6/E-30/10/2017 (1) L3/M6H/E-30/10/2017 (1)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155) (1)* Clone 34 (B1-ST155) (1)* Clone 4 (A-ST48) (1)** Clone 4 (A-ST48) (1)**	2 (46,6 Kpb) (1)* (1) 3 (47,7 Kpb) (1)** (1)** (2)	99,99	97

*GenBank accession no. of the reference sequence: MH121702.1

Figure 4.21. Reconstruction of IncX1 plasmids identified in *E. coli* carrying the multi-resistance region 2.

Another IncX1 origin of replication with the MR4 region (*tetA* and *bla*_{TEM-1D}) was identified on the farm (see results section 6.7) in seven isolates, six of which belonged to clone 9 (Table 4.24).

The plasmid could not be reconstructed because the origin of replication was in a small plasmid.

Table 4.24. Tracking and reconstruction of IncX1 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates with the multi-resistance region 4.

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date (n)	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)
L1/M3/A-24/06/2016 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016 (1)	A-ST48
L2/M3/B-14/09/2016 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017 (2)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)

IncX1 plasmids were detected in 12 other isolates from 11 different STs, one of them corresponding to clone 9. The resistance gene (*bla*_{TEM-1B}) was only detected in one ST155 isolate from batch 5 eggs (Table 4.25). This *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene was detected preceded (at 108 bp) the TnEc1 transposase of the *Tn3* transposon.

The plasmid could only be reconstructed in two egg isolates, one from batch 1 (B1-ST2165) and one from batch 5 (A-ST695), neither of which contained antibiotic resistance genes. The contigs of the isolates were compared with a 36.1 Kpb *E. coli* IncX plasmid (Sokurenko *et al.*, 2021) (GenBank accession no. CP069446.1 [unpublished]), yielding coverage values between 87 and 92%, and identity values between 98.16 and 98.58%. The plasmid in these isolates consisted of a single contig of between 36 and 39.7 Kpb.

Table 4.25. Tracking and reconstruction of IncX1 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date (n)	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	Antibiotic resistance genes (nn)	identity with reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L1/M5H/C-12/12/2016 (1)	B1-ST2165	No resistance genes	98,16%	87%
L1/M6/C-27/03/2017 (2)	B1-ST1403	No resistance genes		
L1/M8/C-30/10/2017 (1)	D-ST13021	No resistance genes		
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016 (1)	A/B1-ST1850	No resistance genes		
L2/M7/D-25/09/2017 (1)	A-ST48	No resistance genes		
L3/M3/B-17/01/2017 (1)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	No resistance genes		
L3/M6H/E-30/10/2017 (1)	B1-ST3672	No resistance genes		
L3/M8H/E-06/06/2017 (1)	A-ST695	No resistance genes	98,58%	92%
L4/M1/B-12/03/2017 (1)	C-ST88	No resistance genes		
L4/M6/F-29/03/2018 (1)	A-ST1286	No resistance genes		
L5/M6H/C-14/08/2018 (1)	B1-ST155	bla _{TEM} -1B		

*GenBank accession no. of the reference sequence: CP069446.1

IncX4 Plasmids

The IncX4 origin of replication was identified in a D-ST1882 isolate from laying hens, but no antibiotic resistance gene was detected in it.

The contigs of the isolate were compared to a 33.8 Kpb plasmid isolated from *E. coli* published in Zurfluh *et al.* (2018) (GenBank accession no.: CP029976.1) obtaining, with a single 32.7 Kpb contig, 92% coverage and 99.93% identity.

6.4.1.4. IncB/O/K/Z plasmids

An IncB/O/K/Z-type origin of replication was identified in 16 isolates, but an IncK2-type plasmid could be reconstructed in only 11 isolates.

In the others, no resistance genes were identified in the same contig of the origin of replication and no reference plasmid was identified for these isolates that, when contigs were pooled, had coverage and/or identity percentages above 60%. These 5 isolates were from 5 different STs: B2-ST140, Clade I-ST770 (Clone 10), D-ST69, D-ST4243 and A-ST1818.

IncK2 plasmids

This plasmid, carrying the resistance gene *bla_{CMY-2}* was found in all six isolates from clone 13, one from clone 5, one from clone 7, and in isolates ST1158, ST937 and ST155 (Table 4.26).

The genome of the isolates was compared to an 85.9 Kpb IncK2 plasmid (Seiffert *et al.*, 2017) (GenBank accession no.: KR905384.1). The contigs used to reconstruct the plasmids ranged from three to 26. Percentage coverage values ranged from 91% to 100%, while percentage identity values ranged from 99.74% to 99.99%. The estimated size of the plasmids ranged from 89.3 to 106.7 Kpb (Table 4.26).

Table 4.26. Tracking and reconstruction of IncK2 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date	Clone No. (Phylogroup-ST)	No. of contigs forming the plasmid (size of contigs together)	identity with reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L1/M2/A-05/04/2016	B1-ST937	8 (92.5 Kpb)	99,81	98
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016	Clone 11 (D-ST1158)	3 (97.5 Kpb)	99,95	100
L1/M3/A-24/06/2016 (3)	Clone 13 (D-ST4243)	9 (92 Kpb) (1) 6 (99,6 Kpb) (1) 7 (105,6 Kpb) (1)	99,74-99,86	93-98
L2/M3/B-14/09/2016	Clone 13 (D-ST4243)	9 (102.8 Kpb)	99,84	93
L3/M1/B-11/10/2016	B1-ST155	8 (106.7 Kpb)	99,85	98
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016 (2)	Clone 5 (A-ST48)	26 (104,9 bp) (1) 13 (103,9 bp) (1)	99,93-99,96	91-98
L3/M3/B-17/01/2017	Clone 13 (D-ST4243)	9 (100 Kpb)	99,96	92
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017	Clone 13 (D-ST4243)	18 (89.3 Kpb)	99,99	91

*GenBank accession no. of the reference sequence: KR905384.1

The resistance gene *bla_{CMY-2}* was detected at the 5' end (at 324 bp) of an insertion sequence of the IS1380 family encoding the *ISEcp1* transposase. This structure (*bla_{CMY-2} - ISEcp1*) was also identified in the IncI1-ST12 plasmid (see results section 6.4.1.2) (Figure 4.22).

Figure 4.22. Reconstruction of IncK2 plasmids identified in *E. coli*

6.4.1.5. *IncA/C2* plasmids

An IncA/C2 type origin of replication was identified in isolates of clone 9 (A-ST93), carrying a 1.1 integron (*dfrA1-aadA1-qacEA1-sul1*) (see results section 6.6.1) (Figure 4.23). This small plasmid (approximately 23 Kpb) was identified in growing pullets and laying hens from the first four batches (Table 4.27).

The genome of the isolates was compared with the sequence of a 20.4 Kpb plasmid published in GenBank (accession no. GQ293498.1) (Novais *et al.*, 2010), yielding 84% coverage and 99.84% identity in all cases. The number of contigs with which the plasmids were reconstructed ranged from two to four, with the estimated size of the plasmids being between 23.1 and 23.4 Kpb (Table 4.27).

Table 4.27. Tracking and reconstruction of IncA/C2 plasmids identified in *E. coli* isolates.

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date (n)	Number of contigs forming the plasmid (size of contigs together) (nn)	identity with reference plasmid (%)	coverage with reference plasmid (%)
L1/M3/A-24/06/2016	2 (23.1 Kpb)	99,99	85
L2/M3/B-14/09/2016	2 (23 Kpb)	99,99	85
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016	3 (23.1 Kpb)	99,99	85
L3/M3/B-17/01/2017 (2)	2 (23,1 Kpb) (1) 4 (23,4 Kpb) (1)	99,94-99,99	84-85
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017 (3)	2 (23,2-23,6 Kpb)	99,94-99,99	84-85

*GenBank accession no. of the reference sequence: GQ293498.1. All isolates correspond to clone 9 (A-ST93).

Figure 4.23. Reconstruction of IncA/C2 plasmids identified in *E. coli*

6.4.1.6. *IncQ* plasmids

In six unrelated isolates, an IncQ1 replication origin was identified. This plasmid was detected with three different multi-resistance regions (Table 4.28).

Table 4.28. Resistance genes identified in the IncQ1 plasmids detected in *E. coli* isolates

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date	Philogroup-ST	Resistance genes included in the plasmid
L1/M1/A-18/03/2016	B1-ST162	MR6 region (<i>strA/B-sul2</i>)
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016	A-ST1716	<i>strA/B</i> + Integron 1.1 (<i>dfrA1-aadA1-qacE</i> □ <i>1-sul1</i>)
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017	B1-ST58	Region MR6
L2/M7/D-25/09/2017	A-ST48	Integron 1.1 (<i>dfrA1-aadA1-qacE</i> □ <i>1-sul1</i>) + MR7 region (<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2-strA/B</i>)
L1/M8/C-30/10/2017	D-ST13021	Integron 1.1 + Region MR7
L4/M6/F-19/03/2018	A-ST10	Integron 1.1 + Region MR7

The first time it was detected in an ST162 isolate, it was found with the MR6 region (*sul2* and *strA/B*) (see results section 6.7). This structure was identified again seventeen months later in a B1-ST58 isolate (Table 4.28).

In the next occurrence, the plasmid carried an integron 1.1 (*dfrA1-aadA1-sul1*) with a D environment (see section 6.6.1 of the results), in addition to the *strA/B* gene at its 5' end, in a region of 5.6 kB (Table 4.28).

In the other isolates, the plasmid was found with integron 1.1 (see results section 6.6.1) and the MR7 region (*blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2-strA/B*) (see results section 6.7).

IncQ1 plasmids could not be reconstructed because no reference plasmid was found that, when compared, gave results above 60% coverage.

6.4.1.7. IncHI plasmids

An IncHI2A/ST4 plasmid was identified in an A-ST10 (L5/M3) isolate carrying a 1.2 integron (*aadA2-cmlA1-aadA1-sul3*) with structure B (see results section 6.6.2) (Figure 4.24).

The genome of the isolate was compared to a 215.5 Kpb plasmid isolated from *E. coli* published in GenBank (accession no. CP042898.1) (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2019 [unpublished]), yielding coverage and identity values of 93% and 99.47%, respectively.

In addition, the number of contigs forming the plasmid in the isolate was 10, and the size of these contigs together was 207.4 Kpb.

Figure 4.24. Reconstruction of the IncHI2A plasmid identified in *E. coli*

An IncHI1B plasmid carrying the *tetA* gene was identified in a B1-ST155 isolate (growing pullets / batch 2). At the 3' end of the replication origin (at 4 Kpb) an IS6 insertion sequence (IS26) was found; while at the 3' end of the *tetA* gene, the TnAs1 transposase of the *Tn3* transposon was identified (Figure 4.25).

Figure 4.25. Linear schematic of an IncHIB plasmid fragment identified in an *E. coli* ST155 isolate

The complete plasmid could not be reconstructed as no similar reference plasmid was found.

6.4.1.8. *IncN* plasmids

Only one IncN-ST3 plasmid was identified in one of the two isolates of clone 10 (laying hens (M4) from batch 2). In this plasmid, the MR14 region (*qnrS1-blaTEM-1B-tetA-strA/B*) was detected (results section 6.7), sharing the *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene, in addition to the *strA/B* gene (Figure 4.26).

The complete sequence of the isolate was compared with a 52.5 Kpb IncN plasmid (Dolejska *et al.*, 2013) (GenBank accession no.: JX065631), yielding 98 and 100% coverage and identity percentages, respectively. The plasmid consisted of a single contig of 52.8 Kpb.

The *bla*_{TEM-1B} and *qnrS1* genes were identified at the same distance from each other (5.4 Kpb) as those found in the IncX1 plasmid (section 6.3.1.3), showing the same genetic environment for these two genes.

Figure 4.26.

Reconstruction of the IncN-ST3 plasmid identified in *E. coli*.

6.4.2. Plasmids without resistance genes

6.4.2.1. Col-type plasmids

Eighty-seven Col replication origins were found in 63 isolates distributed as follows: 37 Col156, 26 Col(MG828) and 24 ColpVC (Table 4.29).

Col(MG828) replication origins were identified from laying hens from batch 1 to eggs from sample 6 of batch 5. This origin was mostly identified in isolates from laying hens (n=7) and eggs (n=4) (Table 4.29).

The Col156 origin was identified from growing pullets from batch 1 to laying hens (M6) from batch 4. This replication origin was identified mostly in isolates from growing pullets (n=20) (Table 4.29).

Isolates with ColpVC origins of replication were identified from day-old chicks from batch 1 to laying hens (M7) from batch 4. This origin of replication was mostly identified in isolates from laying hens (n=11) (Table 4.29).

Table 4.29. Col-type replication origins detected in *E. coli* isolates distributed by batch and sampling.

Origin of replication	Lot 1	Lot 2	Lot 3	Lot 4	Lot 5
Col156 (n=37)	M2 (n=2) M3 (n=3) M4 (n=1)	M2 (n=2) M3 (n=1) M4H (n=1) M8 (n=1)	M1 (n=2) M2 (n=6) M3 (n=2) M4 (n=1) M5 (n=1) M4 (n=1)	M1 (n=7) M2 (n=1) M3 (n=3) M4 (n=1) M6 (n=1)	
Col(MG828) (n=26)	M4 (n=1) M5H (n=1) M8 (n=1)	M1 (n=1) M8H (n=1)	M1 (n=1) M2 (n=2) M4 (n=2) M6 (n=2) M8H (n=1)	M6 (n=1)	M6H (n=1)
ColpVC (n=24)	M1 (n=1) M2 (n=1) M4 (n=1) M5H (n=1)	M2 (n=3) M3 (n=2) M4 (n=1) M6 (n=1)	M3 (n=2) M5H (n=1) M6 (n=2)	M1 (n=2) M4 (n=5) M7 (n=1)	

M: Sampling

More than one Col replication origin was detected in 17 isolates, as these plasmids can coexist in the same bacterium.

In 13 isolates, two different Col replication origins were found: In seven Col156 and ColpVC, in five Col156 and Col(MG828) and, in one, Col(MG828) and ColpVC origins (Table 4.30).

In addition, in four isolates a replication origin of the same type was found more than once: in one isolate from growing chicks from batch 2, 12 Col(MG828) replication origins were detected, in two isolates from day-old chicks from batch 4, two Col156 origins were found in each of the isolates, and in one isolate from growing chicks from batch 4, three Col156 origins were identified (Table 4.30). Both in isolates where more than one different Col origin was identified and in isolates where more than one Col replication origin of the same type was found, these were detected in different contigs.

Table 4.30. Isolates in which more than one Col type replication origin was identified.

Batch/sampling/location	Col156	Col(MG828)	ColpVC
L1/M2/A	1		1
L1/M4/C	1	1	
L1/M5H/C		1	1
L2/M2/B		12	
L2/M2/B	1		1
L2/M3/B	1		1
L3/M1/B	1	1	
L3/M2/B	1	1	
L3/M2/B	1	1	

L3/M3/B	1		1
L3/M4/E	1	1	
L4/M1/B	2		
L4/M1/B	2		
L4/M1/B	1		1
L4/M1/B	1		1
L4/M3/B	3		
L4/M6/F	1		1

6.4.2.2.. Plasmids P0111

A p0111 origin of replication was identified in 59 isolates. Thirty of these isolates were from laying hens, this being the growth phase of the animals in which the plasmid was most frequently detected, and nine were egg isolates. In addition, the isolates in which this plasmid was identified had mostly phylogroup A (n=31) and phylogroup B1 (n=23).

The contigs from these isolates were compared to a 92.2 Kpb plasmid p0111 (Darphorn *et al.*, 2021) (GenBank accession no.: NZ_MW390536), yielding coverage and identity percentages of 83% and 98.96%, respectively. The number of contigs with which the plasmid was constructed ranged from 5 to 9, and the sizes of these contigs together ranged from 86.5 to 97.5 Kpb.

No resistance genes were identified in the contigs forming the plasmid in any of the isolates, but *virB* genes were identified in the plasmid.

6.4.2.3. *IncY* plasmids

This origin of replication was detected in 14 isolates from 12 different STs, including one isolate from clone 10, one isolate from clone 12 and two isolates from clone 33, one of them corresponding to eggs (Table 4.31).

Table 4.31. Isolates in which the IncY plasmid was detected.

Batch/sampling/location/sampling date (n)	Clone no. (Phylogroup-ST) (nn)
L1/M4/C-08/09/2016 (2)	B1-ST1608 (1) E-ST1629 (1)
L2/M1/B-27/05/2016 (1)	B2-ST135
L2/M2/B-13/06/2016 (1)	Clone 10 (Clade I- ST770)
L4/M2/B-17/03/2017 (1)	B1-ST2329
L1/M6/C-27/03/2017 (1)	B1-ST1079
L2/M6/D-15/06/2017 (1)	A-ST205
L3/M5/E-13/07/2017 (1)	Clade III- ST2371
L2/M7/D-25/09/2017 (2)	A-ST170 (1) B1-ST1599 (1)
L3/M6/E-30/10/2017 (3)	Clone 33 (B1-ST155) (1) Clone 12 (D-ST394) (1) B1-ST1246 (1)
L4/M7H/F-02/07/2018 (1)	Clone 33 (B1-ST155)

No resistance genes were identified in the contigs in which this origin of replication was detected and, due to the small size of the contigs, the plasmid could not be reconstructed.

6.5. Integrons

Integrons were detected in 46 of the 218 (21.1%) *E. coli* isolates. Class 1 integrons (nine resistance cassette combinations) were identified in 44 and a class 2 integron in two.

Integrons were numbered with a first number indicating the type of integrase (class 1 integrase or class 2 integrase), and a second correlative number, ordered according to the number of isolates in which it is identified, from most to least frequent (Table 4.32).

In six of the integrons (1.1, 1.2, 1.6, 1.7, 1.8 and 2) more than one resistance cassette was identified. Typically, when more than one cassette was detected, aminoglycoside and trimethoprim resistance cassettes were detected in the same integron. In addition, in four integrons (1.1, 1.2, 1.7 and 1.8), sulphonamide resistance cassettes were detected together with aminoglycoside and trimethoprim resistance cassettes. In integrons where only one cassette was identified (1.3, 1.4, 1.5 and 1.9), this was trimethoprim resistance.

Table 4.32. Integrons identified in *E. coli*. The name of each integron, the integrase type (1 or 2), the resistance cassettes and the number of isolates in which the integron has been identified are shown.

Designation integron	Integrase type	Resistance cassettes	No. of isolates in which the integron has been identified
1.1	1	<i>dfrA1-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1</i>	15
1.2	1	<i>aadA2-cmlA1-aadA1-sul3</i>	14
1.3	1	<i>dfrA14</i>	3
1.4	1	<i>dfrA1</i>	2
1.5	1	<i>dfrA5</i>	2
1.6	1	<i>dfrA17-aadA5</i>	2
1.7	1	<i>bla_{OXA.1} - aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1</i>	2
1.8	1	<i>aadA1-aac(3)-Vla-qacEΔ1-sul1</i>	2
1.9	1	<i>dfrA17</i>	1
2	2	<i>dfrA1-sat1-aadA1</i>	2

6.6. Dynamics of integrons

6.6.1. Integron 1.1.

Integron 1.1 (*dfrA1-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1*) was the most frequent (15 isolates) and the one detected for the longest time (24 months). This integron showed the characteristic structure of class 1 integrons including at the 3' end the *qacEΔ1* gene truncated by the *sul1* gene (Figures 4.27, 4.28, 4.29 and 4.30).

The contigs in which the integron was detected from each of the isolates were compared to a 2.8 Kpb fragment of an *E. coli* sequence (GenBank accession no.: GQ293498.1:c6586-9394) (Novais *et al.*, 2010), resulting in 100% coverage and 99.93% identity for all isolates (Table 4.33).

This integron was maintained in the *E. coli* faecal population through four patterns: carried by IncA/C2 plasmids carried by isolates of clone 9; by IncQ plasmids (two different patterns) (detected in unrelated isolates) and by the chromosome of unrelated isolates (table 4.33).

Table 4.33. *E. coli* isolates in which integron 1.1 (*dfrA1-aadA1-qacEA1-sul1*) was detected.

Batch/sampling/Location - date of sampling (n)	Clone no. (Phylogroup-ST) (nn)	Genomic localisation of the integron	Genetic environment (nnn)
L1/M3/A-24/06/2016	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	IncA/C2	A
L2/M3/B-19/09/2016	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	IncA/C2	A
L3/M2/B-25/10/2016	A-ST1716	incQ	D
L2/M4/D-15/11/2016	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	IncA/C2	A
L3/M3/B-17/01/2017 (2)	Clone 9 (A-ST93)	IncA/C2	A
L4/M1/B-12/03/2017	C-ST88	Chromosome	B
L4/M4/F-22/08/2017 (4)	A-ST10 (1) Clone 9 (A-ST93) (3)	Unknown (1) IncA/C2 (3)	C (1) A (3)
L2/M7/D-25/09/2017	A-ST48	incQ	C
L1/M8/C-30/10/2017	D-ST13021	incQ	C
L4/M6/F-19/03/2018	A-ST10	incQ	C
L3/M8/E-06/06/2018	A-ST6616	Chromosome	B

Four distinct genetic environments were identified for integron 1.1 (Figures 4.27, 4.28, 4.29 and 4.30). Environments A, B and C shared an IS21 insertion sequence at the 3' end, encoding the IS1326 transposase, 804 bp from the *sul1* gene of the integron.

In environment A, a Tn3 transposase (*tnAs1*) was identified at the 5' end (at 1.3 kb) (Figure 4.39). The integron with structure A was identified in all cases in an IncA/C2 type plasmid (see section 6.4.1.5 of the results).

Figure 4.27. Integron 1.1: genetic environment A

In the second genetic background (B) (Figure 4.40) the TnAs1 transposase was not detected at the other end and was identified on the chromosome of two unrelated isolates.

Figure 4.28. Integron 1.1: Genetic environment B

For environment C, the multi-resistance region 6 (*blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2-strA/B*) was identified at the 5' end of the integron (at 808 bp) (see section 6.7 of the results) (Figure 4.41).

The C structure was located in IncQ plasmids (see section 6.4.1.6 of the results). This structure was detected in four unrelated isolates (Table 4.28).

Figure 4.29.

Integron 1.1: genetic environment C

In the isolate with profile ST1716, the integron was detected with a different structure (structure D) on an IncQ plasmid. At the 5' end of the integron, the *strA/B* gene was found (Figure 4.42).

Figure 4.30. Integron 1.1: genetic environment D

6.6.2. Integron 1.2.

Integron 1.2 (*aadA2-cmlA1-aadA1-emrE-sul3*) was the second most frequent integron (14 isolates), identified in isolates from four different MLST profiles, mostly with ST155 profile (n=8) (Table 4.34). In this integron, the *rdmC* gene (uniprotKB no.: Q54528) encoding a methylesterase was found in all cases, 1 Kpb away from the integrase and truncated at 73 bp with the *aadA2* resistance gene (Figure 4.31). This structure (IntI1-*rdmC*- *aadA2*) is not described in the reference integron.

Figure 4.31. General structure of the 1.2 integrons identified in *E. coli*

In addition, in all isolates, an IS256 insertion sequence encoding the IS406 transposase between the *emrE* gene (UniProtKB No.: P23895) (which confers resistance to a wide variety of toxic compounds) and the *sul3* gene was also identified within the integron. In addition, all 1.2 integrons found were associated with *Tn3* transposon elements (TnAs1 and TnAs3 transposases).

Two different structures were found for the genetic environment of this integron. In both structures, an IS26 insertion sequence encoding an IS6 transposase (at 2.1 Kpb) was identified at the 3' end of the integron (Figures 4.32 and 4.33).

The contigs in which the 1.2 integron was identified in the isolates were compared to the sequence of an integron identified in *Shigella* isolates by Chang *et al.* (2011) (*GenBank* accession no.: FJ748514). The percentages of identity obtained were between 93 and 100%; and the percentages of coverage between 99.98 and 100% (Table 4.43).

Table 4.34. *E. coli* isolates in which integron 1.2 (*aadA2-cmlA1-aadA1-sul3*) was detected.

Batch/sampling/Location - date of sampling (n)	Clone no. (Phylogroup-ST) (nn)	Mobile genetic element in which the integron is located (nnn)	Genetic environment (nnnn)	% of identity with reference integron* (nnnnn)	% coverage with reference integron* (nnnnnn)
L2/M3/B - 14/09/2016	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	IncI1-ST26	A	100	99,99
L2/M4/D - 15/11/2016 (4)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155) (2)* (2) Clon 20 (B1-ST4038) (1)** A/B1-ST1850 (1)** A/B1-ST1850 (1)** A/B1-ST1850 (1)**	IncI1-ST26 (2)* IncI1-ST26 (2)* IncI1-ST26 (2)* IncI1-ST26 (2)* Unidentified plasmid (2)**.	A (2)* B (2)**	100 (3) 93 (1)	100 (1) 99,99 (1) 99,98 (1)
L3/M4/E - 22/03/2017 (2)	Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	IncI1-ST26	A	100 (2)	99,99 (1) 100 (1)
L4/M4/F - 22/08/2017	Clone 20 (B1-ST4038) (1)	Unidentified plasmid (1)	B	100	100
L3/M6/E - 30/10/2017 (2)	(H) Clone 4 (A-ST48) (1) Clone 33 (B1-ST155) (1)	Unidentified plasmid (2)	B	100	100
L5/M3/A - 28/11/2017	A-ST10	IncHI2	B	100	100
L5/M5/C - 23/04/2018	A-ST10	IncF [F2:A-:B-] [F2:A-:B-] IncF [F2:A-:B-]	B	100	99,99
L4/M7/F - 02/07/2018	(H) Clone 33 (B1-ST155)	Unidentified plasmid	B	100	100
L5/M6/C - 14/08/2018	(H) B1-ST155	Unidentified plasmid	B	100	100

*GenBank accession number of the reference sequence: FJ748514.1.

In the first genetic environment (structure A), the *bla_{SHV-12}* gene was identified after the IS6 insertion sequence (IS26), followed by the *tnAs3* transposase of the *Tn3* transposon. The *tetR* and *tetA* genes were also observed at the 3' end of the *bla_{SHV-12}* gene. Finally, at the 5' end of the *tetA* gene (at about 4 Kpb), the *repA* protein, replication initiator of the IncI1 plasmid, the plasmid in which it was identified (see section 6.3.1.2 of the results), was identified (Figure 4.32).

This environment was detected in five ST155 isolates from clone 34 (Table 4.29).

Figure 4.32. Integron 1.2: genetic environment A

The second genetic environment detected (B) was identified in ten isolates and, during the last 12 months in which this integron was detected, only the B structure was observed.

This structure was found with a TnAs transposase at the 5' end of the integron, associated with the *Tn3* transposon, which differed among the ten isolates (Figure 4.33). Structure B with the *Tn3* transposase transposon type 1 (TnsA1), was observed in five isolates, one of them from eggs. The TnsA3 transposase was found in two isolates from clone 20, two from clone 33 and one isolate ST155 (Table 4.29).

All 1.2 integrons that displayed this genetic environment were located on plasmid DNA, although in seven the type of plasmid carrying the integron could not be identified (Table 4.49).

Figure 4.33. Integron 1.2: genetic environment B

6.6.3. *Integrans 1.3, 1.4, 1.5 and 1.9*

Integrans 1.3 (*dfrA14*), 1.4 (*dfrA1*), 1.5 (*dfrA5*) and 1.9 (*dfrA17*) carried only one trimethoprim resistance gene.

Integron 1.3 (*dfrA14*) (Figure 4.34) was identified in three isolates of different phylogroup and MLST profile: A-ST2253, F-ST1884 and B1-ST101, found for the first time in day-old chicks from batch 1.

Figure 4.34. Schematic of the structure of the integron 1.3.

This integron was found in all isolates in a small chromosomal contig (1571, 2298 and 2359 bp) in which only the integrase and the *dfrA14* gene were identified. The contig from each of the isolates was compared with a fragment of an *E. coli* sequence corresponding to a class 1 integron with the *dfrA14* resistance gene (Accession no.; KM023153.1:c:79841-81482; Fortini *et al.* (2015), in all cases obtaining 100% identity and at least 79% coverage.

Integron 1.4 (*dfrA1*) was found on the chromosome of two isolates at the 3' end of a TnAs1 transposase (at 1.3 Kpb). The *tetR* and *tetA* genes were also identified at the 5' end of the transposase (Figure 4.35). Integron 1.4 was detected in a single sampling, in two isolates from laying hens from the same flock (A-ST48 and A-ST746).

The contigs in which the integron was found were compared with a sequence published in Pryamchuk *et al.* (2009) [unpublished] of an *E. coli* class 1 integron (GenBank accession no.: GQ924770.1), obtaining in both isolates 100% identity and 62% coverage.

Figure 4.35. Schematic of the structure of the 1.4 integron and its genetic environment.

Integron 1.5 (*dfrA5*), was found on an IncF plasmid in two isolates. The TnAs1 transposase was identified at the 5' end (2.4 Kpb from the integron) (Figures 4.36 and 4.37).

The contig of each isolate in which the 1.5 integron was identified was compared to an integron published in Verner-Jeffreys *et al.*, (2009) (GenBank accession no.: FM957880), yielding 95-96% coverage and 100% identity.

This integron was identified in isolates with different profiles (B1-ST58 and B1-ST1431), one of them corresponding to an egg sampling. In isolate B1-ST58, the IncF plasmid detected was F2:A-:B1, while in isolate B1-ST1431, the plasmid was F55:A-:B1.

Two distinct genetic environments were identified for this integron: in the IncF2:A-:B1 plasmid, the multi-resistance region 1.2 and a TnAs1 transposase at the 5' end of the integron were identified (Figure 4.48).

Figure 4.36. Integron 1.5: Genetic environment A

In the F55:A-:B1 plasmid, an IS26 insertion sequence encoding the IS6 transposase was detected at the 3' end of the integron (at 1.2 Kpb) (Figure 4.37).

Figure 4.37. Integron 1.5: Genetic Environment B

In isolate ST58 the insertion sequence IS26 (IS6) was identified in a small contig (820 bp). As it is in a different contig than the integron and the integron is so small in size, it could not be determined whether its position is the same as in the case of the B structure.

Integron 1.9 (*dfrA17*) (Figure 4.38) was identified in an egg isolate of clone 3 (A-ST48). This integron was located in the chromosomal DNA, however, the genetic environment could not be known as it was located in a small contig.

Figure 4.38. Schematic of the structure of integron 1.9.

6.6.4. Integron 1.6

Integron 1.6 (*dfrA17-aadA5*) was identified in two isolates (B1-ST162 and B1-ST2599). At its 5' end, the *bin3* gene, encoding an element of the *Tn552* transposon, was observed (at 679 bp) (Figure 4.39).

This integron was located in plasmid DNA, but the plasmid type could not be identified, as no plasmid replication origin was detected in the same contig.

Figure 4.39. Schematic of the structure of the 1.6 integron and its genetic environment.

6.6.5. Integron 1.7

Integron 1.7 (*bla_{OXA-1}-aadA1-qacEA1-sul1*) was identified on the chromosome of two isolates from clone 15, presenting the characteristic structure of class 1 integrons that includes at the 3' end the *qacEA1* gene truncated 6 bp by the *sul1* gene (Figure 4.40).

An open reading frame commonly described in class 1 integrons (*orf5*), encoding a protein of unknown function, was also observed at the 3' end, and an IS21 insertion sequence, encoding an IS1326 transposase, was identified at the same end of the integron (Figure 4.40).

Figure 4.40. Schematic of the structure of the 1.7 integron and its genetic environment.

The contigs of the isolates in which the 1.8 integron was identified were compared with a published sequence from *E. coli* (Dubois *et al.*, 2003) (GenBank accession no. AY224185.1), yielding 100% coverage and 99.98% identity.

6.6.6. Integron 1.8

Integron 1.8 (*aadA1-aac(3)-Vla-qacEA1-sul1*) was identified on an IncI1/ST26* plasmid (see results section 6.4.1.2) in two isolates B1-ST155 and A-ST46 corresponding to day-old chicks from batch 3 and laying hens from batch 2, respectively.

The integron was found close to a Tn3 transposon, with the TnAs3 transposase identified at the 5' end (1.2 Kpb away) of the integrase gene (Figure 4.51). In addition, between the *aac(3)-Vla* and *qacEA1* genes, an IS256 insertion sequence, encoding an ISEc58 transposase, was detected. At the 3' end of the integron, the insertion sequence IS21 (IS1326) was identified at 1156 bp (Figure 4.41).

Figure 4.41. Schematic of the structure of the 1.8 integron and its genetic environment.

The contigs in which the integron was detected were compared to a sequence fragment from an *E. coli* IncI1 plasmid (Moffat *et al.*, 2020 [unpublished]), which contained the same integron (GenBank accession no.: CP059919.1: c12216-19139), yielding 100% identity in both isolates and 99.98-100% coverage.

6.6.7. Integron 2

The class 2 integron (*dfrA1-sat1-aadA1*) has been identified on chromosome two isolates A-ST170 and A-ST48 from laying hens from batch 1 and growing pullets from batch 2 with two different genetic backgrounds, both on the chromosome (Figures 4.42 and 4.43).

In isolate A-ST170 (structure A), three genes involved in the transposition of the *Tn7* transposon (*tnsC*, *tnsB* and *tnsA*) were detected at the 5' end. In addition, an IS3, encoding the transposase ISEc52, was identified at the 3' end of the integron (Figure 4.42).

Figure 4.42. Integron 2.1: genetic environment A

The sequence of the contig (11.9 Kpb) in which the integron (with structure A) was identified was compared with a partial sequence of *E. coli* corresponding to a Tn7 transposon (GenBank accession no. AB188272.1) (Fujihara *et al.*, 2010 [unpublished]), resulting in 100% identity and coverage.

In the S-ST48 isolate, the TnAs1 transposase was identified, associated with *Tn3* at the 5' end of the integron. The *ybeA*, *ybfA*, *ybfB* and *ybgA* genes were identified at the 3' end of the integron. The transposon transposon protein *Tn7* (*TnsB*), and an IS66 insertion sequence encoding an ISEc78 transposase were also identified (Figure 4.43).

Figure 4.43. Integron 2.1: genetic environment B

The contig (16.1 Kpb) in which the integron (structure B) was identified was compared to a sequence of an integron found in an *E. coli* isolate (GenBank accession no.: FJ591055.1) (Laroche *et al.*, 2009), obtaining 100% coverage and 99.72% identity.

In neither of the two class 2 integrons has the 3' conserved region commonly described in class 2 integrons composed of five *tns* genes been observed.

6.6.8. Faulty integrons

In three unrelated isolates (Table 4.35), a 341 bp fragment of the *IntI1* gene, which is 1119 bp long, was identified. In all, the *sull* gene was found at the 3' end of the integrase fragment (at 2.5 Kpb) (Figure 4.44) in a contig corresponding to the chromosomal DNA.

Table 4.35. Isolates with defective integrons identified in *E. coli*

Batch/sampling/Location - sampling date	Philogroup-ST
L1/M2-A-05/04/2016	B1-ST937
L4/M1-B-12/03/2017	B1-ST3935* B1-ST3935* B1-ST3935* B1-ST3935* B1-ST3935
L5/M4-C-09/01/2018	B2-ST919

Figure 4.44. Schematic of defective integron and its genetic environment

6.7. Regions of multi-resistance

Fifteen MR regions have been detected (Table 4.36).

Table 4.36. multi-resistance regions identified in *E. coli* isolates

Region MR (n)	Resistance genes	Region size in kb (n)	Location (n)
1 (10) • 1.1* • 1.2**	<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA</i>	*8,8 (5) **3,1 (5)	Plasmid IncF (10)
2 (9)	<i>blaCTX-M-1-tetA-sul2</i>	26	IncI1/ST3 plasmid
3 (9)	<i>blaTEM-1B-qnrS1</i>	6,9	Plasmid IncX1
4 (6)	<i>blaTEM-1D-tetA</i>	5,5	Plasmid IncX1
5 (4)	<i>blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2- blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2- blaTEM-1B-strA/B-sul2- tetA</i>	9	Plasmid IncF (3) Chromosome (1)
6 (4)	<i>strA/B-sul2</i>	2,5	IncQ Plasmid (2) Plasmid IncF (1) Chromosome (1)
7 (3)	<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2- strA/B</i>	8,8	IncQ Plasmid
8 (2)	<i>sul1-tetA</i>	2,4	Chromosome
9 (2)	<i>blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2</i>	7	Plasmid IncF
10 (2)	<i>sul2-dfrA36-floR</i>	6,2	Chromosome

11 (1)	<i>catA1-tetA-sul2</i>	6,9	Chromosome
12 (1)	<i>blaTEM-1B-strA/B-tetA</i>	11,5	Plasmid IncF
13 (1)	<i>sul2-strA/B-blaTEM-1B</i>	3,2	Plasmid IncF
14 (1)	<i>qnrS1-blaTEM-1B-tetA-strA/B</i>	13,5	Plasmid IncN
15 (1)	<i>su2-tetA</i>	2,2	IncI1/ST3 plasmid

n: number of isolates

The MR1 region (*blaTEM-1B-tetA*) was found with two different sizes (8.8 and 3.1 Kpb) in IncF plasmids (Table 4.37).

The MR1.1 region was identified on IncF plasmids (F18:A5:B1 and F18:A6:B1) in five isolates from batch 1 of clones 15, 16 and one isolate ST1056 from eggs (Table 4.37).

The MR1.2 region was then detected on F plasmids (F35:A-:B-, F-:A-:B- and F2:A-:B1) in five isolates (clones 7, 8 and 10, and one isolate ST58 from laying hens from batches 2 and 4 (Table 4.37).

Table 4.37. *E. coli* isolates in which the MR1_(*blaTEM-1B* and *tetA*) region was detected.

Region RM	Genomic location (n)	Clone No. (Phylogroup-MLST) (nn)	Batch/sample-date (nnn)
1.1	Plasmid IncF(F18:A5:B1)	Clone 15 (B1-ST58)	L1/M1-03/2016
1.1	Plasmid IncF (F18:A5:B1) (1) Plasmid IncF (F18:A6:B1) (2)	Clone 15 (B1-ST58) (1) Clone 16 (B2-ST4456) (2)	L1/M2-04/2016 (3)
1.1	Plasmid IncF(F18:A5:B1)	B1-ST1056	L1/M8H-10/2017
1.2	Plasmid IncF (F35:A-:B-) (1) Plasmid IncF (F-:A-:B-) (1)	Clone 7 (A-ST1303) (1) Clone 8 (A-ST165) (1)	L2/M6-06/2017 (2)
1.2	IncF plasmid (F35:A-:B-)	A-ST170	L2/M7-09/2017
1.2	Plasmid (IncF F2:A-:B1)	B1-ST58	L4/M4-08/201
1.2	IncF plasmid (F35:A-:B-)	Clone 7 (A-ST1303)	L4/M7-07/2018

n: number of isolates

In the environment of the MR1 region (*blaTEM-1B-tetA*), elements of the *Tn3* transposon (the *Tn2* transposase, the *tnpR* resolvase and the *TnAs1* transposase) were detected. Differences in the genetic environment of the regions were observed: in the MR1.1 region a *TnsA1* transposase was identified among the resistance genes, which was not identified in the MR1.2 region (Figures 4.45 and 4.46).

Figure 4.45. Genetic environment of the MR 1.1 and 1.2 regions

Figure 4.46. Comparison of MR 1.1 and MR1.2 regions.

The 26.4 Kpb MR2 region (*blaCTX-M-1-tetA-sul2*) was identified in all isolates on an IncI1/ST3 plasmid (Table 4.41).

Table 4.41. *E. coli* isolates in which the MR2 region (*bla*_{CTX-M-1}-*tetA*-*sul2*) was detected in an IncI1/ST3 plasmid.

SLST-Phylogroup	Batch/sampling-date
5853	L1/M4
155	L1/M8
Clone 24 (ST155) (1) Clone 25 (ST117) (1) ST155 (1)	L3/M1 (3)
A-ST10 (1) 1716 (1) Clone 25 (ST117) (1)	L3/M2 (3)
Clone 25 (ST117)	L3/M4

The MR3 region (*qnrS1*-*bla*_{TEM-1B}) was found with a size of 6.9 Kpb. The region was identified mainly in isolates from clone 34 (ST155), but also in isolates from clone 4 (ST48), and in isolates ST23 and ST128 over 13 months, in batches 2 and 3 (Table 4.38).

Table 4.38. *E. coli* isolates in which the MR3 region (*qnrS1*-*bla*_{TEM-1B}) was detected on an IncX plasmid.

Clone No. (Phylogroup-MLST)	Batch/sampling-date
Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	L2/M3-09/2016
Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	L2/M4-11/2016
B2-ST1828	L3/M1-10/2016
C-ST23	L3/M2-10/2016
Clone 34 (B1-ST155)	L3/M4-03/2017 (2)
Clone 34 (B1-ST155) (1) Clone 4 (A-ST48) (1)	L3/M6-10/2017 (2)

The genes included in the region shared the same genetic environment in all isolates in which it was identified (*bla*_{TEM-1B}-*tnpR*-*Tn2*-*IS3*-*qnrS1*-*ISKr*) (Figure 4.48).

Figure 4.48. Genetic environment of the MR3 region.

The MR4 region (*bla*TEM-1D-*tetA*) was observed on an IncX1 plasmid in six isolates, mostly from clone 9 (A-ST93) and in one isolate ST48. The TnAs1 transposase was detected at the 5' end of the *tetA* gene, as well as at the 3' end of the *tetR* gene (Figure 4.49).

Figure 4.49. Genetic environment of the MR4 region

The MR5 region (*bla*TEM-1B-*strA/B-sul2-tetA*) was identified in four isolates with distinct STs, none of which belonged to a clone. The first two times it was identified was on IncF plasmids (F24:A-:B1 and F18:A5:B1); 14 months later, it was found on chromosomal DNA from an isolate of laying hens from batch 4 and, finally, again on an IncF plasmid (F18:A5:B1) from laying hens from batch 2. In total, the region was detected for 17 months on the farm (Table 4.39).

Table 4.39. *E. coli* isolates in which the MR5 region (*bla*TEM-1B-*strA/B-sul2-tetA*) was detected.

Genomic localisation	SLST-Philogroup	Batch/sampling-date
IncF plasmid (F24:A-:B1)	A-ST2253	L1/M1-03/2016
Plasmid IncF (F18:A5:B1)	F-ST1484	L1/M2-04/2016
Plasmid IncF (F18:A5:B1)	B1-ST2599	L2/M7-09/2017
Chromosome	B2-ST1818	L4/M4-08/2017

In this region, the Tn2 transposase and the *Tn3* transposon resolvase were detected at the 5' end of the *bla*TEM-1B gene and the TnAs1 transposase, also associated with the *Tn3* transposon, between the *sul2* and *tetA* genes (Figure 4.50).

Figure 4.50. Genetic environment of the MR5 region.

The MR6 region (*strA/B-sul2*) was found in four different STs isolates. This region was found in isolates from all four batches on two IncQ plasmids, one IncF plasmid (F18:A-:B1) and on the chromosome (Table 4.40).

Table 4.40. *E. coli* isolates in which the MR6 region (*strA/B-sul2*) was detected.

Genomic localisation	SLST-Philogroup	Batch/sampling-date
Plasmid IncQ1	B1-ST162	L1/M1-03/2016
IncF plasmid (F18:A-:B1)	B1-ST162	L2/M2-06/2016
Chromosome	D-ST4243	L3/M3-01/2017
Chromosome	C-ST88	L4/M1-03/2017
Plasmid IncQ1	B1-ST58	L4/M4-08/2017

The environment of the MR6 region could not be known because, in all isolates, the resistance genes included in the region were found alone in a small contig (2.5 Kpb).

The MR7 region (*bla_{TEM-1B}-tetA-sul2- strA/B*) was detected on an IncQ1 plasmid in three isolates from different TS, none clonal. This region was observed for five months on farm (Table 4.41).

Table 4.41. *E. coli* isolates in which the MR7 region (*bla_{TEM-1B}-tetA-sul2-sul2- strA/B*) was detected in an IncQ1 plasmid

SLST-Philogroup	Batch/sampling-date
D-ST13021	L1/M8-10/2017
A-ST48	L2/M7-09/2017
A-ST10	L4/M6-03/2018

In this region, the *tnpR* resolvase of the *Tn3* transposon was detected at the 3' end of the *bla_{TEM-1B}* gene and an IS26 transposase at the 3' end of the *tetA* gene (Figure 4.51).

Figure 4.51. Genetic environment of the MR7 region.

The MR8 region (*sul1-tetA*) was identified on the chromosome of two isolates. One of them (day-old chicks from batch 4) corresponding to clone 30 (B1-ST155) and the other (laying hens from batch 1) ST1629. The *TnAs1* transposase was found at the 5' end of the *tetA* gene and the IS66 insertion sequence was found at the 5' end of the *sul1* gene (Figure 4.52).

Figure 4.52. Genetic environment of the MR8 region

The MR9 region (*blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2*) was detected on an IncF plasmid (F24:A-:B1) in two isolates of clone 33 (B1-ST155) from laying hens and batch 3 and 4 eggs, respectively.

The *Tn2* transposase and the *tnpR* gene, elements of the *Tn3* transposon, were found at the 5' end of the *blaTEM-1B* gene, and the *TnAs1* transposase of the *Tn3* transposon was detected between the *tetA* and *sul2* genes (Figure 4.53).

Figure 4.53. Genetic environment of the MR9 region

The MR10 region (*sul2-dfrA36-floR*) was identified only on the chromosome of clone 15 isolates. The ISShes11 transposase, belonging to the *Tn3* transposon family, and IS6, encoding the IS26 transposase, were identified at the 3' end of the *floR* gene (Figure 4.54).

Figure 4.54. Genetic environment of the MR10 region

The MR11 region (*catA1-tetA-sul2*) was identified on the chromosome of a laying hen isolate from batch 4, which was part of clone 3 (A-ST48). A *Tn2* transposase was detected at the 5' end of the *catA1* gene and a *TnAs1* transposase, both from the *Tn3* transposon, at the 3' end (Figure 4.55).

Figure 4.55. Genetic environment of the MR11 region

The MR12 region (*blaTEM-1B-strA/B-tetA*) was identified in an IncF plasmid (not typed) in a B1-ST1308 isolate from laying hens of the first batch. Two *Tn3* transposon elements (*Tn2* and *tnpR*) were identified at the 5' end of the region; in addition, an insertion sequence (IS3) encoding the IS1133 transposase and the *TnAs1* transposase (*Tn3* family) were found between the *strA/B* and *tetA* genes (Figure 4.56).

Figure 4.56. Genetic environment of the MR12 region

The MR13 region (*sul2-strA/B-blaTEM-1B*) was identified in an IncF24:A-:B1 plasmid from a laying hen isolate of the third batch (B1-ST101). Two insertion sequences (ISPa38 and IS110) were found at the 5' end of the *sul2* gene, while the *tnpR* gene (*Tn3*) and the *Tn2* transposon were identified at the 3' end of the *blaTEM-1B* gene (Figure 4.57).

Figure 4.57. Genetic environment of the MR13 region

Finally, the MR14 region (*qnrS1-blaTEM-1B-tetA-strA/B*) was found in an isolate of clone 10 (Clade I-ST770) from laying hens from the second batch. In the IncN plasmid, the same structure as described

above was found in the MR3 region (blaTEM-1B-tnpR-Tn2-IS3-qnrS1-ISKr). In addition, a TnAs1 transposase was detected in this region at the 3' end of the *tetA* gene (Figure 4.58).

Figure 4.58. Genetic environment of the MR14 region

The MR15 (*sul2-tetA*) region was detected in ten isolates on an IncI1/ST3 plasmid. The isolates in which the region was detected were the same as those in which the IncI1/ST3 plasmid was identified (Table 4.15) (Results section 6.4.1.2).

At the 3' end of the *sul2* gene, the insertion sequences IS110 and, in the case of isolates not corresponding to clone 3, an IS30 and IS6. At the 3' end of the *tetA* gene, the transposase TnAs1 and the insertion sequence IS91 were detected (Figure 4.47).

Figure 4.47. Comparison of the genetic environments of the MR15 region in the different isolates in which it was detected.

DISCUSSION

The main objective of this thesis is to expand the knowledge of resistance gene transmission in egg

production, which has been scarcely studied in commercial *E. coli* populations, and to determine to what extent this animal production poses a risk to public health through contamination of food or the environment.

CHAPTER 1. Antibiotic resistance in laying hens

Monitoring of antibiotic resistance levels in *E. coli* indicator in laying hens is not mandatory in the European Union, so there is no harmonised data, as is the case for chickens, turkeys, pigs and calves under one year of age. In the EU, this surveillance in laying hens only includes data on antibiotic resistance in *Salmonella spp.* and resistance levels in this animal species are generally lower than in other poultry production species such as turkeys and broilers (EFSA and ECDC 2022).

Antibiotic resistance studies in *E. coli* from laying hens are scarce (Table A.1) compared to other animal species. We found 15 publications that include phenotypic data on antibiotic resistance of *E. coli* isolates from laying hens sampled on farms in different countries. Eight focus on healthy animals (Schwaiger *et al.*, 2008; Harisberger *et al.*; 2011; van Hoorebeke *et al.*, 2011; Oosterik *et al.*, 2014; Pehlivanoglu, 2017; Rivera-Gomis *et al.*; 2021a; Rivera-Gomis (a and b) *et al.*; 2021b; and Pais *et al.*, 2023), and five in diseased animals, (Lanz *et al.*, 2003; Cavicchio *et al.*, 2015; Li *et al.*, 2019; Zajac *et al.*, 2019; Gambi *et al.*, 2022 and Hess *et al.*, 2022). Of these, only seven were published prior to the start of the research project in which this PhD thesis is framed in 2016.

The percentage of multi-resistant isolates varied among these studies, with percentages of 20% (Harisberger *et al.*, 2011; van Hoorebeke *et al.*, 2011), 45% (Pais *et al.*, 2023) and 95.7% (Hess *et al.*, 2022); with sulfonamides and ampicillin being the antibiotics for which most resistant isolates are observed. Furthermore, in studies involving other animals, both production (chickens, broiler turkeys, pigs and cows) and domestic (dogs and cats) (Lanz *et al.*, 2003; Cavicchio *et al.*, 2010; Zajac *et al.*, 2019), the levels of multi-resistance in laying hens are lower than in other animal species. However, laying hens are the second most resistant animals in the study by Li *et al.* (2019), above cattle and wildlife, and only below pigs.

Although antibiotic resistance levels are lower in *E. coli* in laying hens than in other production animal species, high rates of resistance to some antibiotics make it necessary to monitor antibiotic resistance in laying hens.

The only longitudinal studies of phenotypic antibiotic resistance in *E. coli* from laying hens were conducted in Japan (Koyama *et al.*, 2020) and Austria (Hess *et al.*, 2022). Koyama *et al.* (2020) studied environmental samples in a farm of healthy laying hens, detecting the highest percentage of multidrug-resistant *E. coli* isolates (31.6%) in the 0-4 month old pullet houses. Hess *et al.* (2022) analysed *E. coli* isolates from diseased hens on 18 layer farms in Austria, detecting 95% of multi-resistant isolates. In both

studies, they observed a higher percentage of multi-resistance than that observed in this thesis in isolates from non-selective culture medium.

It should be noted that, in this thesis, the percentages of isolates resistant to cefotaxime/ ceftazidime differ significantly depending on the culture medium (0.7% CTX and 1% TAZ in medium without antibiotic and 88.3% CTX, 86.1% TAZ in medium supplemented with CTX), so we consider that isolates resistant to these antibiotics are not predominant on this farm. These results differ from those presented by Apostolakos *et al.* (2020), as in their study there was neither a bias towards certain ESBL-ampC genotypes in selective medium compared to non-selective isolation, nor an underestimation of them by the non-selective method compared to the selective isolation. Pehlivanoglu *et al.* (2017) used selective medium (CTX 2 µg/mL or TAZ 2 µg/mL) for isolation of *E. coli*, and observed 100% resistant isolates to 7 of the 11 beta-lactams against which resistance levels were studied. Pais *et al.* (2014), who isolated *E. coli* on ampicillin medium, observed that more than 80% of isolates were resistant to ampicillin and more than half were resistant to ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid. In this thesis, 43.8% of the isolates on CTX medium were resistant to nalidixic acid, and 51.1% to ciprofloxacin.

Studies of resistance levels in *E. coli* isolated from on-farm eggs are even scarcer. Schwaiger *et al.* (2008) studied resistance levels in both shell and contents of eggs collected from organic and conventional farms in Germany and found no resistant isolates from eggs, whereas in this thesis, we identified 20% of multi-resistant isolates from eggs when using isolation media without antibiotics.

Rasheed *et al.* (2014) and Grande *et al.* (2016) studied resistance levels in *E. coli* from eggshells that were collected from shops in India and Spain, respectively. Rasheed *et al.* (2014) identify 60% of multidrug-resistant isolates, while Grande *et al.* (2016) detect almost 30% of multidrug-resistant isolates.

CHAPTER 2. Diversity of *E. coli* in faecal populations

The number of isolates per sample to be studied to estimate the diversity of *E. coli* in the gut microbiota of laying hens depends on the research objectives (Moreno *et al.*, 2019). This number has been analysed in some studies.

Lidin-Janson *et al.* (1978) concluded that the probability of detecting the predominant genotypes in an *E. coli* population increases from 86% (testing one colony) to 99% (testing five colonies). Schlager *et al.* (2002), studying the diversity of *E. coli* in stool and urinary tract samples from young women, found that analysis of 28 colonies was sufficient to detect up to 90% of non-predominant genotypes.

Stoesser *et al.* (2015) studied beta-lactamase-producing *E. coli* populations in faecal samples, noting that analysis of 16 colonies per sample recovered four distinct ST profiles per individual. Li *et al.* (2019) individually analysed broiler chicken faecal samples, identifying three to nine different ST profiles per individual by collecting more than 100 colonies. In some of the samples in this thesis where 10 colonies

were collected, up to nine distinct ST profiles were identified, although individual samples were not analysed in this thesis.

Blaak *et al.* (2015) studied diversity in 1,140 ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolates from faeces, wastewater and environment (soil, air, dust, flies, leaks and faeces of other animals) from layer farms, choosing three different combinations of traits: Phylogenetic group/ESBL genotypic profile, ST/Phylogenetic group/ESBL genotypic profile/Antibiotic resistance profile and ESBL genotypic profile/Antibiotic resistance profile. Choosing the first combination, they obtained a Simpson's index of 0.51 in isolates from faeces and wastewater and 0.60 from the environment; with the second combination they obtained values of 0.63 and 0.77 and, with the third combination, 0.37 and 0.56.

In this thesis, the diversity of *E. coli*, both phenotypic resistance profiles and ST profiles, was studied using the same Simpson's index (D), whose values vary between 0 and 1 (Hunter *et al.*, 1988). Since the values of this index were higher than 0.6 with both types of data, the number of isolates collected in this study (8-10) was sufficient to cover the diversity of *E. coli*.

It should be noted that a higher genetic diversity has been identified in the laying hen samples than in the pullet samples. Although phenotypic diversity is higher in the first sampling, genetic diversity increases in subsequent samplings. The increase in interspecies diversity in the gut microbiota of hens increases with the age of the hens (Videnska *et al.*, 2014) as more species represented in the microbiota could lead to genetic exchange between different bacterial populations, with *E. coli* populations acquiring resistance genes that are, in principle, less common in this bacterial species, which explains the higher genetic, rather than phenotypic, diversity in samples of laying hens. Gupta *et al.* (2021) carried out a longitudinal study of the microbiome of laying hens and described a stabilisation of the hen gut microbiome over time.

CHAPTER 3. Antibiotic resistance genes described in *E. coli* from laying hens

When the research project in which this thesis is framed was started in 2016, 24 antibiotic resistance genes had been described in *E. coli* from laying hens (*bla*_{CMY-2}, *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-2}, *bla*_{SHV-12}, *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *bla*_{TEM-52}, *strA*, *strB*, *tetA*, *tetB*, *tetC*, *sul1*, *sul2*, *cat*, *aadA1*, *aadA2*, *aadA5*, *aadA13*, *dfrA1*, *dfrA12*, *dfrA17*, *dfrVII*, *sat2* and *estX*) had been described (Table A.2). Of these 24 genes, seven (*bla*_{TEM-52}, *tetC*, *aadA13*, *dfrA12*, *dfrVII*, *sat2* and *estX*) have not been identified in this thesis.

Five of the 32 antibiotic resistance genes identified in this thesis (*dfrA36*, *mphA*, *aac(3)-IId*, *sat1* and *aph(3)-Ia*) have not been previously described in *E. coli* isolates from laying hens. Moreover, this is the first study of genotypic data of resistance in *E. coli* from laying hens in Spain, so this is the first description of the 32 genes identified in *E. coli* from this avian species in our country.

There are few resistance gene studies in *E. coli* from laying hens that are generalist, as most are focused on clinically important antibiotics such as beta-lactams (Wasyl *et al.*, 2012; Chauvin *et al.*, 2013; Blaak *et al.*, 2015; Pehlivanoglu, 2017; Shim, 2019; Ceccarelli, 2019; Baez *et al.*, 2021; Yang *et al.*, 2022; Wei *et*

al., 2022; Liao *et al.*, 2022; Pais *et al.*, 2023), fluoroquinolones (Li *et al.*, 2019; Koyama *et al.*, 2020), colistin (Irrgang *et al.*, 2016; Zajac *et al.*, 2019) or more than one particular antibiotic (Niero *et al.*, 2018; Seo *et al.*, 2018; Jochum *et al.*, 2021) (Table A.2).

Four of the genotypic studies of resistance in *E. coli* are generalist in that they do not focus on specific antibiotic groups (Table A.2): in the first one, Lanz *et al.* (2003) identified eight genes (*sul1*, *sul2*, *strA*, *strB*, *aadA*, *tetA*, *tetB* and *tetC*) by hybridisation and PCR in septicaemic laying hens in Switzerland; Videnska *et al.* (2014) found seven genes (*strA/B*, *sul1*, *sul2*, *tetA*, *tetB* and *cat*) in faeces of healthy laying hens in Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovenia by PCR; Cavicchio *et al.* (2015), also by PCR, identified 10 genes [*aadA*(1, 2, 5, 13), *dfrA*(1, 12, 17), *dfrVII*, *sat2* and *estX*] in APEC isolates from hens with colibacillosis in Italy; and Zhu *et al.* (2021) found 12 genes (*tetA*, *emrB*, *emrC*, *bla_{TEM}*, *sul2*, *strB*, *sul1*, *tetM*, *tetX*, *tetQ*, *oqxB* and *qnrS*) in manure and soil samples from nine healthy laying hen farms in China, also with PCR. In this thesis, 14 of the above genes (*sul1*, *sul2*, *strA*, *strB*, *tetA*, *tetB*, *aadA* (1, 2, 5), *dfrA1*, *dfrA* (1, 12), *bla_{TEM}* and *qnr*) have been identified.

Beta-lactam resistance genes

As a cefotaxime-supplemented culture medium was added in this study, the number and variety of beta-lactam resistance genes was high. In fact, 87% of the ESBL and *ampC* genes and all *bla_{TEM-1D}* genes we detected were identified in isolates obtained with this selective medium.

Seven different beta-lactam antibiotic resistance genes were found in this study. As mentioned above, there are numerous studies in *E. coli* from laying hens that focus on beta-lactam resistance genes and use a selective medium to obtain isolates.

The most commonly detected genes in laying hen samples are those identified in this thesis: *bla_{TEM}*, *bla_{CTX-M}*, *bla_{CMY}*, *bla_{SHV}* and *bla_{OXA}* (Table A.2).

In manure from laying hens, chickens, pigs, and beef and dairy farms on farms in China (Yang *et al.*, 2022), 100% of *E. coli* isolates were found to carry a *bla_{geneTEM-1}*, and also in China (Zhu *et al.*, 2021) observed, in a laying hen farm, that in 100% of chicken manure samples, regardless of growth stage, *E. coli* isolates with a *bla_{geneTEM}* were identified. Therefore, it is common to identify *bla_{geneTEM}* in poultry, including laying hens.

The *bla_{TEM-1D}* gene is not frequently identified. It was first described in amoxicillin-clavulanic acid-resistant *E. coli* isolates from hospital patients in France in 2000 (Leflon-Guibout *et al.*, 2000). There are no resistance studies in bacteria isolated from animals describing the presence of this gene; however, there are studies reporting its presence, albeit at a very low frequency in both *E. coli* and other bacterial species such as *Acinetobacter baumannii* (Van Hout *et al.*, 2020; Al-Hassan *et al.*, 2021), in samples from

hospitalised individuals.

Of the two *bla*_{TEM-1} genes identified, *bla*_{TEM-1B} was the most frequent. In Spain, there are no descriptions in *E. coli* from laying hens, but *bla* *gene*_{STEM} were found in 100% of *E. coli* isolates from chicken hindquarters and livers purchased in a supermarket (García-Béjar *et al.*, 2021). In other countries, they have been described in laying hens, such as in breeding hen farms in Korea (Kim *et al.*, 2021), where the presence of *E. coli* isolates carrying the *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene was described.

The *bla* *gene*_{OXA-1} was identified in this thesis in two clonal isolates (day-old and growing chicks). In laying hens, *bla*_{OXA} genes have been described in China (Li *et al.*, 2019; Yang *et al.*, 2022; Wei *et al.*, 2022 and Liao *et al.*, 2022) and in the United States (Jochum *et al.*, 2021). This gene has also been detected in *E. coli* isolates in studies carried out in healthy broilers in Tunisia (Soufi *et al.*, 2009) and Egypt (Saad *et al.*, 2019), and in chickens with septicemia in China (Li *et al.*, 2015).

The *bla* *gene*_{OXA-1} has been observed in isolates of carbapenemase-producing bacteria from hospitalised people in Romania (frequency 65%) (Maciuca *et al.*, 2015), in *E. coli* isolates from healthy people in Seville, Spain (Torres *et al.*, 2015) or in ESBL-producing bacteria isolated from bacteraemia patients in a UK hospital (Livermore *et al.*, 2018), so this gene appears to be more frequent in isolates from humans than in isolates from broilers or laying hens, regardless of their health status.

This gene has also been detected in other animals such as dogs in Turkey (Aslantas and Yilmaz, 2017), fish in Tunisia (Hassen *et al.*, 2020), pigs in China (Yuan *et al.*, 2020) or seals in Ireland (Vale *et al.*, 2021).

The *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene was first described in multidrug-resistant isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from hospitalised individuals in 1987 by Sirot *et al.*, who also transferred this gene to *E. coli* by conjugation, demonstrating that this gene had the ability to spread to other bacterial species. Ramos *et al.* (2020) described the most frequent ESBL-encoding genes in the world, with *bla*_{CTX-M-1} being the most frequent in European countries, India and Tunisia, and *bla*_{CTX-M-14} being the most frequent in the United States and China. In particular, the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene is the most frequent cephalosporin resistance gene in Europe in broiler isolates (Ramos *et al.*, 2020). *bla*_{CTX-M-1} is a very frequent gene in studies carried out in poultry with cephalosporin-resistant isolates (Rahman *et al.*, 2020). Effendi *et al.*, 2021 observed in a study in broiler chickens that almost 98% of the cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* isolates carried a *bla*_{CTX-M-1}.

In laying hens, the presence of this gene was first described in healthy hens in Poland (Wasył *et al.*, 2012). It has subsequently been described in other countries such as France (Chauvin *et al.*, 2013), the Netherlands (Blaak *et al.*, 2015; Ceccarelli *et al.*, 2019), Italy (Niero *et al.*, 2018) or Cuba (Baez *et al.*, 2021). In broiler chickens, Effendi *et al.* (2021) observed that almost 98% of cephalosporin-resistant *E.*

coli isolates carried a *bla* gene_{CTX-M}. In this thesis, the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene was mainly responsible for cephalosporin resistance, being found in more than 30% of isolates resistant to cefotaxime and/or ceftazidime.

The *bla*_{CTX-M-14} gene was first described in 2001 in Korea in *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and *Shigella sonnei* in isolates from hospitalised children (Pai *et al.*, 2001). In *E. coli* from laying hens, it has been identified in healthy hens in Korea (Seo *et al.*, 2018; Shim *et al.*, 2018) and the Netherlands (Ceccarelli, 2019).

Both *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-14} genes have been detected in Spain in isolates from healthy chickens (Abreu *et al.*, 2014) and with colibacillosis (Solà-Ginés *et al.*, 2015).

The *bla* gene_{CMY-2} was first described in 1990 in *K. pneumoniae* by Bauernfeind *et al.* (1990) and was later shown to be transferable to *E. coli* (Bauernfeind *et al.*, 1996). In *E. coli* from layers, it was first identified by Wasyl *et al.* (2012) and has been detected in laying hens in Italy (Niero *et al.*, 2018), Korea (Seo *et al.*, 2018; Shim *et al.*, 2019), the Netherlands (Ceccarelli *et al.*, 2019) and the United States (Jochum *et al.*, 2021). In Spain, this gene has been identified in *E. coli* from diseased laying hens (Solà-Ginés *et al.*, 2015).

The *bla*_{SHV-12} gene has been identified in *E. coli* from laying hens in Poland (Wasyl *et al.*, 2012) and the Netherlands (Blaak *et al.*, 2015). In Spain, this gene has been detected in *E. coli* isolates from healthy chickens as well as chicken meat, and also in isolates from dogs and humans (Alonso *et al.*, 2017) and in broilers with colibacillosis (Solà-Ginés *et al.*, 2015). In other countries, it has been detected in *E. coli* isolates from broilers in Indonesia (Effendi *et al.*, 2021) or Tunisia (Hassen *et al.*, 2020). The *bla*_{SHV-12} gene has been described as the most frequent gene in beta-lactamase-producing Enterobacteriaceae from retail chicken and poultry meat in Germany and Spain (Alonso *et al.*, 2017).

In addition, other genes that we have not identified in this thesis have been described in several articles in laying hens, such as *bla*_{DHA} (Pehlivanoglu *et al.*, 2017; Li *et al.*, 2019; Yang *et al.*, 2022 and Wei *et al.*, 2022), *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (Shim *et al.*, 2019; Ceccarelli *et al.*, 2019 and Baez *et al.*, 2021), *bla*_{VIM} (Jochum *et al.*, 2021 and Yang *et al.*, 2022) or *bla*_{KPC} (Jochum *et al.*, 2021 and Yang *et al.*, 2022).

It should be noted that three of these genes (*bla*_{SHV-12}, *bla*_{CTX-M-14} and *bla*_{CMY-2}) were detected for the first time in 2003 in *E. coli* from broiler chickens (Briñas *et al.*, 2003), within the Spanish Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Programme (Moreno *et al.*, 2000).

The chromosomal gene *ampC* produces a class C cephalosporinase. This gene in *E. coli* has a weak promoter; however, some isolates overproduce this enzyme due to mutations that create a stronger promoter (Caroff *et al.*, 1998). In the isolates of this thesis, three types of mutations were identified in the *ampC* gene in CTX-resistant isolates (positions -1, -18 and +24). The isolates in which these mutations were identified also carried CTX resistance genes. This coexistence of resistance genes and point

mutations conferring resistance to the same group of antimicrobials has been observed to increase resistance levels (Tracz *et al.*, 2007). The isolates in this thesis that have a mutation in the *ampC* gene and carry a CTX resistance gene all have MIC values greater than 8 mg/L against cefotaxime, whereas 30% of the isolates that only carry a CTX resistance gene have MIC < 8 mg/L. In addition, all isolates with MICs of 4 and 2 mg/L have only a resistance gene.

Quinolone resistance genes

The two quinolone resistance genes found in this thesis (*qnrS1* and *qnrB19*) were mostly identified in isolates selected in antibiotic-supplemented culture medium (33.3% medium with CTX and 33.3% with CIP medium), so their frequency is over-represented.

However, the majority of isolates (92.9%) resistant to fluoroquinolones showed point mutations in genes encoding gyrase (*gyrA* or *gyrB*) and/or topoisomerase (*parE* or *parC*) subunits, which are the main cause of resistance to these antibiotics in *E. coli* (Aldred *et al.*, 2014). Mutations in the *gyrB* and *parE* subunits are considerably less frequent than those in *gyrA* and *parC* (Correia *et al.*, 2017), as we have observed in this thesis.

Different variants of the *qnrS* and *qnrB* genes have been identified in *E. coli* from laying hens in Korea (Seo *et al.*, 2018), Italy (Niero *et al.*, 2018), China (Li *et al.*, 2019; Zhu *et al.*, 2021; Wei *et al.*, 2022; Liao *et al.*, 2022) and Japan (Koyama *et al.*, 2020). Both genes have been detected in broilers in Spain (Martínez-Álvarez *et al.*, 2022) and in other countries: Netherlands (Veldman *et al.*, 2012), Czech Republic (Hricová *et al.*, 2017), Poland (Zajac *et al.*, 2019) or Japan (Belotindos *et al.*, 2022).

Trimethoprim and sulfonamide resistance genes

Sulphonamides and trimethoprim are antibiotics that inhibit folate synthesis and have been used for many decades as antibacterial agents in humans and animals, and resistance to both has become widespread (Skold, 2000). To date, three sulphamide resistance genes (*sul1*, *sul2* and *sul3*) and 40 different types of *dfr* (trimethoprim resistance) genes have been described in gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria (Wüthrich *et al.*, 2019). The *dfr* genes described in *E. coli* are classified into *dfrA* and *dfrB* (less frequent) and most of these found in *E. coli* of animal origin are located in class 1 or class 2 integron cassettes (Poirel *et al.*, 2018).

In this thesis, five *dfrA* genes responsible for TMP resistance have been identified: *dfrA1*, *dfrA5*, *dfrA14*, *dfrA36* and *dfrA17*, with *dfrA1* being the most frequent. Caviccio *et al.* (2015) identified *dfrA1* in an *E. coli* isolate from laying hens in Italy, while in chickens and turkeys included in the same study, they found the *dfrA1*, *dfrA12* and *dfrA17* genes. Shim *et al.* (2019), in *E. coli* from chickens, detected *dfrA14* and *dfrA17*. Racewicz *et al.* (2022) identified *dfrA1*, *dfrA5* and *dfrA17* genes in *E. coli* isolates from broiler

chickens in Poland. It should be noted that we have not found any publications indicating the presence of the *dfrA17* gene in *E. coli* from laying hens.

The *dfrA36* gene has been described for the first time in this thesis in *E. coli* isolates from birds. This gene was first described in the bacterial chromosome of an *E. coli* isolate from healthy calf faeces in Switzerland (Wüthrich *et al.*, 2019), conferring resistance to trimethoprim (MIC \geq 128 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). In addition, this gene was also identified by sequence analysis published in *GenBank* (Wüthrich *et al.*, 2019) in the chromosome of 26 other *E. coli* isolates, in one *Acinetobacter sp.* and in several gammaproteobacteria isolated from different countries (Switzerland, Czech Republic, Germany, Israel, Netherlands, Egypt and USA) and from different origins, mainly cattle and humans, but also dogs and horses. The first *E. coli* sequence (isolated from humans in the gastroenterology unit of a US hospital) in which *dfrA36* was identified was submitted to *GenBank* in June 2013 (GenBank accession no.: ADTK01000026) by Weinstock *et al* [unpublished].

In this thesis, the *dfrA36* gene was identified on the chromosome of the two isolates of clone 15 from day-old and growing chicks sampled in 2016, the first time this gene has been detected both in poultry isolates and in Spain.

Prior to the publication of the gene sequence in *GenBank* (August 2019), the *ResFinder 2.1 software* did not detect any TMP resistance gene in these isolates, which phenotypically showed resistance (MIC $>$ 32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Once the gene was published, we detected a 587-bp fragment that had 100% identity and coverage with the TMP resistance gene *dfrA36* (*GenBank* accession no. CP038791).

The genetic environment of *dfrA36* in this thesis was virtually identical to that described by Wüthrich *et al.* (2019) (Figure 5.1). In addition, both had a class 1 integron at the 3' end of the *floR* gene that includes the sequence *aadA1-qacE Δ 1-sul1*. In the case of the isolate of this thesis, the complete sequence of the integron was *IntI1-bla_{OXA-1}-aadA1-qacE Δ 1-sul1*, while in the isolate published by Wüthrich *et al.* (2019), it was *IntI1-aadB-aadA1-qacE Δ 1-sul1* (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1. Comparison of the genome fragments in which the *dfrA36* gene has been identified in the publication of Wuthrich *et al.*, 2019 (top) and in clone 15 of this thesis (bottom). [Scheme made with EasyFig].

Lanz *et al.* (2003) identified *sul1* and *sul2* genes in *E. coli* isolates from layers with septicaemia in Switzerland, and Videnska *et al.* (2006) detected both genes in *E. coli* from laying hens in a study carried out in different countries (Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovenia). In Bangladesh, Rahman *et al.* (2020) identified all three genes in chicken meat isolates. In Spain, these genes have been identified in *E. coli* isolates from broiler chickens (Marchant *et al.*, 2013), as well as in Germany (Guerra *et al.*, 2003), Korea (Dessie *et al.*, 2013), Tunisia (Soufi *et al.*, 2011), Nepal (Joshi *et al.*, 2019), or Canada (Yang *et al.*, 2021a) and, in goshawks and eagles from Slovakia (Handrova *et al.*, 2019). As we have seen in this thesis, Soufi *et al.* (2011) found that the most frequent sulphonamide resistance gene was *sul2*, followed by *sul1* and, less frequently, *sul3*. In laying hens in Spain, these three genes have also been identified in *Salmonella* isolates (Riaño *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, these *sul* genes are frequently found in *E. coli* isolated from laying hens and other poultry, both productive and wild.

[Aminoglycoside resistance genes](#)

Three *aadA* genes conferring resistance to streptomycin-spectinomycin (*aadA1*, *aadA2* and *aadA5*) were found, the first time *aadA5* has been detected in *E. coli* isolates from laying hens. Lanz *et al.* (2003) identified *aadA* in *E. coli* isolates from layers with septicaemia in Switzerland, although they did not

specify which variant. The *aadA1* gene has also been previously detected in isolates from laying hens in Italy (Cavicchio *et al.*, 2015), in a study including isolates from other production birds (turkeys and broilers) in which they detected four other *aadA* genes that were not observed in the hen isolates (*aadA2*, *aadA5*, *aadA13* and *aadA17*).

In other studies in broiler chickens, *aadA* genes (especially *aadA1*) were identified in *E. coli* isolates in China (Liu *et al.*, 2021), Poland (Błazejewska *et al.*, 2022) and the United States (Iwinski *et al.*, 2022).

Two other frequently identified streptomycin-spectinomycin resistance genes are *strA* and *strB*. In this thesis they are referred to as *strA/B* as they were detected together in all isolates.

Lanz *et al.* (2003) identified *strA/B* in *E. coli* isolates from sick hens, as did Wei *et al.* (2022), who studied cloacal swab isolates from laying hens in China. However, they are not always identified together. The *strA* gene was the most frequent gene in a study analysing isolates from laying hens in Europe (Videnska *et al.*, 2014), but they do not report the presence of *strB*.

Another aminoglycoside resistance gene detected was *aph(3')-Ia* (n=2), which is described for the first time in *E. coli* isolates from laying hens in this thesis. This gene has been found in *E. coli* isolates from various sources: chicken meat in Tunisia (Soufi *et al.*, 2009), chickens with colibacillosis in Italy (Cavicchio *et al.*, 2015) and water, workers and faeces from broiler chickens on a farm (Aworh *et al.*, 2021).

The genes *aac(3)-Vla* (n=2), and *aac(3)-IId* (n=1) were also identified. For one of these genes (*aac(3)-IId*), this thesis is the first description in *E. coli* isolates from laying hens, although it has been previously identified in other avian species: *aac(3)-IId* was found in *E. coli* isolates from broiler chickens with colibacillosis in Korea (Kim *et al.*, 2020; Yoon *et al.*, 2020). *Aac(3)-II* genes have also been detected in *E. coli* from broilers in Tunisia (Soufi *et al.*, 2011), Morocco (Nayme *et al.*, 2019) or Poland (Racewicz *et al.*, 2022), being this gene frequent in this species of production poultry. It should be noted that in Spain the presence of *aac(3)-II* genes has also been observed in environmental samples from broiler farms (Martínez-Álvarez *et al.*, 2022).

The *satI* gene, which confers resistance to streptothricin, has been observed in this thesis for the first time in *E. coli* from laying hens. This gene has previously been identified in *E. coli* isolates from broiler chickens and, as observed in this thesis, as part of class 2 integrons, in France (Soufi *et al.*, 2009), China (Rehman *et al.*, 2008) and Korea (Dessie *et al.*, 2013).

Tetracycline resistance genes

The *tetA* and *tetB* genes are the most frequent tetracycline resistance genes in *E. coli* of animal origin (Poirel *et al.*, 2018) and both have been identified in the isolates from the farm analysed, with *tetA* being

the most frequent. These genes have been described in *E. coli* in laying hens in Switzerland (Lanz *et al.*, 2003), Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.*, 2020) and Croatia, Slovenia, Czech Republic and Hungary (Videnska *et al.*, 2014). Videnska *et al.* (2014) observed that the *tetB* gene is characteristic of the microbiota of laying hens in Slovenia, although it is found less frequently in broiler isolates; Lanz *et al.* (2003), detected twice as many isolates with *tetA* as with *tetB* in *E. coli* from laying hens. In laying hens and broilers in Egypt, the *tetA* gene was identified in more than 50% of the *Salmonella* isolates studied (Elez *et al.*, 2021). In laying hens in Spain, the *tetA* gene has only been identified in *Salmonella* isolates (Riaño *et al.*, 2006).

E. coli in broiler chickens have been detected in Spain (García-Béjar *et al.*, 2021), and in other countries such as Poland (Ćwiek *et al.*, 2021).

Phenolic resistance genes

Phenolic resistance genes in *E. coli* are *cat*, *floR*, *cmlA* and *cfr* (Poirel *et al.*, 2018), of which three (*cmlA1*, *catA1* and *floR*) have been detected in this thesis. In *E. coli* from laying hens, *cat* genes have been detected in faeces from healthy hens in Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovenia (Videnska *et al.*, 2014) and in cloacal swabs from hens in China (Wei *et al.*, 2022); and *cmlA* and *floR* genes in China (Wei *et al.*, 2022; Liao *et al.*, 2022). In meat from laying hens from poultry shops in Bangladesh, the *floR* gene has been detected in cloacal swabs and eggs in China (Wei *et al.*, 2020; Liao *et al.*, 2022) and, the *cmlA1* gene has been identified in cloacal swabs in China (Wei *et al.*, 2020) and in meat for consumption in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.*, 2020) and, the *catA1* gene in meat for consumption in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.*, 2020).

All three genes have been described in broiler chickens in Spain (Alonso *et al.*, 2017; Martínez-Álvarez *et al.*, 2022). Notably, the *cmlA1* and *catA1* genes have recently been detected in *Salmonella* kentucky isolates from laying hens in Spain (Samper-Cativiela *et al.*, 2022).

Macrolide resistance genes

The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) has not defined resistance cut-off points for macrolides in Enterobacteriaceae, but reports that isolates with MICs to azithromycin greater than 16 µg/mL are likely to have resistance mechanisms (EUCAST, 2023). In this thesis, the two isolates in which the *mphA* gene was detected had MIC values greater than 32 µg/mL, while 13 other isolates had an MIC to azithromycin of 32 µg/mL and were considered phenotypically resistant to azithromycin; however, no macrolide resistance genes were detected in these isolates.

Gomes *et al.* (2019), studying macrolide resistance genes in *E. coli*, found that 93% of isolates with MICs above 32 µg/mL had *mphA*, while almost 90% of isolates with MICs below 32 µg/mL had no genes or mutations conferring resistance to this antibiotic, so the use of 32 µg/mL as a cut-off point seems appropriate for suspecting the presence of *mphA*.

We have not found descriptions of the *mphA* gene in *E. coli* from laying hens; however, this gene was detected in isolates from soil samples from a broiler farm in the United States (Hailu *et al.*, 2021) and in cloacal isolates from broiler chickens in China and Sudan (Abdelgader *et al.*, 2018).

Fosfomicin resistance genes

The fosfomicin resistance gene *fosA7* was first described in *S. enterica* Serovar Heidelberg isolates from broiler chickens in Canada (Rehman *et al.*, 2017). Also in Canada, the *fosA7* gene was identified in *E. coli* isolates from clinical samples from humans, which had been collected in 2007, 2008 and 2011 (Milner *et al.*, 2021). In *E. coli*, this gene was also detected in isolates from free-ranging poultry in Poland, which were sampled between 2017 and 2020 (Skarzyńska *et al.*, 2021). In laying hens, Liao *et al.* (2022) detected *fosA7* genes in China, although they do not specify which ones.

The *fosA7* gene has been identified in isolates from two day-old chicks with ST602 profile in this thesis, so the source of this gene in the egg production cycle studied in this thesis is external to the farm.

This gene has also been detected in broiler, pig and pigeon farms in China (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Zhang *et al.* (2022) carried out a phylogenetic analysis of the *fosA7* genes detected in *E. coli* isolates ST602 and ST2599, showing that these genes are closely related to those found in human isolates, potentially posing a threat to human health. The two isolates found in this thesis had an ST602 profile and their genetic environment was very similar to that of the isolates detected by Zang *et al.*, 2022 (*GenBank* accession no.: OM355479.1) (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.1. Comparison between the genetic environments of the *fosA7* gene in the sequenced ST602 isolates (bottom) and the ST602 isolates from the publication of Zhang *et al.*, 2022 (top). [EasyFig]

CHAPTER 4. Multi-resistance regions

Ten different genes were detected in RMs, with *tetA*, *blaTEM*_{1B}, *sul2* and *strA/B* being found in more regions, either in combination with each other or associated with other resistance genes. These associations

of *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA*, *strA/B* and *sul2* genes have already been described in other studies of *E. coli* isolated from rabbits (Rhouma *et al.*, 2020), with at least two of these genes found in virtually all multidrug-resistant isolates.

In multidrug-resistant isolates, resistance genes together with associated mobile elements can be found in associated multi-resistance regions, which are located on both plasmids and chromosomes (Partridge, 2011). The accumulation of resistance genes in these regions means that a bacterium may be able to rapidly acquire a combination of resistance genes en bloc (Walsh, 2006) and, the association of resistance genes in these regions allows co-selection for maintenance (O'Brien, 2002). Capture of these resistance genes in these regions is often mediated by insertion sequences and transposons (Partridge, 2011).

In particular, the *Tn3* transposon family is a widespread family and one of the earliest bacterial transposons identified (Shkumatov *et al.*, 2022). The first described integron of the *Tn3* family was *Tn5271* in 1995 (Nakatsu *et al.*, 1995). *Tn3* transposons can modify the structure of plasmids, transferring large fragments of chromosomal DNA to the plasmid (Szuplewska *et al.*, 2014).

In 13 of the 15 multi-resistance regions identified in this thesis, elements of the *Tn3* family have been identified. Bailey *et al.* (2011) associate the *bla*_{TEM} with *Tn2* transposons, which are the most frequently found in *E. coli*. They found that all *bla*_{TEM} genes were contained within a *TnA* transposon (of which *Tn2* is a variant) or a fragment thereof. It was also observed in the same study that IS26 insertion sequences, which are implicated in the formation of multi-antibiotic resistance regions, are associated with truncated *Tn2* transposons. In three of the regions identified in this thesis (MR2, MR7 and MR10), we also found IS26 adjacent to the resistance genes that form these regions. In addition, one of the regions (RM4) was identified in a *Tn801* transposon, which is closely related to *Tn3* (Chouchani *et al.*, 2007).

In the MR5 and MR13 regions, both identified on an IncF plasmid, elements of the *Tn3* transposon were identified. Both regions share a common fragment (*bla*_{TEM-1B}-*tetA*-*sul2*), however, in the MR5 region the *tetA* resistance gene is also identified (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2. Comparison of the genetic environments of the MR5 (top) and MR13 (bottom) regions. [EasyFig]

The same genes identified in the MR5 region appear, in a different order, in the MR7 region (*blaTEM-1B-tetA-sul2-strA/B*). This gene rearrangement may be due to the presence of an IS26 insertion sequence in the MR7 region. Wein *et al.* (2022) showed that, at low antibiotic concentration, the IS26 insertion sequence mediates the amplification of a multi-resistance region, accompanied by gene rearrangement.

Another example of gene rearrangements, in which the IS26 insertion sequence is also involved, has been observed in the MR15 and MR9 regions: in both we detected the *tetA* and *sul2* genes, although in a different order, and in addition, in the MR9 region, we found an insertion of the *blaTEM-1B* gene (Figure 5.3). The IS26 insertion sequence, in addition to mediating rearrangements, can cause adjacent deletions (Mollet *et al.*, 1985).

Figure 5.3. Comparison of the genetic environments of the MR15 (top) and MR9 (bottom) regions.

In some of the identified regions, we observed rearrangement, loss and gain of resistance genes as homologous recombination occurs between similar DNA fragments, resulting in inversions of DNA fragments, or exchanges of small DNA segments within those fragments (Partridge, 2011). These recombinations are also mediated by insertion sequences, ISCR or ISEcp1 elements, or transposons (Partridge, 2011; Szuplewska *et al.*, 2014; Reid *et al.*, 2015).

This ISEcp1 element is identified close to the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene in the MR2 region. This ISEcp1-*bla*_{CTX-M-1} structure is lost in the MR15 region identified, as in MR2, in an IncII/ST3 plasmid (Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4. Comparison of the genetic environments of the MR2 (top) and M15 (bottom) regions. [Easyfig]

Figure 5.5 shows the homology of four regions (MR7, MR1.2, MR14 and MR9), which carry at least two of the *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA*, *strA/B* and/or *sul2* genes. Among these regions we can also observe loss or gain of resistance genes and genetic rearrangements (Figure 5.5).

Figure 5.5. Genetic environment of the MR7 (top), MR1.2, MR14 and MR9 regions (bottom). [EasyFig]

CHAPTER 5. Integrons

The first study of integrons in *E. coli* from laying hens was carried out by Lanz *et al.* (2003) in diseased hens in Switzerland. Lanz *et al.* (2003) observed significant associations between the presence of *sul1* and *aadA1* genes and the presence of the *Int1* integrase gene. Oosterik *et al.* (2014) observed, in a study conducted in *E. coli* from chickens in Poland, that 21.6% of isolates contained a class 1 integron, although they did not detect class 2 or class 3 integrons; they also observed associations between the presence of the *Int1* gene and TMP-, SUL- and TET-resistant phenotypes. Caviccio *et al.* (2015) detected class 1 and class 2 integrons in diseased laying hens in Italy, with frequencies of 48.4% and 6.5%, respectively, with the most frequently observed resistance cassettes being *aadA2* in class 1 and *aadA1* integrons and the combination *dfrA1-sat2-aadA1* in class 2 integrons. Shim *et al.* (2019) detected class 1 integrons in 13% of the *E. coli* CTX^R isolates from laying hens studied.

Studies in broiler chickens in Iran (Kalantari *et al.*, 2021) and Poland (Racewicz *et al.*, 2022) have identified class 1 integrons in 72% and 60% of the isolates studied, respectively. Class 2 integrons were identified in both studies, although with a much lower frequency.

The most common cassettes associated with class 1 integrons in *E. coli* confer resistance to beta-lactams, aminoglycosides, trimethoprim and chloramphenicol, either together or separately (Hall *et al.*, 1993; Fluit *et al.*, 1999; Kaushik *et al.*, 2018). In this thesis, we found at least one trimethoprim or aminoglycoside resistance cassette in all the integrons identified.

Specifically, *aadA1* is the most frequently found in class 1 integrons identified in Enterobacteriaceae, followed by *aadA5* and *dfrA17* (Kaushik *et al.*, 2018). In this thesis, all *aadA* and *dfrA* resistance genes (except *dfrA36*) were always part of integrons, as well as 94% of *sul3* and 68% of *sul1* genes identified.

It is noteworthy that only three of the nine class 1 integrons (1.1: *dfrA1-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1*; 1.7: *bla_{OXA.1}-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1* and 1.8: *aadA1-aac(3)-Vla-qacEΔ1-sul1*) possessed the conserved 3' region typical of class 1 integrons consisting of the *qacEΔ1* gene truncated by *sul1* (Messier *et al.*, 2001). This typical structure was not identified in the other integrons, most of them consisting of only one resistance gene (1.2: *aadA2-cmlA1-aadA1-sul3*; 1.3: *dfrA14*; 1.4: *dfrA1*; 1.5: *dfrA5*; 1.6: *dfrA17-aadA5* and 1.9: *dfrA17*).

The resistance cassettes of class 2 integrons are not as diverse as those of class 1 integrons (Kadlec *et al.*, 2008). Resistance cassettes to aminoglycosides, trimethoprim or sulfonamides are found in these integrons (Ploy *et al.*, 2000), with the most common cassette combination in these integrons being the one detected in this thesis (*dfrA1-sat1-aadA1*) (Kaushik *et al.*, 2018).

Integrons associate with other mobile genetic elements that play a role in their mobilisation (Domingues

et al., 2012). Class 1 integrons associate with the ISCR1 region, capable of transferring molecules by a rolling circle mechanism, and with transposons of the *Tn3* family (Deng *et al.*, 2015), while class 2 integrons associate with *Tn7* transposons (Kaushik *et al.*, 2018), as we have observed in one of the isolates of this thesis. Normally, the conserved 3' segment contains *tns* genes, responsible for integron mobilisation through insertion into the bacterial chromosome (Gillins *et al.*, 2014). In only one of the class 2 integrons identified in this thesis, located in a *Tn7* transposon, we identified three *tns genes*.

The integrons that have been identified on the chromosome have been identified close to transposases of transposon *Tn7* and to IS30 (Integron 2.1: genetic environment A), to IS66 (Integron 2.1: genetic environment B), to IS21 (integron 1.1: genetic environment B) and to the *TnAs1* transposase of transposon *Tn3* (integron 1.4). IS21 has been described close to class 1 integrons (Valverde *et al.*, 2006; Conza *et al.*, 2010; Jones-Dias *et al.*, 2016) and class 2 integrons (Alonso *et al.*, 2018), suggesting its role in integron mobility. Gaze *et al.* (2011) identified IS30 near class 1 integrons, and these sequences may be widespread in class 1 integrons.

In terms of location, the majority of integrons (81.7%) were on plasmids, which is their most common location. Integrons do not have the ability to move, but can do so via other mobile genetic elements, primarily transferable plasmids (Sabbagh *et al.*, 2021), being transmitted within bacteria of the same species and between different bacterial species (Gillins *et al.*, 2014).

All class 2 integrons and some class 1 integrons identified in this thesis have been found in the bacterial chromosome only (integron 1.8: *bla_{OXA-1}-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1*; integron 1.3: *dfrA14*; integron 1.4: *dfrA1* and integron 1.9: *dfrA17*), while one integron was identified in both chromosome and plasmid (integron 1.1: *dfrA1-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1*). The other integrons have always been detected on plasmids. Chromosomal integrons are detected in 10% of all sequenced genomes, particularly in almost all *Vibrio* species (Richard *et al.*, 2022), a somewhat lower percentage than that observed in this thesis.

Soufi *et al.* (2009) identified in *E. coli* from broiler chickens from Tunisia a class 1 integron with the same resistance cassettes as those observed in integron 1.1 in this thesis (*dfrA1-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1*). As did Novais *et al.* (2010) and Le-Vo *et al.* (2019) in *E. coli* from sick people from different countries in Europe and Vietnam, respectively; and in *Salmonella* isolates from salmonellosis patients in Spain (Garcia *et al.*, 2010).

In this thesis, this integron was detected in IncA/C2 and IncQ plasmids. Novais *et al.* (2010), Le-Vo *et al.* (2019) and Garcia *et al.* (2010) also identified this integron in an IncA/C2 plasmid. IncQ plasmids carrying integrons have also been described in Enterobacteriaceae isolated from human clinical samples in Korea (Jeong *et al.*, 2018), Poland (Piotrowska *et al.*, 2020) and in *E. coli* in Spain (Hernández-García *et al.*, 2018), although in no case with the same resistance cassettes as those identified in the sequenced isolates;

however, integrons with the same cassettes have been identified in IncI1 (Dawes *et al.*, 2010) and IncF (Siqueira *et al.*, 2016) plasmids.

Curiao *et al.* (2011) describe an integron in *E. coli* isolates from farm animals in Switzerland that contains the cassettes observed in integron 1.2 (*aadA2-cmlA1-aadA1-sul3*) in an IncI1 plasmid, as we have found in this thesis. This integron was also found, in the isolates of this thesis, in IncH and InF plasmids. In IncH plasmids, integrons have been described in *E. coli* from diseased pigs in China, with different resistance cassettes to those of integron 1.2 (Liang *et al.*, 2022). IncH plasmids are not frequently detected in *E. coli*; however, they are found with a high frequency in *Salmonella* isolates in China, carrying class 1 integrons (Chen *et al.*, 2016; Zhao *et al.*, 2018; Shang *et al.*, 2021). In IncF plasmids, integrons with different resistance cassettes have been detected in *E. coli* from chicken, pig and calf in Norway (Sunde *et al.*, 2015) and from diseased pigs in Hungary, Czech Republic and Austria (Szmolka *et al.*, 2015).

In this thesis, integron 1.5 (*dfrA5*) has been identified in an IncF plasmid. Fricke *et al.* (2008) describe a class 1 integron with a *dfrA5* resistance cassette carried by an IncF plasmid in *E. coli* from marine sediments.

It has been estimated that empty integrons, i.e. with only the integrase gene, account for one third of all integrons (Sabbagh *et al.*, 2021). However, no empty integron has been identified in this thesis, although in three isolates a class I integrase fragment of only 341 bp was identified close to a *sul1* gene, a structure we have termed a "defective integron" in this thesis. We have found no references to these "defective" integrons.

CHAPTER 6. Plasmids

Plasmids are the most important vehicles for the spread of antibiotic resistance genes between bacteria. These mobile genetic elements can also carry other mobile genetic elements such as transposons or IS (Partridge *et al.*, 2018).

Studies detecting plasmids in *E. coli* isolates from laying hens focus on resistance to beta-lactams (Pehlivanoglu, 2017; Ceccarelli *et al.*, 2019), quinolones (Li *et al.*, 2019), colistin (Irrgang *et al.*, 2016; Zajac *et al.*, 2019), or resistance genes to the three antibiotic groups mentioned (Jochum *et al.*, 2021). However, there are no studies analysing plasmids that are not biased towards specific resistance genes. The same is true for studies in broiler chickens: Tan *et al.* (2023) study plasmids carrying genes encoding beta-lactamases; Leinyuy *et al.* (2023) resistance to quinolones, aminoglycosides and beta-lactams; or Madni *et al.* (2023) to colistin.

IncF plasmids were the most frequently detected, although not all of them carried antibiotic resistance genes. These plasmids are found only in Enterobacteriaceae (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018), being the most

frequently described plasmid type in bacterial isolates from humans and animals, mainly *E. coli*. The most commonly identified RST is F2:A-:B- (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018).

Yang *et al.* (2015) observed a high diversity among IncF plasmids identified in isolates from production animals such as poultry and pigs, and in domestic animals such as dogs and cats; in this thesis, an even higher diversity was observed. Furthermore, the study by Yang *et al.* (2015) was conducted over 10 years on 80 different farms, whereas all the RSTs observed in this thesis were detected on the same farm over a period of approximately 30 months.

Resistance genes to fluoroquinolones, aminoglycosides and beta-lactams have been described in these plasmids (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018). In addition, these plasmids usually confer multi-resistance since, being large plasmids, they often carry several different antibiotic resistance genes (Yang *et al.*, 2015). In IncF plasmids we have predominantly detected aminoglycoside (*strA/B*, *aadA1* and *aadA2*), ampicillin (*bla*_{TEM-1B}) and tetracycline (*tetA*) resistance genes; however, we have not detected fluoroquinolone resistance genes in any of them. These genes are identified on IncF plasmids in *E. coli* isolates from different sources: Szmolka *et al.* (2015) identify *aadA1* and *strA* genes in isolates from pigs with diarrhoea in Hungary; Yahia *et al.* (2018) found *bla*_{TEM-1B} and *tetA* in wild birds in Tunisia; Mbelle *et al.* (2019) *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA* and *strA* in hospitalised individuals in South Africa; Mohsin *et al.* (2017) *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA*, *aadA1* and *strA/B* in migratory birds in Germany; and Martinez-Álvarez *et al.* (2022) *bla*_{TEM-1B}, *tetA* and *aadA1* in broiler chickens in Spain.

Plasmids from the IncI incompatibility group were the second most frequent among the sequenced isolates. These plasmids have been reported to be the most frequently found in *E. coli* isolated from animals in Europe, especially chickens, carrying genes encoding ESBL and ampC (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018; Darphorn *et al.*, 2021). Most of the genes encoding ESBL and AmpC were detected in this thesis in plasmid DNA, with plasmids being the mobile genetic platform where these genes are often localised (Gekenidis *et al.*, 2020). Specifically, IncI1 plasmids have been the main platform where ESBL and ampC genes (*bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{SHV-12} and *bla*_{CMY-2}) have been detected in this study, confirming what was observed in previous studies carried out in poultry (Saliu *et al.*, 2017).

In addition, a high diversity in terms of the pMLST of these plasmids was also observed. Other studies carried out on *E. coli* and *S. enterica* isolates from animals and humans over four years in three different countries also identified high diversity (Smith *et al.*, 2015). As mentioned above, it should be noted that the diversity observed in this thesis was over two and a half years on a single farm.

As for the *bla*_{CMY-2}, it was identified in two plasmids of different incompatibility group (IncK2 and IncI1/ST12). The gene has been detected in these two plasmids in poultry *E. coli* in previous studies (Ageroso *et al.*, 2014; Saliu *et al.*, 2017; Seiffer *et al.*, 2017; Apostolakos *et al.*, 2020).

At the 5' end of the *bla*_{CMY-2} gene, an IS1380 insertion sequence, encoding the ISEcp1 transposase, was detected at the same distance (324 bp) from the gene in both plasmids in which it was identified (IncK2 and IncI1/ST12) (Figure 5.6). This structure (*bla*_{CMY-2} - ISEcp1) has been described in *E. coli* isolates from different birds in Greece (Athanasakopoulou *et al.*, 2021); in *E. coli* isolates from broiler chickens on IncI1/ST12 plasmids in Korea (Wei *et al.*, 2021); in *E. coli* isolates from broiler chickens on IncI1/ST12 plasmids in Korea (Wei *et al.*, 2021); in *Salmonella* isolates from laying hens on IncA/C2 plasmids in Japan (Shigemura *et al.*, 2021) or in *E. coli* isolates from broilers and humans in Brazil (Koga *et al.*, 2019). The fact that this *bla*_{CMY-2} - ISEcp1 structure was found in different plasmids suggests the role of ISEcp1 in the transposition of this gene between plasmids of different incompatibility group and, furthermore, ISEcp1 probably plays an important role in the dissemination of this beta-lactamase and in increasing its zoonotic potential (Athanasakopoulou *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 5.6. Comparison of the genetic environments of the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} on IncK2 and IncI1/ST12 plasmids

Furthermore, the structure detected in the IncK2 plasmid in this thesis (*sugE-blc-bla*_{CMY-2} - ISEcp1) has been described in other studies, both in IncK2 plasmids (Verdet *et al.*, 2009; Chiu *et al.*, 2021) and in IncI1/ST12 plasmids (Carattoli *et al.*, 2021), suggesting in the latter study that this structure is regulated by species-dependent host-host factors and may undergo minor rearrangements.

The *bla*_{SHV-12} gene has been identified in poultry in IncI1 plasmids from different STs, mainly ST3 and ST26 (Alonso *et al.*, 2017) as described in this thesis, although it has also been detected in plasmids from other incompatibility groups, such as IncX (Apostolakos *et al.*, 2020). In the study by Alonso *et al.* (2017), the association of IncI1/ST3 plasmids harbouring the *bla*_{SHV-12} gene with poultry is observed, and the association of IncI1/ST26 plasmids harbouring the *bla*_{SHV-12} gene with a wide range of hosts that contribute to the spread of these genes, such as dogs, humans, wild birds and also poultry.

The third incompatibility group identified was IncX, carrying ampicillin (*bla*_{TEM-1B} and *bla*_{TEM-1D}), tetracycline (*tetA*) and fluoroquinolone (*qnrS1*) resistance genes. These plasmids are widely distributed in *E. coli* isolates carrying *qnrS* genes in laying hens in Korea (Seo *et al.*, 2019), wildlife and broilers in Tunisia (Abbassi *et al.*, 2021), broilers in Italy (Niero *et al.*, 2018), pigs and calves in Germany (Juraschek *et al.*, 2021), as well as in domestic, wild and production animals and in humans and wastewater in Australia, Czech Republic, Spain, Germany, Poland, Paraguay and Slovakia (Dobiasova *et al.*, 2016) carrying fluoroquinolone (especially *qnrS* genes) and beta-lactamase resistance genes.

IncK plasmids are mainly associated with the dissemination of *bla*_{CMY-2} (as identified in this thesis) and *bla*_{CTX-M-14} genes in Europe (especially in Spain and the UK) (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018), and are frequently found in *E. coli* from animal sources (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018), including laying hens (Ceccarelli *et al.*, 2019) and broiler chickens (Seiffert *et al.*, 2017).

Other less frequent plasmids that have been identified carrying resistance genes are IncA/C, IncQ, IncH and IncN.

IncA/C plasmids are frequently found in multidrug-resistant isolates, carrying genes for resistance to sulfonamides, tetracyclines, third- and fourth-generation cephalosporins, trimethoprim and aminoglycosides (Call *et al.*, 2010; Han *et al.*, 2012; Hancock *et al.*, 2017) in human and animal isolates, including broiler chickens (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2017); in this thesis, an IncA/C2 plasmid carrying a class 1 integron consisting of *dfrA*, *aadA1*, *qacEΔ1* and *sul1* genes was identified, as discussed in the previous section.

IncQ plasmids are not common, but they can be found carrying integrons (Poirel *et al.*, 2010), as we have seen in the previous section, and genes for resistance to sulfonamides, aminoglycosides and gentamicin (Heuer *et al.*, 2002; Yau *et al.*, 2010). In this thesis, IncQ plasmids have been identified carrying, in addition to class 1 integrons (*dfrA1-aadA1-qacEΔ1-sul1*), genes conferring resistance to ampicillin (*bla*_{TEM-1B}), sulphonamides (*sul2*), tetracycline (*tetA*) and aminoglycosides (*strA/B*).

The IncH plasmids identified were two (IncHI2A and IncHI1B), carrying a class 1 integron (consisting of the *aadA2*, *cmlA1*, *addA1*, *emrE* and *sul3* genes) and a *tetA* gene, respectively. These IncHI plasmids are associated with multidrug-resistant enterobacterial isolates (especially *K. pneumoniae*) from broiler chickens, cattle, pets and wildlife (Schlüter *et al.*, 2014) in Europe, although they are more frequently found in human and environmental isolates (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018).

Finally, IncN was the least frequently identified plasmid type carrying antibiotic resistance genes. This plasmid is commonly found in animal isolates, specifically from chickens, cattle, pigs and horses and in human isolates (García-Fernández *et al.*, 2011) commonly carrying resistance genes to quinolones,

aminoglycosides, tetracyclines and genes encoding ESBLs (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018). In the isolates of this thesis we have identified an IncN plasmid carrying the multi-resistance region 14 (*qnrS1-blaTEM-1B-tetA-strA/B*). In 2011 the first IncN plasmid carrying fluoroquinolone resistance genes was described in *E. coli* isolates from production animals, namely healthy pigs, in Eastern Europe (Szmolka *et al.*, 2011) and later described in human isolates in Brazil (Segura *et al.*, 2020). The plasmid described by Szmolka *et al.* (2011) also carried the *blaTEM-1B* resistance gene. Although IncN plasmids are described as the most frequent carrier of the *blaCTX-M-1* gene in animals (Garcia-Fernandez *et al.*, 2011), it has not been identified on this farm with this gene.

In the two plasmids in which the *qnrS1* gene has been detected (IncX1 and IncN), we observed a common fragment of 6.9 Kpb in size with the same structure (*blaTEM-1B - tnpR (Tn3) - Tn2 (Tn3) - IS3 (ISEc36) - qnrS1 - ISKr94 (ISKpn19)*) (Figure 5.7). Szmolka *et al.*, (2011) describe a similar structure (*blaTEM-1B - tnpR (Tn3) - tnpA (Tn3) - qnrS1*) in an IncN plasmid. In the same way, and as we have observed in this thesis, the association of the *qnrS1* gene to the *Tn3* transposon could also facilitate its mobilisation between plasmids of different incompatibility groups, such as IncX and IncN plasmids.

Figure 5.7. Comparison of fragments of IncX1 and IncN plasmids in which MR3 and MR14 regions were detected, respectively.

Three types of plasmids (Col, p0111 and IncY) have been detected without antibiotic resistance genes. Plasmids not only confer an advantage to the host bacterium in relation to antibiotic resistance, but may also carry other beneficial genes, such as virulence genes, tolerance to heavy metals or catabolism of single nutrient sources (Carroll *et al.*, 2018). Col plasmids are the most commonly identified in this thesis, with some isolates carrying up to 12 Col-like replication origins. The copy number per cell of small plasmids such as Col plasmids can be as high as 50 or more (Clark *et al.*, 2019). These plasmids are characterised by encoding colicins, proteins whose function is to destroy other bacteria, giving the carrying bacteria a

competitive advantage (Calcuttawala *et al.*, 2021).

The p0111 plasmids have been detected in *E. coli* isolates from pig samples carrying the colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* (Duggett *et al.*, 2018); from ducks carrying *bla*_{CTX-M-2} genes (Wang *et al.*, 2022); and from humans carrying the *aadA2*, *tetA* and *dfrA12* genes (Kao *et al.*, 2018). This plasmid has also been identified carrying the genes *mdfA*, *tetA*, *qnrS1*, *dfrA14*, *sul2*, *aph(6)-Id*, *bla*_{OXA} and *bla*_{TEM} in *E. coli* from chicken samples with a frequency of almost 40% (Awoh *et al.*, 2021). In this thesis, this plasmid was found without resistance genes in 27% of the sequenced isolates, being especially detected in the laying phase. Although no antibiotic resistance genes were identified, five *virB* genes, encoding virulence proteins, which are advantageous for bacteria carrying the plasmid, were detected in all p0111 plasmids in this thesis.

Finally, IncY plasmids are a rare group of plasmids (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018). In this thesis, they were detected in 6% of isolates. These plasmids typically confer ampicillin resistance, carrying *bla*_{CTX-M-15} in *E. coli* isolates from humans (Rasheed *et al.*, 2020). They also confer colistin resistance, carrying the *mcr-1* gene in *E. coli* isolates from pigs (Zhang *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, the presence of IncY in *E. coli* has been associated with the presence in the same bacterium of plasmids from the IncF, IncI and IncHI2 incompatibility groups (Rozwandowicz *et al.*, 2018). In this thesis, 57% of isolates with an IncY plasmid also carried an IncF plasmid.

CHAPTER 7. Chromosome

Ten of the 32 resistance genes found in this thesis were identified only on the bacterial chromosome, while nine were identified on both plasmid and chromosome.

Although antibiotic resistance genes are most commonly located on plasmids, which makes them more mobile, their insertion into the bacterial chromosome removes the need for the continuous presence of antibiotics for their stability in the bacterium (Goswami *et al.*, 2020).

Wang *et al.* (2021) describe the presence of antibiotic resistance genes in both plasmids and chromosomes. Genes encoding efflux pumps (such as *tet* or *floR*) are mostly found on chromosomes; genes that alter the antibiotic target (such as *mcr-1*) in both locations; and those whose function is to replace the antibiotic target (such as *sul* or *dfr*), protect it (such as *qnr*) or inactivate the antibiotic (such as *bla*, *aadA*, *aph*, *aac* and *cat*), mostly on plasmids. Flow pumps have, in addition to a role in antibiotic resistance, other physiological functions in bacteria, which is why they are found on chromosomes, while other resistance mechanisms that do not have physiological functions (such as genes that replace or protect targets) are found on plasmids (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Wang *et al.* (2021) studied 2580 plasmid-containing genomes from three bacterial species (including *E. coli*) included in *NCBI RefSeq* and found that, in *E. coli*, 33% of the genes studied (genes for resistance to fluoroquinolones, sulfonamides, trimethoprim,

aminoglycosides, colistin and beta-lactamases) may be in both genomic locations, a percentage similar to that observed in this thesis.

The *qnrB19* gene was identified in a single isolate from laying hens. No transposase was detected in its environment that could be involved in its transposition between mobile genetic elements and chromosome, as suggested by Dionisi *et al.* (2009). Transfer of this gene to the chromosome has been previously described in *Salmonella* isolates (González *et al.*, 2013), although not in *E. coli*.

The *bla*_{CTX-M-14} gene was identified on the chromosome, the first time this gene has been described on the bacterial chromosome of poultry *E. coli* isolates, although Wang *et al.* (2021) observed that 35% of *bla*_{CTX-M-14} genes were located on the *E. coli* chromosome. ISEcp1-mediated transposition of this gene from plasmids to the *E. coli* chromosome has been demonstrated (Hamamoto *et al.*, 2019). In this thesis, the gene was detected at a distance of 80 bp from an IS903 transposase, which could be involved in the transposition of this gene between mobile genetic elements and the chromosome. Rodríguez *et al.* (2014) have described chromosomal integration of the *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and *bla*_{CTX-M-14} genes in *E. coli* isolates from clinical samples.

As indicated above, the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene has been identified in IncII/ST3 plasmids, although it has also been identified in the bacterial chromosome in this thesis. The presence of this gene has not been described in the *E. coli* chromosome, but it has been described in clinical strains of other bacterial species such as *Proteus mirabilis* (Song *et al.*, 2011) and *Enterobacter cloacae* (Liu *et al.*, 2015). Ferreira *et al.* (2014) found the *bla*_{CTX-M-2} gene in the bacterial chromosome of *E. coli*.

Kjeldsen *et al.* (2015) integrated the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene into the chromosome of an *E. coli* strain, detecting higher expression of messenger RNA when the gene was on the chromosome than when the gene was located on the native IncII plasmid, suggesting that its location on the chromosome is an advantage for the bacteria carrying the gene.

The integration of the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene into the chromosome could be mediated by the insertion sequence IS1380 (encoding the transposase ISEcp1), and was identified, in the isolates of this thesis, at 288 bp of the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene both in the plasmid (IncII/ST3) and in the chromosome (Figure 5.8). This insertion sequence was also found associated with other *bla*_{CTX-M} genes in other studies: to *bla*_{CTX-M-14} and *bla*_{CTX-M-9} in *P. mirabilis* (Song *et al.*, 2011), to *bla*_{CTX-M-2} in *E. coli* (Ferreira *et al.*, 2014) and to *bla*_{CTX-M-15} in *E. coli* (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2014), including in an IncII/ST3 plasmid (Carattoli *et al.*, 2021), suggesting that this insertion sequence plays a role in the mobilisation and chromosomal integration of CTX-M genes in this bacterial species, as described by Hamamoto *et al.* (2019) with the *bla*_{CTX-M-14} gene.

Figure 5.8. Comparison of chromosome fragments of clone 9 and IncI1/ST3 plasmid isolates in which the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene was detected [EasyFig].

Four *dfrA* genes (*dfrA1*, *dfrA17*, *dfrA36* and *dfrA14*) have been identified on the chromosome in this thesis. These genes were frequently found in chromosomal DNA, but started to be identified in plasmids in the years following the clinical introduction of trimethoprim (van Hoek *et al.*, 2011). The location of the *dfrA1*, *dfrA17* and *dfrA14* genes is discussed in the previous sections, as they have been identified in this thesis in chromosomal integrons. The *dfrA36* gene, as we have seen in the previous section, has only been identified on the bacterial chromosome (Wüthrich *et al.*, 2019).

The *catA1* (n=4) and *floR* (n=2) genes have been identified in all isolates on the bacterial chromosome. The *floR* gene has already been described on the *E. coli* chromosome (Blickwede *et al.*, 2004; Doublet *et al.*, 2005; Wang *et al.*, 2021) although, like other genes, it can be transmitted between plasmids and chromosome via *tnpA* transposases (Doublet *et al.*, 2005; Lu *et al.*, 2018). *catA1*, which is a gene that has been described on the chromosome of *E. coli* (Blickwede *et al.*, 2004; Doublet *et al.*, 2005; Wang *et al.*, 2021), 2005; Lu *et al.*, 2018). *catA1*, which is normally identified on conjugative plasmids (Dolejska *et al.*, 2011; Falgenhauer *et al.*, 2017), has also been identified on the *E. coli* chromosome (Grevskott *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2021). In the other isolates, no element (IS, transposases...) has been identified to explain its mobilisation. The *fosA7* gene (n= 2) has also been identified in this thesis only in the bacterial chromosome. Its presence in the *E. coli* chromosome has been observed in other studies (Guo *et al.*, 2016; Ito *et al.*, 2017), although it has also been identified in plasmids (Güneri *et al.*, 2022), suggesting that there is a transmission between plasmid and chromosome.

The *tetB* gene has also been detected in all isolates (n=15) on the bacterial chromosome.) These genes are most commonly identified in plasmids, although they can be transferred between chromosomes and

plasmids, as well as between different bacterial genera (Wang *et al.*, 2021); *sul1* and *sul2* can also be observed in both genomic locations (plasmid and chromosome) (Jiang *et al.*, 2019).

The *strA/B* genes have not been described in the *E. coli* chromosome, as we have seen in this thesis, although they have been described in other bacterial species such as *Xanthomonas campestris* (Zankari *et al.*, 2012).

The *bla*_{TEM-1B} gene is mostly detected in plasmids, as we have seen in the previous section, although it has been identified in the chromosome in two isolates sequenced in this thesis. This gene has been previously described on the chromosome of *E. coli* isolated from humans (Hansen *et al.*, 2019; Hubbard *et al.*, 2020).

CHEPTER 8. Resistance gene dynamics and transmission

Animal production systems are a good model for studying the dynamics and spread of antibiotic resistance genes in closed populations. There are also longitudinal studies of antibiotic resistance gene dynamics in human populations: in nasopharyngeal samples from children in South Africa (Manenzhe *et al.*, 2020), or in faecal samples from children at risk of eczema in Singapore (Loo *et al.*, 2020). Although it is almost impossible to find matching human population models.

However, studies of the dynamics of *E. coli* resistance genes in animal populations are scarce.

In laying hen farms, this issue has been analysed in four longitudinal studies (Table A.3), however, this thesis is the first longitudinal study in laying hens that includes samples from day-old chicks to the end of laying hens as well as eggs.

The first of these was carried out in Japan (Koyama *et al.*, 2020), where they sampled the farm once a month for 5 years, collecting environmental samples and focusing on plasmid-localised quinolone resistance genes (PMQR) and observing that these genes were prevalent throughout the study samples. In this thesis, these PMQR genes have also been detected in all growth stages sampled.

Two other longitudinal studies in hens were carried out in China: Zhu *et al.* (2021) analyse both animal manure and soil and manure samples from nine commercial egg production farms, sampling at different stages of the hens (growing, brooding, early-laying, peak-laying and late-laying), finding the same resistance genes at all stages; Liao *et al.* (2022) study ceftifur-resistant *E. coli* from egg samples and cloacal swabs of hens from a single layer farm, sampling at the same stages as Zhu *et al.* (2021) and finding a high prevalence of these resistant bacteria at all five stages sampled. Like Zhu *et al.* (2021) and Liao *et al.* (2022), in this thesis we identified seven resistance genes in all samplings (day-old chicks, growing pullets, laying hens and eggs).

Finally, Hess *et al.* (2022) conducted a longitudinal study in Austria in which they analysed organ samples

from laying hens with oophoritis and salpingitis for 55 weeks in 18 different farms, observing that the number of antibiotic resistant isolates increased with the age of the birds. In contrast to Hess *et al.* (2022), in this thesis we identified more resistant isolates in the first sampling (day-old chicks).

In *E. coli* broiler chickens, there are longitudinal studies of resistance gene dynamics, mostly focused on beta-lactam resistance, in farms in Spain (Jiménez-Belenguer *et al.*, 2016), Portugal (da Costa *et al.*, 2009), Germany (Laube *et al.*, 2014), the Netherlands (Huijbers *et al.*, 2016 and Van Hoek *et al.*, 2018), Japan (Koyama *et al.*, 2019), Ecuador (Hedman *et al.*, 2019), Brazil (Gazal *et al.*, 2020; Menck-Costa *et al.*, 2022) and Italy (Farooq *et al.*, 2022) (Table A.4).

Studies of resistance gene transmission in the production pyramid also focus on resistance to these antibiotics (Nilsson *et al.*, 2014; Mo *et al.*, 2014; Zurfluh *et al.*, 2014; Dame-Korevaar *et al.*, 2017; Apostolakos *et al.*, 2019; Gupta *et al.*, 2021 and Liu *et al.*, 2021) (Table A.4).

Day-old chicks are a source of entry of resistance genes into the farm, being the sample in which most multi-drug resistant isolates have been detected. These multi-resistant bacteria spread during the production cycle between animals and eggs from different samples and flocks. Numerous longitudinal studies in broiler farms have produced results that support this theory.

Nilsson *et al.* (2013) observed that the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} in imported breeding animals on one farm was transmitted along the production pyramid. Huijbers *et al.* (2016) studied ESBL-producing *E. coli* in different samples from an organic broiler farm during two consecutive production cycles and observed that day-old chicks positive for these resistance genes play a role in the on-farm introduction of ESBL-producing *E. coli*. Da Costa *et al.* (2009) observed that, 4 days after placement of day-old chicks on the farm, 14 new resistance profiles were found, which were maintained until the end of the study (33 days), while new patterns were found.

Jiménez-Belenguer *et al.* (2016) suggest the possibility that the high percentages of antibiotic resistance observed in day-old chicks that have not previously been in contact with antibiotics are due to vertical transmission of resistance genes from the parental flocks, and that these day-old chicks in turn have the ability to transmit these genes down the production pyramid. Van Hoek *et al.* (2018) identified the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene in day-old chicks entering the farm, as well as in subsequent sampling. Apostolakos *et al.* (2019) studied the transfer of ESBL-producing *E. coli* on three broiler farms in four different samplings over one year, detecting the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} at all levels of the broiler production pyramid and identifying the highest prevalence of this gene in imported chicks on the farm. Hedman *et al.* (2019) identified more multidrug-resistant isolates in chick bacteria than in adult broilers, as we have observed in this thesis.

In addition, it is likely that there is another reservoir of these bacteria on the farm as resistance genes were

found even after disinfection of the farm between different batches.

Dame-Korevar *et al.* (2017) studied ESBL-producing *E. coli* from cloacal swabs, intestinal contents, eggs and environmental samples during the rearing and laying periods and at decension in a broiler farm, observing that, although the prevalence of the *bla*_{CMY-2} gene in faeces decreased over time in faeces, its prevalence did not decrease in environmental samples, constituting the pens as a reservoir for these genes. In this thesis, however, we have detected ESBL genes, including *bla*_{CMY-2} in faecal samples from all growth stages of the hens and the farm itself may be a reservoir for these genes, as indicated by Dame-Korevar *et al.* (2017), the farm environment.

Gupta *et al.* (2021) also observed more resistant bacteria in environmental samples than in cloacal swab samples in a study conducted over 41 days on a broiler farm and, in addition, identified more resistant bacteria in late samples than in early samples.

Gazal *et al.* (2020) analysed, for 38 days (3 samples), samples of cloacal swabs, litter, feed, water and beetles present in five farms, identifying ESBL-producing *E. coli* in the three samples of litter samples, and beetles; and non-ESBL-producing *E. coli* in the three samples of water, litter, swabs and feed samples. Thus, in these farms, water, feed, litter and even beetles act as reservoirs of different resistance genes.

However, and contrary to what we have seen in this thesis and in previously mentioned studies, in the study by Liu *et al.* (2021) in which they study *E. coli* from cloacal swabs of chickens at days 1-2, 17-20 and 35-40, they identify a lower percentage of resistance in the first samples. Therefore, the on-farm entry of multidrug-resistant bacteria in the six farms studied by Liu *et al.* (2021) must not be day-old chicks, but there must be an alternative route of entry. This same pattern was observed in a broiler farm in Israel, as discussed above (Gupta *et al.*, 2021).

Farooq *et al.* (2022) carried out a longitudinal study in 4 conventional and 4 intensive broiler farms, in which they obtained litter samples at the beginning and at the end of the cycle, observing no significant differences in resistance percentages, as we have seen in this thesis, neither between the different samples, nor between the different types of farms.

Longitudinal studies of *E. coli* resistance have also been conducted in other birds such as Alaskan gulls (Ahlstrom *et al.*, 2018), geese in Italy (Massaccesi *et al.*, 2021), sentinel ducks in Germany (Dreyer *et al.*, 2022), broiler ducks in Thailand (Assawatheptawee *et al.*, 2022) and migratory birds in Korea (Song *et al.*, 2022) (Table A.3).

Ahlstrom *et al.* (2018), Dreyer *et al.* (2022) and Song *et al.* (2022) study wildlife samples and claim that migratory birds are a potential source of antibiotic resistance dissemination.

Massaccesi *et al.* (2021) conducted a longitudinal study on a goose farm observing that geese can contaminate the farm environment with antibiotic resistant bacteria and that the transmission of these bacteria could be reduced by reducing the density of the animals.

Looking at the environment and the location of resistance genes, this thesis has observed eleven transmission patterns in the *E. coli* population studied, which we have termed "Russian doll" patterns, involving several elements at overlapping levels: MR regions and integrons, which cluster resistance genes, and plasmids and clones, which contain them (Figure 5.4 and table A.4). In this thesis, we consider transmission to have occurred when we have identified clonal isolates in at least two different samples, or resistance genes, plasmids, integrons or regions in at least two isolates from different samples.

The simplest transmission models include a single element identified in at least two different samples: MR region (1), integron (2), plasmid (3) or clone (4) (Figure 5.4). Five models include two different elements: resistance genes included in MR regions transmitted either by plasmids (5) or by clones (6); resistance genes included in integrons located in plasmids (7) or in the chromosome of clones (8); and resistance genes in plasmids and transmitted in clones (9). Finally, more complex transmission models include three different elements: resistance genes in MR regions within a plasmid transmitted in clonal isolates (10) and resistance genes in an integron carried by a plasmid and transmitted through clones (11) (Figure 5.9) (Table A.4).

Figure 5.9. Transmission patterns of antibiotic resistance genes detected in *E. coli* on farm. AR: Antibiotic resistance

Table A.4 in the annex shows the transmission patterns followed by each of the genes that have been identified in more than one sampling.

Clonal transmission

Tenaillon *et al.* (2010) review the population structure of commensal *E. coli* in humans describing that, despite recombination events, the population structure is predominantly clonal.

A study carried out in poultry, including laying hens, suggests that the bacterial population is more diverse in these animal species than in other production species, such as pigs and calves, with poultry *E. coli* populations not showing a clonal population structure (Leekitcharoenphon *et al.*, 2021). As in the latter study, although 30 clones have been detected and, as we have seen, play a role in the transmission of antibiotic resistance, clonal populations do not seem to be predominant in the microbiota of the animals included in this study.

Studies on clonal dissemination in *E. coli* exist, although they focus either on specific clones or on clones carrying specific resistance genes in animals: Schauer *et al.* (2016) study clonal transfer of ESBL-producing ST140 isolates in poultry and Falgenhauer *et al.* (2019) study clonal isolates transmitted between poultry and humans. In human studies, Banerjee *et al.* (2013) and Khoshbayan *et al.* (2022) studied ST131 clonal isolates in clinical samples and Adler *et al.* (2012) and Dehkharghani *et al.* (2021) studied clonal transmission in ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

Studies in poultry samples (Schauer *et al.* 2016; Falgenhauer *et al.*, 2019; Bojesen *et al.*, 2020) warn of the importance of studying clonal transmission, as ST410 or ST10 clones are implicated in the transmission of multidrug-resistant isolates: Schauer *et al.* (2016) describe ESBL-producing ST140 isolates identified in birds, dogs, environment and humans, noting cross-species transmission and, stressing the importance of not basing studies solely on the spread of multi-resistance caused by transmission by plasmids or other mobile genetic elements; Falgenhauer *et al.* (2019) describe that poultry farms are sources of ESBL-producing bacteria, as clonal *E. coli* ST10 isolates have been identified in both farms and humans, resulting in clonal transmission between species; finally, Bojesen *et al.* (2020) identified an ST10 clone in a broiler unit implicated in multiple outbreaks. These ST10 isolates are associated with extraintestinal infections in humans.

Nilsson *et al.* (2014) identified the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} in grandparent chickens imported for breeding, this being the entry point of that gene into the production pyramid, as we have seen above. Furthermore, at all levels of the pyramid they identified an *E. coli* clone carrying this gene on a plasmid; thus, as we have seen in this thesis, Nilsson *et al.* (2014) identify in the broiler production pyramid a "Russian doll" type transmission model involving clonal isolates carrying the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} (Model 9).

Bojesen *et al.* (2020) studied the persistence of ST10 *E. coli* in a broiler farm, identifying ST10 isolates over 18 months.

In this thesis, clones were found at intervals of up to 19 months on the farm and, in 10 of the 30 clones identified, we detected at least one egg isolate, whereby clonal isolates present in day-old chicks, growing pullets and/or laying hens may eventually pass into the eggshell.

In some of the clones, intraclonal diversity has been observed, with losses or gains of resistance genes, some of them located on plasmids; multi-resistance regions or integrons, occurring among isolates of the same clone. Stegger *et al.* (2020) studied clonal isolates from urine of people with urinary tract infections and faeces of healthy people and observed intraclonal diversity, with some isolates from the same clone diverging by up to 15 genes.

Although the transmission of several clones has been detected on the farm, only five resistance genes following a purely clonal transmission have been observed in the thesis (transmission model 4): *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *sul2*, detected at an interval of 14 months in clones 9 and 13 (with isolates from both clones being identified in different batches), respectively; *tetB* and *fosA7*, detected at an interval of 5 months in clone 24 (with isolates from the clone being identified in different batches); and *catA1*, detected at an interval of one month in isolates from clone 15 from the same batch.

Horizontal gene transmission

Resistance genes were mainly detected in mobile genetic elements carried by unrelated isolates. Plasmids, in particular, were the mobile genetic elements most implicated in the transmission of resistance genes in the farm studied. These extrachromosomal elements are a major contributor to the bacterial cell acquiring and transmitting antibiotic resistance genes and virulence genes (Bennet, 2008; Bozcal, 2018).

Neither integrons (Gillings *et al.*, 2014) nor multi-resistance regions (Partridge, 2011) have the ability to move on their own, however, both elements have been identified in non-clonal isolates on farm in more than one sampling, with transmission occurring between animals on farm. Multi-resistance regions and integrons can persist, evolve and be transmitted via transposases and insertion sequences (Partridge, 2011; Partridge *et al.*, 2018).

One of the regions was found on the chromosome of clonal isolates adjacent to an IS26 transposase, while the transmission of most of the regions is explained by their location on plasmids (carried by clonal isolates and unrelated isolates), which is the most common location of these resistance structures (Partridge, 2011).

In some longitudinal studies, plasmid-mediated transmission of certain resistance genes has been observed, including some of the specific models we have identified in this thesis.

Mo *et al.* (2014) observed that plasmid-mediated AmpC-producing *E. coli* were identified at all levels of the broiler production pyramid, so the transmissibility of these bacteria in the production pyramid studied

by Mo *et al.* (2014) was primarily due to the role of plasmids.

In a study carried out at different levels of the broiler production pyramid in France (Zurfluh *et al.*, 2014) identified IncI1/ST3 plasmids carrying *bla*_{CTX-M-1} genes in unrelated isolates (Model 3), as we have identified in this thesis, collected at different levels of the pyramid. This study provides evidence for vertical transmission of these plasmids from a common source. This same transmission pattern (*bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene on IncI1/ST3 plasmids carried by non-clonal isolates) has been identified in a broiler farm in the Netherlands (van Hoek *et al.*, 2018). Baron *et al.* (2018) conducted studies in two broiler farms, and also identified the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene on an IncI1/ST3 plasmid. Clonal transmission of the gene was not described, although some of the isolates in which the gene was detected belonged to the same phylogroup, suggesting that the spread of the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene in this type of farm is primarily plasmid-mediated.

Dame-Korevar *et al.* (2017) detected the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} carried by IncA/C2 plasmids in a flock of breeding hens for a longer period of time (up to week 33) than observed in our study in either of the plasmids in which it was identified (IncX and IncI1/ST26), however, it was not detected in the laying phase, as detected in this thesis. Interestingly, although it was identified over a long period of time on an IncA/C2 plasmid, the authors pointed out that the inability to persist in animals could be due to an ineffective combination of *bla*_{CMY-2} and the IncA/C plasmids.

Some non-longitudinal studies have also identified what we have termed "Russian doll" models. Chen *et al.* (2019) identified *bla*_{TEM-1D} genes in plasmid DNA carried by ST131 clonal isolates. In this thesis we identified the *bla*_{TEM-1D} gene together with *tetA* (MR4) in IncX plasmids in isolates of clone 9 (Transmission model 10).

Alonso *et al.* (2017) detected *E. coli* ST23 and ST57 clones carrying the *bla*_{SHV-12} gene that are widely distributed in different settings (including clinical settings). This study also detected ST131 clones, associated with CTX-M production, suggesting the existence of potentially epidemic clones carrying plasmids with antibiotic resistance genes, describing that both clonal and plasmid transfer facilitate the spread of *bla*_{SHV-12} genes, as we have observed in this thesis since, in the sequenced isolates, the *bla*_{SHV-12} gene has been transmitted by plasmid (transmission model 3) and by the plasmid-clone binomial (transmission model 9). Coque *et al.* (2008) also describe a Russian doll model in the *bla*_{CTX-M-15} gene: they identify this IncF plasmid gene carried by ST131 and ST405 clones.

Blaak *et al.* (2015) and Baez *et al.* (2021) detect the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene in *E. coli* isolates from up to 11 different MLST profiles in laying hen isolates. Furthermore, a study by Mo *et al.* (2020) in poultry confirms the occurrence of this gene in isolates from different MLSTs, suggesting that the main form of transmission of this gene is not clonal.

Agersø *et al.* (2014), Alonso *et al.* (2017) and Apostolakos *et al.* (2020) agree that the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} is mainly transmitted by plasmids, although they also provide information on the clonal spread of *bla*_{CMY-2}, as we have detected in this thesis, in which we have identified the plasmid-borne *bla* gene_{CMY-2} in both non-clonal isolates (transmission model 3) and clonal isolates (transmission model 9).

Roer *et al.* (2019) describe another "Russian doll" model: an ST131 clone carrying IncI1/ST12 plasmids with the *bla* gene_{CMY-2} identified in different countries and in samples from different origins (meat products, humans and broilers), determining that this clone is also a zoonotic source of the resistance gene *bla*_{CMY-2}.

As for integrons, 24 of the 44 we identified were detected either in non-clonal isolates or in only one isolate of a clone. Therefore, their on-farm transmission between isolates did not correspond to clonal transmission. Integron flanking insertion sequences and transposases play a role in the mobilisation of integrons between chromosomes of different bacteria and between plasmids and chromosomes (Domingues *et al.*, 2012).

The persistence of integrons on the farm could be explained by their low energetic cost because, as mentioned above, the promoter is not expressed in the absence of antibiotics, due to the SOS inhibition system, which prevents expression (Gillins *et al.*, 2014; Lacotte *et al.*, 2017). Engelstädter *et al.* (2016) demonstrated that functional integrase integrons can be stably maintained in the population despite fitness costs. This selective advantage is due to the fact that gene mixing generates genetic diversity, which allows the population to respond quickly to changing selective pressures. In addition, horizontal gene transfer favours the stable maintenance of integrase.

As we have seen, the transmission of resistance genes in this farm where there is no selective pressure for antibiotic use is complex, with some of the genes following up to four different transmission patterns and up to three different elements found in the most complex transmission patterns (11 and 12).

In this thesis, we have identified 12 resistance genes in eggshell isolates, finding seven of them in all growth stages studied. The persistence of these resistance genes in the egg production cycle poses a threat to public health, as these resistant bacteria identified on the surface of eggs can pass into eggs through tiny cracks, as suggested by Fernet *et al.* (2011) in a study in which they analysed *Enterococcus faecalis* in broiler eggs.

7. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

FIRST: E. coli MLST profile data allow better estimation of bacterial diversity compared to phenotypic antibiotic resistance profile data, as the same resistance profile is found in different MLST profiles.

SECOND: The high values of the diversity index used (Simpson's index) indicate that the number of *E. coli* isolates analyzed per sample (between eight and ten) is sufficient to estimate bacterial diversity in the type of samples analyzed.

THIRD: The detection of antibiotic resistance genes in *E. coli* in day-old chicks indicates that hatcheries are sources of entry of antibiotic resistance genes into egg production farms, but not the only source, as the finding of other resistance genes in subsequent sampling indicates that other sources exist.

FOURTH: The detection of antibiotic resistant *E. coli* isolates in eggshells marks a pathway for their entry into the food chain.

FIFTH. The detection and genetic characterisation of a wide range of resistance profiles in *E. coli* throughout the commercial egg production cycle points to the desirability of adding this indicator bacterial-animal species binomial to surveillance programmes for antibiotic resistance in animals.

SIXTH: Transmission of resistance genes in *E. coli* in commercial production farms is mediated primarily by plasmids and, to a lesser extent, by clones.

SEVENTH: Although isolates resistant to cephalosporins, antibiotics declared to be of clinical importance, do not seem to be predominant in laying hens in this type of farms, their presence and dissemination in clones and in mobile genetic elements makes it necessary to monitor them.

FUTURE WORK AND PERSPECTIVES

This thesis opens up other possible future work. Firstly, it shows that resistance gene monitoring in laying hens should be more frequent. Although resistance levels are not as high as in other farm species, the presence of clinically important antibiotic resistant bacteria demonstrates the need to include these farms in future longitudinal antibiotic resistance studies.

Possible further studies could focus on day-old chick suppliers as we have shown that these animals are a source of input to the farm. In addition, further studies could focus on, besides the animals, the farm environment as well as on animals living with the hens (insects, rodents), to discover the reservoirs of resistant bacteria on these farms.

8. PhD project self-evaluation

The objectives that were set at the beginning of the project have mostly been achieved. Deliverables D-E14-5.1 (List of plasmids putatively present on *E. coli* isolated) and D-E14-6.1 (List of *E. coli* from animals isolates to be sequenced) were delayed because of the coronavirus pandemic. For deliverable 6.1 we needed to perform antimicrobial susceptibility studies to obtain phenotypic profiles of interest for sequencing. The impossibility of accessing the laboratory during the months of lockdown delayed the completion of the antibiograms. For the same reason, deliverable D-E14-6.2 was delayed from September 2020 to July 2021. This manuscript, already published, contained data on cefotaxime-resistant isolates, for which we had to perform antibiotic susceptibility testing and subsequent sequencing. The postponement in laboratory work and, therefore, in obtaining the list of isolates to be sequenced, meant that the manuscript had to be delayed. In addition, the whole genomic sequencing (WGS) of isolates was carried out in another institute that was also affected by the pandemic. Deliverable D-E14-7.1 (A list of *E. coli* from eggs to be sequenced) was produced one month ahead of schedule. Deliverable D-E14-8.1 (Manuscript) was delayed from June 2021 to February 2022, yet it has not yet been delivered. And thesis draft (D-E14-9.1) was scheduled for December 2021 but is being delivered in October 2022. The reason that these two deliverables have been delayed so much is because of the backlog of previous deliverables. In addition, due to the end of the grant, the student started working in another research centre, so she did not have enough time to finish the draft of the thesis in the scheduled month. Deliverable 8.1 will be supplied after the completion of the draft thesis document.

As far as milestones are concerned, all of them have been achieved. Milestone 1 (Updated list of phenotypic features of the *E. coli* isolates collection) was achieved on time. Milestone 2 (Training of the PhD-student on bioinformatic analysis of raw sequences) was achieved in September 2019, when the student carried out the short-term mission in Denmark. Milestone 3 (New sequenced *E. coli* isolates from animals) was delayed from September 2020 to April 2021. As indicated above, the deliverable associated with this milestone was delayed due to the impossibility of accessing the laboratory. In addition, the external institute carrying out the sequencing was affected by the pandemic and accumulated a heavy workload. The last milestone (4) was also delayed: although the list of isolates to be sequenced was delivered ahead of schedule, sequencing was postponed due to the reason discussed above.

Overall, and albeit with some delay, all deliverables and milestones (except deliverable 8.1) have been successfully achieved.

9. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
PhD1-AMR2-ECO-HEN	D-E14-5.1.	A list of plasmids putatively present on <i>E. coli</i> isolates	M27 (March 2020)	M31 (May 2020)		
	D-E14-6.1	A list of <i>E. coli</i> from animals isolates to be sequenced	M28 (April 2020)	M33 (July 2020)		
	D-E14-6.2.	Manuscript	M33 (September 2020)	M43 (July 2021)	https://zenodo.org/record/6626506	
	D-E14-7.1.	A list of <i>E. coli</i> from eggs to be sequenced	M37 (January 2021)	M36 (December 2020)		
	D-E14-8.1.	Manuscript	42 (June 2021)	-		
	D-E14-9.1.	Doctoral thesis draft	48 (December 2021)	M58 (October 2022)	Be aware that this is the first draft of the PhD thesis and that this document must be fully revised, corrected and improved before be public available.	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
PhD1-AMR2-ECO-HEN	M-E14-1	Updated list of phenotypic features of the <i>E. coli</i> isolates collection	M15 (March 2019)		Yes	
	M-E14-2	Training of the PhD-student on bioinformatic analysis of raw sequences	M17 (May 2019)		Yes	10.5281/zenodo.5708230
	M-E14-3	New sequenced <i>E. coli</i> isolates from animals	M33 (September 2020)		Yes	
	M-E14-4	New sequenced <i>E. coli</i> isolates from eggs	M37 (January 2021)		Yes	

10. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.),

11. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

12. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

Doing her PhD thesis within the OHEJP project has allowed the student to get to know the work of other people working in the same and related research fields. It also allowed her to do a short term mission in which she was able to acquire knowledge to use in her own work. She has also been able to share her project with other colleagues in the 3-minute thesis competitions, and to present the project at the conferences organised by the OHEJP that she was able to attend. In addition, she has attended several workshops and seminars given by members of the OHEJP project.

13. Transferrable skills and Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
<i>Whole bacterial genome sequencing. Tools and applications</i>	<i>Bioinformatics</i>	<i>February 2019</i>	<i>DTU</i>
<i>EURL-Training course on antimicrobial resistance</i>	<i>Antimicrobial resistance</i>	<i>24/09/2019-27/09/2019</i>	<i>EURL-AR Network</i>
<i>Specialisation diploma of in bioinformatics analysis</i>	<i>Bioinformatics</i>	<i>07/10/2019-22/06/2020</i>	<i>Universidad Pablo Olavide de Sevilla (UPO)</i>
<i>Spreadsheets with EXCEL I</i>	<i>Informatics</i>	<i>01/01/2020-01/05/2020</i>	<i>Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM)</i>
<i>Epidemiological and statistical aspects of a research</i>	<i>Epidemiology</i>	<i>03/03/2020-09/06/2020</i>	<i>UCM</i>
<i>Biosecurity seminar</i>	<i>Biosecurity</i>	<i>15/06/2021</i>	<i>UCM</i>

<i>Digital innovations for One Health Practitioners</i>	<i>Digital innovations</i>	<i>15/02/2021-18/02/2021</i>	<i>OHEJP, BfR</i>
<i>Research career conference</i>	<i>Research</i>	<i>14/01/2021, 18/01/2021</i>	<i>UCM</i>
<i>One Health EJP Communications and Media Workshop</i>	<i>Communications</i>	<i>05/10/2020-06/10/2020</i>	<i>OHEJP</i>
<i>ASM Satellite Workshop</i>	<i>Digital Innovation and Data Management</i>	<i>21/05/2019</i>	<i>OHEJP</i>
<i>Python data visualization</i>	<i>Informatic</i>	<i>14/09/2020-15/12/2020</i>	<i>UCM</i>
<i>Summer school</i>	<i>Environmental Issues in One Health: from risk assessment to surveillance</i>	<i>26/07/2021-06/08/2021</i>	<i>OHEJP, Instituto Superiore di Sanità</i>
<i>Advanced workshop on bioinformatics and omics data analysis in R</i>	<i>Bioinformatics</i>	<i>24/04/2022-29/04/2022</i>	<i>UCM</i>
<i>Spreadsheets with EXCEL II</i>	<i>Informatics</i>	<i>11/06/2021-31/10/2021</i>	<i>UCM</i>
<i>Visavet journal Club</i>	<i>Scientific articles discussion</i>		<i>Visavet, UCM</i>

14. Ethical Reviews

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020

15. Scientific Publications

Publication date	Publication title	Authors	DOI reference	Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? *please specify embargo length	Is it a Gold Open Access?
July 2022	Clonal and plasmid-mediated flow of ESBL/AmpC genes in <i>Escherichia coli</i> in a commercial laying hen farm	Irene Aldea, Alicia Gibello, Marta Hernández, Pimlapas Leekitcharoenphon, Valeria Bortolaia, Miguel A. Moreno	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2022.109453	https://zenodo.org/record/6626506	Yes, in funding section		Yes

16. Additional Outputs

- Participation in congresses:

- Poster presentation:

1. One Health EJP ASM 2020 (27/05/2020-29/05/2020): First report of trimethoprim resistance gene *dfrA36* on an IncF-plasmid in *Escherichia coli* isolated from day-old chicks:

<https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

2. One Health EJP ASM 2021 (09/06/2021-11/09/2021): Dynamics of extended spectrum β -lactamase resistance gene *bla_{SHV-12}* in a laying hen commercial farm:

https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/OHEJP2021_Abstractbook.pdf

3. One Health EJP ASM 2022 (11/04/2022-13/04/2022): Putative APEC isolates from healthy animals and eggs in a laying-hen commercial farm:

https://ohejp2022.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/OHEJPASM-ABSTRACT-BOOK_07.04.pdf

- Oral presentation:

1. XXVII Microbiology Spanish Society National Congress of Microbiology (28/06/2021-02/07/2021): *bla_{CMY-2}* gene dynamics in a commercial egg production farm

<https://congresoSEM21.es/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/XVIII-Congreso-Nacional-de-Microbiologi%CC%81a-FINAL-7.pdf>

- Seminars:

- The student gave a seminar on her thesis project to her fellow students of the doctoral school of veterinary medicine (UCM)

- Other:

- 3MT Thesis: The student participated in the three-minute thesis competition held at the OHEJP annual congresses in 2020, 2021 and 2022.

17. **Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications**

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

The highlights of the deliverable D-E14-6.2 (VETMIC-2022 publication <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2022.109453> -) deserve special attention for better understanding of the complexity of AMR determinants flow in commercial food producing systems:

- . Flow of ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* in the studied layer farm showed a clone-plasmid mixed model.
- . *bla*_{CTX-M-1} *bla*_{SHV-12} and *bla*_{CMY-2} were the predominant detected genes.
- . The ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* persisted in the farm for between six and 15 months.
- . Environmental sources of ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* must be found.

The models for AMR flow described in this publication are not limited to ESBL/AmpC genes but also detected with other AMR genes (manuscript in preparation).

Some of these AMR genes has been detected in *E. coli* from the shell of eggs posing a putative public health concern.

European monitoring of AMR in animals should consider the inclusion of commensal *E. coli* from laying hens as a valuable AMR indicator.

18. One Health impact

The study of antibiotic resistance on a layer farm and its impact on the One Health perspective for national and international policy makers is of utmost importance because of the implications for public health. The findings of this study strongly reveal that resistant bacteria persist on the farm even in the absence of antibiotics and have the ability to be transmitted through eggs. This transmission of resistant bacteria through poultry products can lead to serious health problems both locally and globally.

In this context, the One Health approach becomes central to addressing the problem of antibiotic resistance in animal husbandry, including laying hens. The One Health approach recognises the interconnection between human, animal and environmental health, and highlights the need to address these problems in a holistic and collaborative manner. National and international policy makers play a crucial role in implementing effective policies and regulations to address antibiotic resistance in poultry production.

It is essential that policy makers promote measures that restrict the unnecessary use of antibiotics in animal husbandry and encourage responsible management practices. Robust surveillance and monitoring systems must be put in place to detect and control the presence of resistant bacteria on poultry farms as well as in poultry products for human consumption. In addition, research and development of alternatives to antibiotics in animal husbandry, such as improved hygienic conditions and the use of probiotics, should be promoted.

19. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	3MT thesis
Date:	2020/2021/2022

Place:	Online event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Digital Innovations for One Health Practitioners
Date:	15 th -19 th February 2021

Place:	Online event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	

Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	XXVII Microbiology Spanish Society National Congress of Microbiology
Date:	6 th -8 th July 2021

Place:	Online event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 of One Health EJP
Date:	9 th -11 th June 2021

Place:	Online event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	2 nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme
Date:	May 27 th - 29 th , 2020,

Place:	Online event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	

Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting
Date:	May 22nd-24th 2019.

Place:	Dublin		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	VII Jornada VETINDOC - 5º PhDay Complutense
Date:	7 October 2021

Place:	Madrid		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Summer School 2021
Date:	26 th July-6 th August 2021

Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	

Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

